

**INVESTIGATING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TERTIARY EDUCATION AND
ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN NIGERIA**

ADEWUYI SAMUEL AKINOLA

**Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the
requirements of the University of the West of Scotland
for the award of Doctor of Business Administration**

August 2021

Declaration

I declare that this Thesis in part or as a whole has not been submitted by me or someone else to any institution of learning toward any degree in any part of the world.

Abstract

The extant literature establishes entrepreneurship as a source of innovation and change for productivity, economic growth, and competitiveness. Similarly, education is credited as an indispensable and sustainable mechanism of individual and collective development based on knowledge and skills channelling. Thus, educational training and development in all industries and nations have been crucial to entrepreneurship development, especially in tertiary education. Education and entrepreneurship intersect and coexist as agents of the economic development of any nation in a broader context. In the same vein, the Nigerian government has embedded entrepreneurship into its 2004 tertiary education reform, but little research has examined the interplay between tertiary education and entrepreneurship. Therefore, the researcher explored phenomena with a mixed methods research approach, using secondary data gathered from the Global Entrepreneurship and Development Institute (GEDI) and collected primary data through a survey of graduate entrepreneurs in Nigeria. The findings include (1) a positive relationship between the level of entrepreneurs and outturns of tertiary institution graduates in Nigeria, (2) evidence of a negative relationship between entrepreneurship and types of Nigerian graduate jobs, (3) no evidence of a correlation between entrepreneurship and tertiary education, (4) established favourable influences of tertiary education on entrepreneurial skills development in Nigeria, and (5) a positive relationship between educated entrepreneurs and successful entrepreneurs in Nigeria. In that light, the study has helped to understand the interplay of tertiary education and entrepreneurship, which may provide a basis for strategic managers and policymakers in the education sector to promote long-term sustainable business development and socioeconomic growth.

Dedication

I dedicate this doctoral degree to the Sovereign, the God Almighty.

Acknowledgement

I would like to acknowledge my latter and former lead supervisors' Dr Mizan Rahman and Dr Khalid Bichou, for your guidance and corrections; I am grateful.

I thank my viva examiners team. The chair, Dr Shehzad Ahmed, for encouragement and leadership. The internal and external examiners Dr Daba Chowdhury and Dr Obby Phiri, for the comments and suggestions.

I appreciate my family - my wife, Bunmi Victoria Akinola and my children Faith and Triumphant Akinola for their understanding, love, and support throughout this program and always.

I am grateful to my Big Daddy family, Mr and Mrs Olatunji and Ayodele Akinola for their emotional and financial support.

Also, I am grateful to everyone who has supported me in a different capacity throughout this programme; thank you all.

Table of Contents

Declaration	i
Abstract.....	ii
Dedication	iii
Acknowledgement	iv
Table of Contents	v
List of Figures	xi
List of Tables.....	xiii
CHAPTER ONE: GENERAL INTRODUCTION.....	1
1.1 Background	1
1.2 Research Gaps and Motivation	1
1.3 Research Aims and Objectives	4
1.4 Research Questions and Hypotheses	5
1.5 Significant Contributions of Study.....	6
1.6 Structure of the Thesis.....	7
CHAPTER TWO: THE CONTEXT OF NIGERIAN TERTIARY EDUCATION	9
2.1 Nigerian Tertiary Education System	9
2.1.1 University Education System in Nigeria	10
2.1.2 Polytechnics Education System in Nigeria.....	11
2.1.3 Monotechnic Education System in Nigeria.....	11
2.1.4 Innovation Enterprise Institutions (IEIs) in Nigeria	13

2.1.5 Vocational Enterprise Institutions (VEIs) in Nigeria.....	13
2.1.6 Technical Colleges in Nigeria.....	14
2.1.7 Issues and Challenges with Nigerian Tertiary Education Institutions	15
2.2 Account of Students Enrolment and Graduates of Nigeria’s Tertiary Institutions.	17
2.3 Applications of Entrepreneurship Education in Nigeria	18
2.3.1 Historical of the Nigerian Entrepreneurship Education System.....	18
2.3.2 Nigerian Transition from Traditional Entrepreneurship System and Effects .	19
2.3.3 Nigerian New System of Entrepreneurship Education.....	22
2.3.4 Modern-Day Nigerian Entrepreneurship Education Effects and Challenges ...	23
2.4 Summary	26
CHAPTER THREE: LITERATURE REVIEW ON ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND EDUCATION	27
3.1 The Facets of Entrepreneurship.....	27
3.1.1 Definitions of Entrepreneurship.....	28
3.1.2 Entrepreneurship Classifications.....	30
3.1.3 Basic Forms of Entrepreneurship	33
3.2 Theoretical Framework.....	34
3.2.1 Theory of Economic Development.....	35
3.2.2 Need for Achievement Theory.....	37
3.2.3 Theory of Social Change.....	38
3.2.4 Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB).....	39
3.3 Significance of Education and Entrepreneurship and Interplay Between Them....	40

3.3.1 Significance of Education.....	40
3.3.2 Significance of Entrepreneurship.....	42
3.3 Interplay Between Education and Entrepreneurship.....	43
3.3.4 Empirical Evidence on the Relationship Between Education and Entrepreneurship.....	44
3.4 Measurement of Entrepreneurship	45
3.4.1 Global Entrepreneurship Index (GEI).....	46
3.5 Conceptual Framework.....	49
3.6 Development of Research Questions and Hypotheses	51
3.7 Chapter Summary and Conclusions.....	56
CHAPTER FOUR: RESEARCH APPROACH AND METHODOLOGY.....	59
4.1. Research Philosophy	59
4.2 Research Approaches.....	61
4.3 The Process of Research Design.....	62
4.3.1 Methodological Choice.....	63
4.3.2 Purpose of the Study	65
4.3.3 Research Strategies.....	67
4.3.4 Times Horizons and Milestones.....	73
4.3.5 Access Issues and Ethical Considerations.....	74
4.4 Research Methods.....	75
4.4.1 Sources of Data Collection.....	76

4.4.2 Types of Data Collection	77
4.4.3 Sampling Design.....	77
4.4.3.1 Research Population	78
4.4.3.2 Research Sampling Unit.....	79
4.4.3.3 Research Sampling Frame	79
4.4.3.4 Research Sample Size Determination	80
4.4.3.5 The Study Sample.....	83
4.4.3.5.1 Probability Sampling Techniques.....	84
4.4.3.5.2 Non-Probability Sampling Techniques.....	87
4.4.3.5.3 Sampling Techniques Adopted for this Study.....	90
4.4.4 Data Collection Methods	91
4.4.4.1 Secondary Data Collection Methods	91
4.4.4.2 Primary Data Collection Methods.....	92
4.4.4.2.1 Survey Method.....	92
4.4.4.2.2 Questionnaire.....	93
4.4.5 Research Instruments Measurement.....	94
4.5 Summary of Research Approach and Methodology	98
CHAPTER FIVE: DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS	100
5.1 Secondary Data Collected	100
5.1.1 Global Entrepreneurship Index (GEI).....	100

5.1.1.1 The Global Entrepreneurship Index Ranking of the Five Selected Countries	104
5.1.2 Summary of Higher Institutions in Nigeria.....	105
5.1 Primary Data Collected.....	106
5.1.1 Statistical Presentation and Analysis of the Survey Responses	106
CHAPTER SIX: RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	118
6.1 General Characteristics of the Data.....	118
6.1.1 Hypothesis One.....	118
6.1.2 Hypothesis Two.....	121
6.1.3 Hypothesis Three.....	124
6.1.4 Hypothesis Four	126
6.1.5 Hypothesis Five	128
6.2 Hypotheses Test Results in Discussion	130
6.2.1 The Level of Entrepreneurs and Outturns of Graduates in Nigeria	130
6.2.2 Entrepreneurship and Types of Nigerian Graduate Jobs	132
6.2.3 Correlation of Entrepreneurship and Tertiary Education.....	135
6.2.4 Influences of Tertiary Education on Entrepreneurial Skills Development....	137
6.2.5 The Relationship Between Educated Entrepreneurs and Successful Entrepreneurs.....	139
CHAPTER SEVEN: CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS.....	142
7.1 Conclusions	142

7.1.1 Research Summary	142
7.1.2 Findings and Conclusions.....	145
7.2 Recommendations	147
7.3 Research Contributions.....	148
7.4 Research Limitations and Suggestions for Further Studies	150
REFERENCES	152
APPENDICES	174
Appendix One: Ethical Approval Letter	174
Appendix Two: Sample of Invitation Letter to Pilot and Answer Survey.....	175
Appendix Three: Sample of Questionnaire	176

List of Figures

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework.....	35
Figure 2: Conceptual Model for Education and Entrepreneurship Interplay in Nigeria..	51
Figure 3: Opportunity Perception	101
Figure 4: Start-Up Skills.....	101
Figure 5: Risk Acceptance.....	102
Figure 6: Cultural Support.....	103
Figure 7: Opportunity Start-up.....	103
Figure 8: Human Capital.....	104
Figure 9: Entrepreneurs Identification	106
Figure 10: Finding if becoming an entrepreneur is a result of tertiary education.....	107
Figure 11: Does research participant provide vocational/innovation training	107
Figure 12: Finding if the programme provided by the respondent’s institution is platform for students to become entrepreneurs.....	108
Figure 13: How often do graduates establish their own business venture as a result of acquired skills	108
Figure 14: Finding on the number of respondents’ employees	109
Figure 15: Finding on how often respondents have positions available for graduates of tertiary institution	109
Figure 16: Finding on how important do respondents see an act of creating business venture in Nigeria	110
Figure 17: Finding on to what extent respondents think Nigerian regulatory bodies support business start-ups.....	110
Figure 18: Finding on whether the course of study helped start a business	111

Figure 19: Finding about whether the respondents see Nigerian tertiary institution graduates as major competitor in their sector	111
Figure 20: Finding on how frequently respondents receive job applications from recent graduates.....	112
Figure 21: Is Nigeria is an entrepreneurial nation as a result of tertiary institution graduates creating a business venture	112
Figure 22: Finding about how respondents rate the contribution made by their tertiary education to their business start-up.....	113
Figure 23: Finding on how respondents rate the quality of becoming an entrepreneur through Nigerian technical Institutions.....	113
Figure 24: Finding if respondents believe people are more likely to become an entrepreneur in Nigeria if they graduate from university	114
Figure 25: Finding on respondents' main motive for starting a business	114
Figure 26: Finding on what capacity respondents think Nigeria needs a graduate of vocational/innovation training institutions.....	115
Figure 27: Finding on whether respondents think their course of study in Nigeria helps them to succeed in business	115
Figure 28: Finding if respondents agree that being educated helps nurture long-term business relationships.....	116
Figure 29: Respondents' gender	116
Figure 30: Age group of respondents.....	117
Figure 31: Findings of the Study Model.....	145

List of Tables

Table 1: Probability and Non-probability Sampling Techniques	83
Table 2: Probability Sampling Techniques Classifications and their Merits and Demerits	84
Table 3: Summary of Research Approach and Methodology	98
Table 4: The Global Entrepreneurship Index rank of the five selected countries	105
Table 5: Summary of Tertiary Education Institutions in Nigeria	105

CHAPTER ONE: GENERAL INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

It is widely known that entrepreneurship is a source of innovation and change that encompasses productivity, economic growth, and competitiveness. At the same time, education through the acquisition of knowledge and skills is widely recognised as an indispensable and sustainable mechanism of individual and collective development. Across industries and countries, educational training and development, especially at the tertiary level, is a crucial tool for entrepreneurial development. With the understanding that education and entrepreneurship intersect and coexist as agents of innovative change, technological development and competitiveness at both individual and national levels, this research seeks to examine the state of and the relationship between entrepreneurship and tertiary education in the Nigerian context. Evidence has shown that Nigeria has many established tertiary institutions, and the country has formally embedded entrepreneurship into its 2004 tertiary education reform. However, scant research has examined the interplay between tertiary education and entrepreneurship.

1.2 Research Gaps and Motivation

Both the academic and professional literature has recognised the role of entrepreneurship as a lever of poverty alleviation, innovation and productivity, firms and country's competitiveness and wider economic and social development (Awwad & Al-Aseer, 2021; Naminse, et al., 2019; Angulo-Guerrero, et al., 2017; Dragomir & Panzaru, 2015; Machado, et al., 2021; Kuratko & Morris, 2018; Arruti & Panos-Castro, 2020; Adeosun & Shittu, 2021; Iglesias-Sanchez, et al., 2016; Hassan, et al., 2020). Researchers have also found that education has a positive impact on an individual and a firm's growth and national and international development. Findings include education quality played a

significant role in enhancing inclusive growth (Adeniyi, et al., 2021), tertiary education reduces income inequality (Munir & Kanwal, 2020), education having a positive impact on entrepreneurial performance (Bianchi & Biffignandi, 2012), tertiary education increasing formal entrepreneurship (Jimenez, et al., 2015), entrepreneurship education significantly influencing students' entrepreneurial intentions (Oguntimehin & Olaniran, 2017), and making stronger relationships with subsequent entrepreneurial activity in seemingly entrepreneurship-hostile institutional environments (Walter & Block, 2016).

Historically, the United States embraced entrepreneurship education in the 1940s and thereafter, the concept has been adopted and integrated into education in many countries as a component of new economic strategies for fostering job creation (Zhou & Xu, 2012). However, as noted by Graevenitz et al. (2010, p. 111), 'entrepreneurship education has been introduced and promoted in many countries, and at many institutions of tertiary education, little is known at this point about the effect of these courses'. In Nigeria, the tertiary education reform enacted in 2004 has, for the first time, incorporated entrepreneurship in the national education system (FRN, 2004). This point was further revisited in 2013 (FRN, 2013), where entrepreneurship education was fully embedded into the higher education curriculum.

Since then, limited research has analysed the impact of the education reform on entrepreneurship. In particular, scant research on education and entrepreneurship in the Nigerian context has addressed the importance of entrepreneurship, its success, type of knowledge, skills, attitudes or usefulness in developing the national economy (Ayodotun, et al., 2021; Francis, et al., 2019; Yatu, et al., 2016; Awogbenle & Iwuamadi, 2010; Owualah & Obokoh, 2008; Iyortsuun, et al., 2020; Udefuna, et al., 2013; Alarape, 2008; Ezeh, et al., 2020; Sanusi, et al., 2017). In a similar vein, limited research has been

undertaken to examine the impact of entrepreneurship education on employment and national development. One of the few studies on the subject found that perceived entrepreneurial lecturers had a significantly positive link with students' entrepreneurial intentions (Otache, 2019). However, Adelaja (2021) indicated no significant relationship between entrepreneurial education and entrepreneurial intention in Nigeria. Similarly, entrepreneurship education was found to have a positive but insignificant effect on graduate entrepreneurship in Nigeria (Odumosu, et al., 2020). Nwekeaku (2013) found that universities in Nigeria understand the importance of entrepreneurship education and adapt the curriculum, but there are no fundamental changes in the teaching and learning process. A similar investigation by Nwosu and Chukwudi (2018) revealed that university graduates were unemployable, which impeded the success of entrepreneurship education in Nigeria.

The above studies provided a basis and justification for the researcher to investigate the relationship between entrepreneurship and education in Nigeria, focusing primarily on tertiary education as the highest formal institutional education before entering or accessing the labour market. Education is acknowledged as a weapon for upward stratification, social and economic development of any nation (IseOlorunkanmi, et al., 2021), and students are the distinct entrepreneurial agents embedded in the unique contexts of higher education institutions (Harima, et al., 2021). Nurturing entrepreneurial skills and intentions among youth is central to the socioeconomic development agenda of countries across the world (Aboobaker & D, 2020).

1.3 Research Aims and Objectives

The primary aim of this study is to examine the interplay between tertiary education and entrepreneurship in Nigeria. A secondary aim is to examine the impact of entrepreneurship education on employment and economic development. Additionally, this study attempts to investigate further areas of research identified by authors such as Guerrero, et al (2018, p. 19) on ‘the potential influence of generational cohorts on individual entrepreneurial decisions’, Turner and Gianiodis (2018, p. 144) on ‘the next step(s) in the entrepreneurial journey - moving from intentions to action, tracking performance across time, the transition from academics to real-world application, and how important prior knowledge and experience affect entrepreneurial intention’ and Costa, et al (2018, p. 70) on ‘the measurement of the sustainability of the effects of training overtime after the training, the impact of different instructors on training outcomes and exploring the stability of cognitive structures across different backgrounds and cultures’.

Last but not least, the relationship of tertiary education and entrepreneurship in the context of Nigeria must be investigated based on Feldman (2014), Lackeus (2015), Imperial College London (2018), and OECD (2008) questions and recommendations which state

The question of why some places grow and prosper is a fundamental question in social science research (Feldman, 2014, p. 9), there is a need for more and closer collaboration between researchers and practitioners in the two domains of education and entrepreneurship (Lackeus, 2015, p. 35) and understanding the entrepreneurial dynamic is vital for a country looking to encourage growth in the quest for economic recovery (Imperial College London, 2018). As globalisation is reshaping the international economic landscape whereby technology changes, creating more significant uncertainty in the nations’ economy

and the dynamism of entrepreneurship is believed to be the solution (OECD, 2008).

As such, the combined aim of the study is to deliver a broad understanding of the relationship between tertiary education and entrepreneurship in Nigeria in ways that promote socioeconomic and business development in the country. This would provide a basis for making both sector (education) and wider policy recommendations in view of establishing a successful link between education and entrepreneurship in ways that promote long-term sustainable business development and socioeconomic growth.

1.4 Research Questions and Hypotheses

Given the background and objectives of the study and in view of an extensive literature review in Chapters 2 and 3 of this thesis, the main research questions were identified as follows:

1. Is there a positive relationship between the level of entrepreneurs and outturns of tertiary institution graduates in Nigeria?
2. Is there a negative relationship between entrepreneurship and types of Nigerian graduate jobs?
3. Is there a correlation between entrepreneurship and tertiary education in Nigeria?
4. Are there positive influences of tertiary education on entrepreneurial skills development in Nigeria?
5. Is there a positive relationship between educated entrepreneurs and successful entrepreneurs in Nigeria?

The above research questions have been translated in the following research hypotheses:

H₁ – There seems to be no positive relationship between the level of entrepreneurs and outturns of tertiary institution graduates in Nigeria

H₂ – There seems to be a negative relationship between entrepreneurship and types of Nigerian graduate jobs

H₃ – There is likely no correlation between entrepreneurship and tertiary education in Nigeria

H₄ – There is no positive influences of tertiary education on the entrepreneurial skills development in Nigeria

H₅ – There is no positive relationship between educated entrepreneurs and successful entrepreneurs in Nigeria.

1.5 Significant Contributions of Study

Entrepreneurship and education intersected and are considered as the mechanism for sustainable economic development by way of innovation, productivity, employment generation, and building nation's human capital (Angulo-Guerrero, et al., 2017; Bianchi & Biffignandi, 2012; Arruti & Panos-Castro, 2020; Adeosun & Shittu, 2021; Hernandez-Sanchez, et al., 2019). With this understanding, Nigeria has seen with some established higher institutions for decades as well as embedded entrepreneurship education at a different level of educational reforms and government mandatory policies (FGN, 2019; FRN, 2004; FRN, 2013). However, literature shows that Nigeria's trajectory number of unemployed graduates increases yearly and has less impact on education and entrepreneurship in terms of the development at individual and national levels (Aririah, 2021; Akinpelu, 2020). Not only that, but the number of these studies also appears to be small and published in unrecognised journal indexes. Therefore, these made it imperative

to research with the aim to establish the interrelationship of entrepreneurship and tertiary education that could set a stage for sustainable business development and socioeconomic growth.

In quest of research this topic, deductive research approach and mixed methods research design adopted, because of the literature review followed by theories adopted and combines quantitative and qualitative techniques and analytical procedures. Consequently, the significant contributions of this study finding to the policy maker and strategic educational managers include expanding literature of entrepreneurship and tertiary education in the context of developing Nigeria. This research contributed to the practices and nation's policymakers' decision-making process by demonstrating the lack of relationship between entrepreneurship and tertiary education. The study made a practical contribution to tertiary education institution managers who have a strategic role in promoting and widening institutionalisation of entrepreneurship education by presenting empirical evidence on the state and relationship of tertiary education and entrepreneurship in Nigeria. Also, the study contributed to the managerial knowledge by indicating the influences of tertiary education on the entrepreneurship skills development of Nigerian graduates.

1.6 Structure of the Thesis

The rest of this thesis is structured as follows. Chapter Two presents the context of Nigerian tertiary education, where tertiary education in Nigeria is defined and discussed with brief issues and challenges and accounts of the enrolled students and graduates.

Chapter Three covers the historical background of entrepreneurship, defines and classifies entrepreneurship, and discusses some forms of entrepreneurship. Then, four relevant theories are examined, and the significance of entrepreneurship and education,

followed by the national measurement of entrepreneurship, are discussed. The application of entrepreneurship education is reviewed, including the Nigerian system of entrepreneurship, before formal entrepreneurship is traced and discussed, and issues, challenges and consequences are demonstrated. Then, a conceptual framework is designed and presented, research questions/hypotheses are discussed, and the chapter ends with the summary and conclusions.

Chapter Four covers the research approach and methodology. It comprises the employed research philosophy assumptions, approaches, design, methods, and data collection. Chapter Five presents and analyses the data gathered, and Chapter Six covers the results and discusses the findings. Finally, Chapter Seven concludes with recommendations and research contributions.

CHAPTER TWO: THE CONTEXT OF NIGERIAN TERTIARY EDUCATION

This chapter provides an overview of the tertiary education system in Nigeria, the issues and challenges and a brief account of students' enrolment to graduation and after.

2.1 Nigerian Tertiary Education System

Tertiary education in Nigeria is given after post-basic education. Higher education refers to all organised learning activities at the tertiary level (Jaja, 2013). Higher education institutions represent a diverse group of organisations that provide education, including universities, polytechnics, and higher education colleges (Veiderpass & McKelvey, 2016). This comprises universities, innovation enterprise institutions (IEIs), colleges of education, monotronics, polytechnics, and other specialised institutions (FRN, 2013). The Nigerian education system encompasses three different sectors: basic education (nine years), post-basic/senior secondary education (three years), and tertiary education (four to six years, depending on the program of study) (FRN, 2013).

The management of Nigeria's educational sector is the Federal Ministry of Education (FME) parastatal, overseeing policy development, financial planning, quality control, and data collection and management. FME is the only channel and intermediary for national and international cooperation, collaboration and coordination of all the educational matters in Nigeria (FRN, 2013). Other leading agencies working in partnership with FME within Nigeria at a specific portfolio are the National Universities Commission (NUC), the National Board for Technical Education (NBTE), and the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) for effective administration (FGN, 2019).

According to the national educational policy framework (FRN, 2013, p. 26), the general goals of the tertiary education institutions in Nigeria are

- a. Contribute to national development through a high-level work force

- b. Provide accessible and affordable quality learning opportunities in formal and informal education in response to the needs and interests of all Nigerians
- c. Provide high-quality career counselling and lifelong learning programmes that prepare students with the knowledge and skills for self-reliance and the world of work
- d. Reduce skill shortages through the production of a skilled work force relevant to the needs of the labour market
- e. Promote and encourage scholarship, entrepreneurship and community service
- f. Forge and cement national unity, and
- g. Promote national and international understanding and interaction

2.1.1 University Education System in Nigeria

Historically, the first-generation of Universities in Nigeria was at the nucleus of the Yaba Higher College, established in 1932 under the regime of British colonies. However, shortly after independence in 1960, many universities were chartered. The first was the University of Ibadan (formerly University College) in 1948 which became a full-fledged University in 1960; following by the University of Nigeria, Nsukka in 1960; Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria in 1962, University of Lagos, Obafemi Awolowo University (formerly University of Ife) and the University of Benin in 1970 (FGN, 2019). Currently, there are 169 universities in Nigeria, comprising 43 federal, 48 state, and 79 private (NUC, 2019). Hence, according to NPE (2013), the expected contributions from all these universities include the following.

- intensifying and diversifying its programmes for the development of a high-level work force within the context of the needs of the nation
- making professional courses contents to reflect our national requirements

- as a part of a general programme of all-round improvement in university education, offering courses such as the history of ideas, philosophy of knowledge, nationalism and information technology (IT); and
- making entrepreneurship skills acquisition a requirement for all Nigerian universities

2.1.2 Polytechnics Education System in Nigeria

A polytechnic in Nigeria is a generic, non-university tertiary technical education training institution. These schools are called polytechnics, colleges of science and technology, and the Institute of Science and Technology. The curriculum exposes students to high-level classroom theories, workshops, and practical and industrial experiences in technical, science and business-oriented fields. These institutions award a national diploma (ND), a higher national diploma (HND) and a post-HND (NBTE, 2017). The admission requirement is a minimum of relevant five subjects passed at credit in SSSC/GCE O-Level or equivalent. Depending on the graduates' level of training from these institutions, they are employed as technicians, higher technicians/technologists or professionals. The Nigerian federal government owns 37 polytechnics, the state governments own 51, and 64 are privately managed, for a total of 152 as of August 2021 (NBTE, 2021).

2.1.3 Monotechnic Education System in Nigeria

Monotechnic is a generic name for a tertiary institution that offers technical education and training in a single discipline. It has the same academic structure, curriculum contents, educational staffing, students' admission and other critical requirements as a polytechnic and awards the ND and HND diplomas (NBTE, 2017). Monotechnics have been re-classified into three sub-categories as follows.

a. Colleges of Agriculture and Related Discipline

A college of agriculture and related disciplines is in the category of monotecnics that offer technical education and training in various aspects of agricultural science and related activities, leading to the award of NDs and HNDs. The programmes offered cut across the traditional and emerging areas of study. The number of agriculture and related programmes offered by the institutions range from one to numerous. The curriculum exposes students to a high level of practical agricultural education and training and the agro-allied industry (NBTE, 2017). The state and federal governments own 33 approved and accredited colleges of agriculture (NBTE, 2020).

b. Colleges of Health Sciences

A college of health sciences is the monotecnic sub-group that offers technical education and training in health-related disciplines, leading to ND, HND and Post-HND certificates. The related programmes spread across several traditional and emerging fields of health technology. Like other monotecnic sub-groups, the curriculum is designed to expose students to a high level of practical and workplace experiences through practical workshops and laboratory hours and extensive industrial training durations. Nigeria has 50 of these institutions; 43 are owned by state and federal governments, and seven are privately owned (NBTE, 2020).

c. Specialised Institutions

Specialised institutions are another monotecnic sub-group that offer technical education and training in a specific discipline (other than agriculture), leading to ND and HND awards. The programmes offered in this institution type cut across the traditional and emerging technical education fields. Once the specific discipline is chosen, the specialised institution only offers a programme(s) related to that field. The curriculum is designed to expose students to a high level of practical and workplace experiences (NBTE,

2017). There are 31 of these facilities; 24 are owned by the federal government, three are owned by state governments and four are privately owned (NBTE, 2020).

2.1.4 Innovation Enterprise Institutions (IEIs) in Nigeria

Innovation enterprise institutions (IEIs) are tertiary institutions that offer vocational and technical education and higher practical content training than polytechnics and monotechnics (NBTE, 2017). They are mainly private-sector driven as they were created from the effort to harness the private informal training institutions' technical skills by bringing them under the mainstream TVET certification umbrella. They are primarily intended to equip secondary school leavers and even graduates of tertiary institutions or working adults with high practice-based vocational and technical skills to meet the demand for industry-ready technical staff. Given this objective, the curriculum focuses more extensively on industry-tailored practical training than other mainstream tertiary institutions. However, unlike polytechnics and monotechnic, IEIs' training terminates after two years (NID1 and NID2), leading to the national innovation diploma (NID) certificate award. These 158 institutions were established to actualise Nigeria's vision to be one of the twenty largest economies in the world by the year 2020 (NBTE, 2007) (NBTE, 2021).

2.1.5 Vocational Enterprise Institutions (VEIs) in Nigeria

Vocational enterprise institutions (VEIs) are private TVET institutions that offer vocational education and training at senior secondary school equivalent levels. Like the IEIs, VEIs were set up to harness the contributions made by private sector informal vocational training institutions to national skills training needs. Through standardisation of the training structure by NBTE, VEIs were brought into the mainstream of the national vocational certification system. They provide vocational training for people at the senior

secondary school level. The curriculum is focused extensively on practical training and industrial experiences (NBTE, 2017). VEIs were established to be offered to various end-users, especially senior secondary school graduates who did not earn up to five credits and who, therefore, can not continue to tertiary education for a period ranging from 1 to 2 years (FRN, 2013).

VEIs run three-year modular programmes where each year of study is terminal. They have a clear and flexible structure and content that equips the trainee with practicable working skills and the possibility to exit at each level. The qualification obtainable at these levels is the national vocational certificate (NVC) Part 1, Part 2 and 3 or Final. VEI is like a technical college except for its modular structure.

VEIs admit candidates with a minimum of basic education certificate (JSS) and cover multi-disciplinary vocation that prepares learners for jobs, directly in industries though at a lower level. NVC holders' academic career path is to apply to innovation enterprise institutions, polytechnics or monotechnics through JAMB. There are 78 approved and accredited vocational enterprise institutions (VEIs) (NBTE, 2021).

2.1.6 Technical Colleges in Nigeria

Technical colleges address the study of technologies and related sciences and the acquisition of practical skills, attitudes, understanding, and knowledge relating to occupations in various sectors of economic and social life (FRN, 2013). Technical colleges are senior secondary schools (SSS) set up expressly for technical and vocational education and training in the Nigerian educational system. They offer mainly skill-based subjects referred to as trades: woodwork, metalwork, mechanical craft practice, bricklaying and concrete making, and some business or commercial oriented vocations such as typewriting, bookkeeping, storekeeping etc. (NBTE, 2017).

A technical college education is structured to cover the three (3) years of senior secondary school classes, referred to as NTC 1, NTC 2 and NTC 3. Upon completing their study, graduates are awarded a national technical certificate (NTC) or a national business certificate (NBC). In addition, the advanced national technical certificate (ANTC) and advanced national business certificate (ANBC) are available for candidates who want further certification in their study trade. The National Business and Technical Education Board (NABTEB) is the agency that examines and award the certificates.

The entry qualification for NTC/NBC is a junior secondary school (JSS) certificate, and that of ANTC/ANBC is the NTC/NBC. NTC/NBC is equivalent to SSCE 'O' level while ANTC/ANBC is equivalent to GCE 'A' level. Both are approved entry qualifications into polytechnics, monotechnics and universities in Nigeria. There are 123 vocational enterprise institutions (VEIs) in Nigeria (NBTE, 2021).

2.1.7 Issues and Challenges with Nigerian Tertiary Education Institutions

Despite the essential roles of education, studies have revealed multidimensional and monumental challenges facing Nigeria's educational sector. These include inadequate funding, misappropriation of allocated funds, brain-drain, dilapidated and inadequate infrastructure, non-functional curricula and obsolete instructional methods (Odeleye, 2009; Adesina, 2011; Agbowuro, et al., 2017; Bamiro, 2012; Iruonagbe, et al., 2015; Okoli, et al., 2016; Olusola, et al., 2017; Olibie, et al., 2018; Udey, et al., 2009; Jacob & Musa, 2020). Also, frequent changes often made on the educational policies with haphazard implementation (Asikiya & Boma, 2015), poor quality of schooling from elementary to tertiary level, arising from the issue of poor quality of teachers characterised by weak school infrastructure and meagre supplies of equipment (Agbowuro, et al., 2017), ineffective implementation engendered primarily by lack of political will, lack of

continuity of programs, and corruption (Okoroma, 2006), and exploitation, inadequate staff training; poor parenting/guidance and poverty (Udey, et al., 2009). Likewise noted is that the potential of higher education systems in developing countries to fulfil their responsibility is frequently thwarted by long-standing problems of finance, efficiency, equity, quality and governance (Saint, et al., 2003). Therefore, education in Nigeria has suffered much neglect manifested in inadequate funding, inconsistent policy changes, lack of infrastructure and disruption of the school system (Iruonagbe, et al., 2015).

In that regard, Agbowuro et al. (2017, p. 39) warned that the setback in the Nigerian education sector is 'a disaster that will set back Nigeria's human and economic development for decades, thus mortgaging future generations unborn if it is unchecked'. To mitigate these problems, scholars and professionals have made the following recommendations: The Nigerian government should adequately resource, finance and increase budgetary allocations at all levels of the education sector; implement effective policies and curricula that will improve all education and harmonise activities at all levels of the education sector (Olibie, et al., 2018). Furthermore, the Nigerian government was advised to carefully select and follow a pragmatic policy with a culture of continuity and run uniformly throughout the country without ethnic sentiments (Asikiya & Boma, 2015), reverse the abysmally low level of allocation to the education sector and ensure proper management of funds (Agbowuro, et al., 2017). The Nigerian government should ensure meeting the needs of tertiary institutions in terms of human resources and finance (Olusola, et al., 2017), adequate training and re-training of all education managers, and provision of sufficient funds for the sector (Udey, et al., 2009). Furthermore, the Nigerian government and the organised private sector should fund research programmes, inventions and mass production of invented products (Odia & Omofonmwan, 2018). Nigerian tertiary institutions must have a paradigm shift from a resource-based economy

to a knowledge-based economy by focusing attention on three key elements: staffing to ensure adequacy in quantity and quality; adequate resource inflow to support the fundamental functions of teaching, research and community service; and the evolution of favourable governance structure (Bamiro, 2012). Finally, the Nigerian government should allocate up to 26% of the annual budget on education spending as recommended by UNESCO (Asiyai, 2013; Orji & Job, 2013; Okoli, et al., 2016).

2.2 Account of Students Enrolment and Graduates of Nigeria's Tertiary Institutions

Hundreds of thousands of new students are admitted to tertiary institutions every year, which, in turn, release the same number of new graduates. Sahara (2019) reported that the Joint Admissions and Matriculation Board (JAMB) list of admission into various Nigerian higher institutions for 2018 includes 443,624 candidates into universities, 81,791 into polytechnics, 59,498 into colleges of education, and 585 into innovation enterprise institutions. Similarly, Akinpelu (2020) reported that admission into various Nigerian higher institutions for 2019 comprises a total of 444,947 students into universities, 96,423 students into polytechnics and monotechnics, 69,810 students into colleges of education, and 1,377 into innovation enterprise institutions. Intakes into Nigeria tertiary institutions are on the increase.

Nigeria's tertiary institutions graduate an estimated 600,000 people (Aririah, 2021; Babalobi, 2019). Nigeria defined graduates as those who have completed their first academic degree at defined tertiary institutions, including universities, polytechnics, and others (Aririah, 2021; Babalobi, 2019). Then, to what extent is the Nigerian labour market able to absorb these graduates? In 2019, it was estimated that about 25 million Nigerian graduates are unemployed in Nigeria (Aririah, 2021; Babalobi, 2019). One record shows that 60,000 Nigeria graduates sat for an interview in 2019 for a jobs slot of

100 vacancies (Babalobi, 2019). These indicated an impossible situation for Nigerian graduates as the labour market is unable to absorb them. However, there are many indications that Nigeria graduates are not employable. This side of the issue will be presented in Chapter Three.

2.3 Applications of Entrepreneurship Education in Nigeria

This theme covers the history of entrepreneurship education in Nigeria, the evolution of the initial entrepreneurship education system, the new system of entrepreneurship education, and modern-day and entrepreneurship education effects and challenges.

2.3.1 Historical of the Nigerian Entrepreneurship Education System

Entrepreneurship education is not a new education system and practice in Nigeria. Gabadeen and Raimi (2012, p. 2) contend that 'it is false to say that entrepreneurship education is recent and a modern phenomenon within the Nigerian context'. Additionally, Akhuemonkhan et al. (2013, p. 2) claimed: 'entrepreneurship education is not a new phenomenon in the annals of Nigeria; it has always been an age-long tradition, a culture and a habit that has consistently been transferred from one generation to another within the diverse ethnic nationalities that made up Nigeria'. Gabadeen and Raimi (2012) revealed that the Nigerian entrepreneurship education system in the pre-independence era was referred to as informal entrepreneurship or traditional entrepreneurship, where various ethnic nationalities imbibe the enterprising attitude of self-employment and self-sufficiency through active involvement in artisanship, crafts, and farming. Later, that system was developed to trade-by-barter where goods were exchanged for goods or services for goods, and it was an enduring and acceptable norm of business in Nigeria until money was introduced worldwide. Trade-by-barter involved exchanging surplus and encouraged specialisation among producers. It led Nigerian communities to the point

of concentration on areas of production to which they were best fitted. Finally, Gabadeen and Raimi (2012, p. 1) remarked that 'it is a classical era of entrepreneurship that marked the beginning of economic development in all the local communities within the enclave that later became Nigeria'.

2.3.2 Nigerian Transition from Traditional Entrepreneurship System and Effects

Western education or formal education was introduced into Nigeria through Christian missionary's activities in the mid - 19th century (Lawal, 2013). The Nigerian transition from a belief entrepreneurship education system and practice started in the 20th century due to the British colonial government's involvement in providing Western education. The motive behind educating Nigerians was a growing need for human capital to meet colonial exigencies and respond to criticism from the early nationalists (Lawal, 2013; Akhuemonkhan, et al., 2013). The colonial administrator's education policy in Nigeria believed was geared towards producing staff who could read and write only to enable them to hold certain positions such as administrative officers, clerks, teachers, and other liberal arts graduates and interpreters (Aladekomo, 2004; Adamu, 2015; Nwekeaku, 2013).

Subsequently, when Nigeria became independent in 1960, she inherited and adopted the infrastructure and education system planted by the colonial master. Post-independence, the Nigerian government did not do much to restructure education curricula at all levels of education (Nwekeaku, 2013). However, for many years, formal education was a reserved privilege of few Nigerians who had the rare opportunity of being absorbed into the civil service as public servants in white-collar jobs as the Nigerian economy was large enough to absorb them, and there was no concern (Gabadeen & Raimi, 2012). During the post-independence period, it was recognised that the Nigerian national education policy

was 'education for paid employment' rather than 'education for self-employment' (Aladekomo, 2004). Hence, it assumed 'the formal colonial education destroyed Nigerians' philosophy of self-employment, independence, creativity and enterprise innovation' (Gabadeen & Raimi, 2012, p. 2). Also, it affirmed that the reason for many Nigerian graduates looking for white-collar jobs was a consequence of colonial education policies (Adamu, 2015).

In this period, Nigerian problems continued to develop, and everyone sought a solution, resulting in studies, professionals' recommendations and lessons from developed nations of the world. The Nigerian government received information including recognition of higher education as the most critical foundational factor and the pivot of social, economic, political, and cultural development (Agbowuro, et al., 2017; Salgur, 2013; Asiyai, 2013; Akinyemi & Ofem, 2012). Also, the impacts of education have shown that educated entrepreneurs are more important in developing regional economies than entrepreneurs with a lower level of education (Taasila, 2010). The importance of the prominent role of education in entrepreneurs' perception, confidence, ability and level of conviction was acknowledged (Iglesias-Sanchez, et al., 2016). Entrepreneurship education as knowledge was declared to produce an essential tool for participating in the real issues of society, contributing thus to the economic and social progress and better quality of life (Dragomir & Panzaru, 2015). For example, 'one specific learning outcome of entrepreneurship education is that it promotes entrepreneurial and innovative orientations that go beyond the question of starting up one's own business' (Storen, 2014, p. 798). Additionally, it was found 'entrepreneurship education is essential not only to shape the mindsets of young people but also to provide the skills, knowledge and attitudes that are central to

developing an entrepreneurial culture' (European Commission/EACEA/Eurydice, 2016, p. 9).

Akhuemonkhan et al.'s (2013, p. 1) study revealed that 'entrepreneurship development could be effective tools for poverty reduction, stimulating employment as well as a fast-tracking realisation of universal primary education and promoting gender equality'. Lawal's (2013) investigation identified the growing rate of unemployment and consequent social vices among Nigerian graduates of tertiary education as the factor responsible for the need for entrepreneurship education in Nigeria. The European Parliament adopted a resolution in September 2015 to promote youth entrepreneurship through education and training (Sojdrova, 2015). The significance of entrepreneurship education was further revealed to the Nigerian government when they discovered that the United States had included it in their curriculum of higher education institutions since 1947 (Kuratko, 2007). The European Union (2013, p. 4) declared that 'reinforcing entrepreneurial education in schools, vocational education institutions and universities will positively impact the entrepreneurial dynamism of nations' economies'.

Similarly, it was discovered that in the late 1990s, some Chinese universities individually introduced entrepreneurship education because of the challenges brought by growing enrolments and graduate employment. After that, the Chinese government started promoting entrepreneurship in 2002 (Zhou & Xu, 2012). The struggle led Nigeria to the 2004 education reform that inculcated the entrepreneurship education curriculum (FRN, 2004) and made it compulsory at all levels of tertiary education in 2006 (Yahya, 2011).

2.3.3 Nigerian New System of Entrepreneurship Education

The Nigerian government became involved in an innovative effort to solve Nigerian problems by embedding entrepreneurship education in the curriculum in 2004. The aim was to

contribute to her national development through high-level relevant manpower training; develop and inculcate proper values for the survival of the individual and society; develop the intellectual capability of individuals to understand and appreciate their local and external environments; acquire both physical and intellectual skills which will enable individuals to be self-reliant and useful members of the society; promote and encourage scholarship and community service; forge and cement national unity; and finally, promote national and international understanding and interaction (FRN, 2004; FRN, 2013).

Entrepreneurship education became imperative in higher institutions in Nigeria as a realistic approach to solving the endemic problem of unemployment (Gabadeen & Raimi, 2012). Accordingly, the Federal Government of Nigeria further strengthened its 2006 position by making a compulsory course for all undergraduate students in three levels of tertiary education irrespective of students' areas of specialisation (Gabadeen & Raimi, 2012; Yahya, 2011). The reason for this effort was noted:

[the] overall objective is to continuously foster entrepreneurship culture amongst students and faculty with a view of not only educating them but also to support graduates of the system towards establishing and maintaining sustainable business ventures, including but not limited to those arising from research. (Yahya, 2011, p. 2)

In that regard, the Federal Government took drastic steps, according to Yahya (2011) (Yahya, 2011):

- ordered entrepreneurship studies centres to be set in Nigerian higher institutions
- development of teachers' guide, instruction manual and students' handbook
- building capacity for at least ten lecturers in each higher institution

- establishment of entrepreneurship resource and knowledge centres at the National University Commission
- development of Master of Science courses and PhD programmes in some selected universities

2.3.4 Modern-Day Nigerian Entrepreneurship Education Effects and Challenges

The new concept of entrepreneurship education into the Nigerian education sector was a welcome idea implemented in good faith. Accordingly, researchers and professionals have remarked on further entrepreneurship education adoption in Nigeria. For instance, Okeke and Edikpa (2014) emphasised that if the new Nigerian entrepreneurship education system is seriously and adequately delivered, it will promote job creation by entrepreneurs and promote economic development. Similarly, Olorundare and Kayode (2014) underlined that it is in the right direction if correctly focused on developing understanding and building the capacity of the students to pursue entrepreneurial behaviours, skills and attitudes in widely different contexts.

However, 'despite the prospect of entrepreneurship education, it is faced the challenges of a paucity of funds, ineffective teaching method, paucity of text-books, and lack of experienced lecturers and host of other factors' (Akhuemonkhan, et al., 2013, p. 16). Similarly, challenges include inadequate trainers or little knowledge of entrepreneurship by the universities' lecturers, inadequate funding for the program by the university administrators and challenges in the area of curriculum development and implementation (Olorundare & Kayode, 2014, p. 155).

Therefore, there is a disconnect and mismatch between the expectations of the industry and the graduates who are products of the Nigerian higher education institutions (Gabadeen & Raimi, 2012; Ofem, et al., 2012). Nigeria was observed to pass through many

changes in virtually every field of endeavour (Adamu, 2015). Many studies conducted and many professional observations revealed that the entrepreneurship education introduced by the Nigerian government does not yield results. The findings and comments include the following.

- Ojeifo (2012) found there are graduates from Nigerian Universities today who are not gainfully employed.
- Nigerian universities produce a graduate who is best suited for white-collar jobs and has little or no basic skills of any other vocational relevance (Olorundare & Kayode, 2014, p. 156).
- Nigerians had no professional skills to enable them to stand on their own or even establish and manage their ventures (Adamu, 2015, p. 86).
- Nigerian university outputs are not employable (Asuquo & Agboola, 2014).
- Graduate turnout outpaced the graduate employment rate over the years in Nigeria (Ofem, et al., 2012, p. 257).
- A significant defect in the Nigerian educational system, inclusive of the universities, is its theoretical inclination (Olorundare & Kayode, 2014, p. 156).
- A study from 2011 to 2020 found that levels of unemployment and underemployment continued to witness a steady and continuous increase (Ayeni, et al., 2020).
- The study on the 'challenge of job creation in Nigeria' found the rate of unemployment rose by 1.1% a year between 2000 and 2010 due to a supply-side 2.5% annual increase in the number of new entrants into the labour market and on the demand side, sectors' inability to create enough jobs (Alemu, 2015).
- Nigeria was reported to have a vast and growing unemployment problem, rising steeply from 3.6% in 2006 to 23.1% in 2018 (NESG, 2020).

- Universities in Nigeria understand the importance of entrepreneurship education and adopt it in the curriculum. However, there are no fundamental changes in the teaching and learning process (Nwekeaku, 2013).
- Another study found the level of entrepreneurial education in Nigerian tertiary institutions was low, graduates produced by the system lack employable skills, thus, the prevalence of unemployment (Agboola, 2010).
- Additionally, identified problems in Nigeria include 'high dependency rate, low per capita income, unwanted pregnancy, general disorder, moral decadence among others' (George & Ukpong, 2013, p. 172).

Thus, literature shows the following to be the main factors responsible for low-level entrepreneurship education outcomes in Nigeria.

- The growth of the Nigerian population at a geometric proportion relative to job placement that is growing at an arithmetic progression (Akhuemonkhan, et al., 2013)
- The technological changes and economic advancement in the world (Adamu, 2015)
- The preference for paid employment and passion for white-collar jobs by Nigerian youth may be a neurosis caused by the formal colonial education (Gabadeen & Raimi, 2012).

Limited findings show that Nigeria's entrepreneurship education system positively affects the individual, community, and national economy. One study examined 'the relationship between entrepreneurship education and students' entrepreneurial intentions in Ogun State-owned universities, Nigeria' and indicated that 'entrepreneurship education significantly influences students' entrepreneurial intentions' (Oguntimehin & Olaniran, 2017). Also, other findings revealed that a

'substantial percentage of the sampled respondents believed that the graduates were employable' (Omoniwa & Adedapo, 2017, p. 58).

2.4 Summary

Chapter Two presented the background of the tertiary education system in Nigeria. Tertiary education in Nigeria is education given after post-basic education. The diverse group of institutions providing education at the tertiary level in Nigeria includes universities, innovation enterprise institutions (IEIs), colleges of education, monotechnic, polytechnics, and other specialised institutions (FRN, 2013). Nigerian Tertiary education is overseen by the Federal Ministry of Education (FME). At the same time, it is supported by the National Universities Commission (NUC), the National Board for Technical Education (NBTE), and the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) (FGN, 2019). In Nigeria, tertiary education objectives include national development via a high-level work force, responding to Nigerian needs by ensuring access to quality learning opportunities formally and informally, and promoting and encouraging scholarship, entrepreneurship, and community service (FRN, 2013). However, Nigerian tertiary institutions having some issues and challenges that are slowing their operations. These issues include inadequate funding, misappropriation of allocated funds, non-functional curricula and obsolete instructional methods, poor quality of schooling from elementary to tertiary level, poor quality of teachers, exploitation, inadequate staff training, poor parenting/guidance and poverty, and inconsistent policy. Furthermore, a brief account of the Nigerian labour market was presented, which shows thousands of graduates are produced without being absorbed into the labour market.

CHAPTER THREE: LITERATURE REVIEW ON ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND EDUCATION

This chapter presents literature on entrepreneurship history and theories, the significance of education and entrepreneurship, the interplay between education and entrepreneurship, applications of entrepreneurship education in Nigeria, measurement of entrepreneurship, conceptual framework, and chapter summary and conclusions.

3.1 The Facets of Entrepreneurship

The linguistic, historical term of entrepreneurship is rooted in the French 'entreprendre' and the German word 'unternehmen'. Both mean to 'undertake' (Veeraraghavan, 2009; Dilanchiev, 2014). A French economist, Richard Cantillon, was the first to coin the phrase entrepreneurship as 'someone who organises and assumes the risk of a business in return for the profits' in about 1730 (Ahmad & Seymour, 2008; Ahmad & Hoffman, 2007). Also, an Austrian economist, Carl Menger (1870), argued that entrepreneurship emerges as people seek out and take advantage of profit opportunities, creating goods that previously did not exist, and finding new ways to develop existing goods (Dilanchiev, 2014). However, in contemporary English, the word 'entrepreneur' is alternately used to indicate a businessman, a founder of a new business, a business owner of an innovative enterprise, an enterprising individual, or the CEO of a large corporation (Wennekers, 2006). It was noted that 'systematic reviews on literature and research on courses and programmes in entrepreneurship began to appear in the 1990s' (Hagg & Gabrielsson, 2021, p. 831), and it was not until the 1990s that the term entrepreneurship became a buzzword both in the media and in political debate (Ahmad & Hoffman, 2007). Hence, the literature showed a shift in that scholarly discussions moved from addressing the issue of teachability to a greater emphasis on learnability (Hagg & Gabrielsson, 2021).

3.1.1 Definitions of Entrepreneurship

There is an absence of an internationally accepted and consensual definition of entrepreneurship (Ahmad & Hoffman, 2007; Arruti & Panos-Castro, 2020). In other words, entrepreneurship is ill-defined, at the best multidimensional concept (Wennekers, 2006). The reason is that it is described as a complex phenomenon that spanned from various contexts (Dilanchiev, 2014; Arruti & Panos-Castro, 2020). While further assumed, entrepreneurship is an elusive phenomenon that is difficult to define and measure (Bianchi & Biffignandi, 2012). For instance, looking at entrepreneurship from scholars' field perspective, an economist will focus on economic growth, psychologists will give preference to cognitive, sociologists will focus on social and organisational elements, and business strategists will be interested in entrepreneurial corporate success activities. How entrepreneurship is redefined and by whom is a major challenge confronting the discipline as it forges the future trajectory (Kuratko & Morris, 2018).

A notable scholar at the Harvard Business School says 'as the pursuit of opportunity beyond resources controlled' (Stevenson, 1983, p. 23). This definition has been argued about because it does not consider the present entrepreneur's unique set of resources and capabilities that can create and actualise opportunities as entrepreneurial people do when they begin where they are (Gartner & Baker, 2010). This definition is well supported on two fundamental facts: 'entrepreneurship as a distinctive approach to managing rather than a specific stage in an organisation's life cycle, and it provides a guidepost for entrepreneurial action by pointing to tactics entrepreneurs can take to manage risk and mobilise resources' (Eisenmann, 2013, p. 3). Entrepreneurship is mostly about risks, innovation, and creative thinking, and the entrepreneur creates and innovates around perceived opportunities by accepting risks and failures (Eroglu & Picak,

2011). The entrepreneurship field focuses on creation activities as distinguished from its closest neighbour, the strategy field (Brush, et al., 2003).

Many private and governmental bodies shed light on entrepreneurship as any attempt at new business or new venture creation, such as self-employment, a new business organisation, or the expansion of an existing business, by an individual, a team of individuals, or an established company (GEM, 2018). In the same vein, an entrepreneur is a person with the vision to see innovation and the ability to bring it to market (GEDI, 2018). Entrepreneurs are those people (business owners) who seek to generate value by creating or expanding economic activity by identifying and exploiting new products, processes, and markets (OECD, 2017). Similar, an entrepreneur is defined as a person who organises, manages, and assumes a business enterprise (Dilanchiev, 2014). Notably, entrepreneurs play a central role while the entrepreneurship process extends beyond the individual to teams, organisations, social networks, and institutions such as rules and regulations and cultural norms (Blundel, et al., 2018).

In Arruti and Panos-Castro's (2020, p. 825) investigation, entrepreneur characteristics are 'being creative, team players, open-minded, innovative, passionate, motivated, hard-working and risk-takers; being able to overcome challenges; having initiative; being proactive, organised and persevering; having leadership skills, communication skills, the ability to adapt; having a positive attitude and, being decision-makers'. Some of these qualities were found in Kuratko (2007) and Cacciotti and Hayton (2015). Also, this individual is an active member facing uncertainty without fear and pursues a worthy goal (Cacciotti & Hayton, 2015; Morgan & Sisak, 2016). Taking risks and indulging in creative destruction and innovation are prominent entrepreneur features (Veeraraghavan, 2009). Entrepreneurs are creative, innovative, risk-taking, dynamic, flexible, brave, opportunity

recogniser, leadership potentiality, network builder, independent and self-reliant people (Vakili, et al., 2019).

In the literature, enterprise word has been discussed with entrepreneurship and entrepreneurs because it tends to be used interchangeably. Enterprise is an alternative term for a business or firm, as in the widely used term 'small and medium-sized enterprise' (SME), including *social enterprises*' such as cooperative, a limited company and community interest companies (Blundel, et al., 2018). An enterprise is defined as the smallest combination of legal units that is an organisational unit producing goods or services, which benefits from a certain degree of autonomy in decision-making, especially for allocating its current resources (OECD, 2017).

3.1.2 Entrepreneurship Classifications

There are many ways to act entrepreneurially. Ranges and scopes are determined by how the entrepreneurial activity is organised, its context, and the goals pursued (Blundel, et al., 2018). In that light, several categorisations of entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship exist:

- **Corporate entrepreneur/intrapreneur:** When entrepreneurial activities occur in an established organisation like government agencies, large corporations and charities. This form of entrepreneurship fosters ventures within major companies or with the assistance of corporations to meet their strategic objectives (Mishra & Zachary, 2014)
- **E-preneurs** are people running a business on the internet; they can be an owner of a sizeable online retail business or self-employed person using online shopping platforms such as eBay.com, Etsy.com, or gumtrees to sell products or services.

- **Ecopreneur** is an individual who establishes ventures or introduces new initiatives to tackle specific environmental problems.
- **Lifestyle entrepreneurs** choose businesses that reflect their passions and are more focused on doing something they love than on the pure profit motive for starting a company, such as a craftsperson with a pottery studio, or a sporting activity, such as leading horse-riding holidays. This type of entrepreneur prioritises quality of life over the general motive of running a business. In this case, pursuing business might not be for commercial purposes or expansion to large businesses but to achieve a reasonable income.
- **Portfolio entrepreneurs:** These people are conscious of uncertainty in business. These individuals operate different ventures simultaneously, intending to reduce risk at the interference of economic crisis, business failure, or depression and still maintain stable income. They are still in different categories ranging from highly wealthy tycoons to fewer people, usually based in rural areas. They are completely different from serial entrepreneurs.
- **Rural entrepreneurs** are business operators who operate in the countryside, usually traditional rural industries such as agriculture, forestry, food manufacturing, rural crafts, and running various businesses in the rural areas. To define this term geographically is difficult because they could be entrepreneurs in a village at the fringe of a large city or in a remote location that engages internationally.
- **Serial entrepreneurs** are different from **portfolio entrepreneurs**. These entrepreneurs establish several ventures over a period by reinvesting turnover from an existing business that might entirely be a new field but cannot be regarded as diversification.

- **Social entrepreneurs'** features can be categorised based on the primary goal of addressing social or environmental problems rather than making money. These are the founders of social ventures or initiators of a programme for social changes. Social entrepreneurship is where entrepreneurial ventures are driven by solving social or cultural issues instead of financial gain or profit (QAA, 2018). Social entrepreneurship has flourished significantly at the practical level but not at the theoretical level (Abu-Saifan, 2012). Social entrepreneurship is where entrepreneurs tailor their activities to be directly tied with the ultimate goal of creating social value (Abu-Saifan, 2012). A traditional entrepreneur's goal is to create economic wealth. In contrast, a social entrepreneur's priority is to fulfil the social mission because social entrepreneurs design revenue-generating strategies to serve the stated mission and deliver social value directly. Thus, social entrepreneurship, a venture, is developed with a mission to help a social cause (Mishra & Zachary, 2014).
- **Technology entrepreneur** is a term that typically describes the founder of a new venture to develop advanced technology that is paramount to information and communications technology (ICT), biotechnology, nanotechnology, and other applied sciences. It is usually associated with technology innovation and is fast-moving based on new scientific discoveries. A technology entrepreneur is recognised as a solution to societal challenges and essential to economic growth and international competition.
- **Green entrepreneurship** is where environmental problems are explored to result in a net positive impact on the natural environment using sustainable processes (QAA, 2018).
- **Digital entrepreneurship** is where digital products and services that are created are marketed, delivered and supported online (QAA, 2018).

- **Nascent entrepreneurs** are (alone or with others) actively engaged in creating a new venture and expect to be the owner or part-owner of this start-up.
- **Co-preneurships** are characterised as a family business, where a couple share management and the responsibility of running a common business (Franco & Piceti, 2020)

3.1.3 Basic Forms of Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship is a multi-faceted phenomenon, and some of the dichotomies of entrepreneurship in the literature include opportunity versus necessity, formal versus informal, and legal versus illegal (Welter, et al., 2016; Wennekers, 2006; Aulet & Murray, 2013; Angulo-Guerrero, et al., 2017; Reynolds, et al., 2001).

- **Opportunity Versus Necessity:** The distinction between necessity and opportunity entrepreneurship depends on the active motivation for activity (Desai, 2009). Opportunity entrepreneurship is an act of starting and growing a business to take advantage of a unique market opportunity, while necessity entrepreneurship is the best option available or, consequently, scarcity (Reynolds, et al., 2001; Angulo-Guerrero, et al., 2017). In more practical terms, an individual with a regular job who chooses to create and grow new firms is opportunity entrepreneurship. Those who have no better work choices are necessity entrepreneurship (Reynolds, et al., 2001). Furthermore, opportunity entrepreneurship is described as voluntary, possessed of high growth aspirations and identification of an attractive business opportunity involving innovative initiatives. Necessity entrepreneurship is the best option available, common in consumer-oriented sectors, involving initiatives that imitate other firms in less complex, lower cost and more immediately accessible to market sectors, building on a more difficult environment with limited opportunities and

mostly concentrated in developing countries (Reynolds, et al., 2001; Angulo-Guerrero, et al., 2017).

- **Occupational Versus Behavioural:** Occupational entrepreneurship refers to individuals owning and managing a business for their own gain and risk. Behavioural entrepreneurship is behaviour in the sense of seizing an economic opportunity (Wennekers, 2006).
- **Formal Versus Informal:** The classification of entrepreneurship as formal/informal and legal/illegal is not mutually exclusive, leading to confusion (Desai, 2009). The distinction between formal and informal entrepreneurship is determined by registration status (Desai, 2009). If a firm has registered with the appropriate government agency, it is a legal entity authorised to do business.
- **Legal Versus Illegal:** This dichotomy is often used interchangeably with the formal/informal dichotomy, though they are not the same. Legal firms are engaged in lawful activities. Traditional entrepreneurship applies to activities that are permitted by law (Desai, 2009).

3.2 Theoretical Framework

This research used four theoretical frameworks: Schumpeter's (1943) theory of economic development to aid understanding of how graduates entrepreneurs are moving into entrepreneurial activities, McClelland's (1961) need for achievement theory to understand how graduate entrepreneurs' feeling influences their entrepreneurial activities, Everett's (1959) theory of social change to examine if Nigerian graduates entrepreneurs are governed by tradition and authority in any of their business venture creation, and Ajzen's (1991) theory of planned behaviour to shed light on graduate entrepreneurs intention build their entrepreneurial activities. These theories are

presented diagrammatically in Figure 1 below. The researcher used these theories to aid understanding of the relationship between tertiary education and entrepreneurship. These are further discussed in detail below.

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework

Source 1: Prepared by the author

3.2.1 Theory of Economic Development

Schumpeter posited that entrepreneurs could not form a social class due to their temporary/transient economic functioning (Schumpeter, 1943). Then, it was assumed that only successful innovative entrepreneurs could have upward social mobility. This theory was based on the 'new combination' of the factors of production – land, labour, capital and organisation (entrepreneurship) called innovation. Therefore, the theorist outlined the prime motivation of entrepreneurs to attain higher social status as an individual or family. Schumpeter made the prerequisite assertion that 'the will and the action' are what anyone needs to be an entrepreneur. Then, he distinguished the innovator and placed that role much higher than the inventor from their origin at the same level. In a sense, that inventor discovers new methods and materials while innovating inventions and discoveries to make new combinations.

Schumpeter's entrepreneurs feature a stance that diverges from other economists' points of view. Simultaneously, he emphasised the individual capacity to learn, adapt, and

respond to process, behaviours and change responsively from the market context (Kirzner, 1973). Thus, Schumpeter responds to other economists' stance that the features of an individual who conducts businesses on a routine basis and not an innovative entrepreneur's distinctive character. Second, Schumpeter emphasised the entrepreneur's leadership as a very discrete individual who does not need to convince others about market desirability or the vision to lead meaningful production and only requires the bank to finance it. Furthermore, Schumpeter emphasised very three significant psychological motivations. These are a dream and willingness to have a private kingdom, willingness to conquer that is the impulse to fight, to prove oneself superior to others, to succeed for the sake of success itself and finally, the joy of creating, of getting things done or simply of exercising one's energy and ingenuity. Historically, Schumpeter's entrepreneurship model, first propounded in 1912 as the main thrust of this economic development theory, has proved to be an enduring and proven entrepreneurship model (Mehmood, et al., 2019).

Conversely, Schumpeter's theory is assumed to have a limited functional scope of an entrepreneur based on innovation emphasis only (Hafiz, et al., 2021; Quinlan, 2011). Also, Piano (2020) demonstrates that Schumpeter did not exalt the individual entrepreneur as the paradigm for economic and political leadership in capitalist societies. Piano further argued that continued emphasis on Schumpeter's alleged glorification of the entrepreneur constitutes a missed opportunity for democratic critics of capitalism and neoliberalism (Piano, 2020). Caution with Schumpeter's theory again is based on the assumption that 'countries lacking a democratic system, these conditions frequently are not fulfilled because it addressed the democratic and economically developed countries' (Pietak, 2014, p. 50).

However, this theory is very much in evidence in the business operations that make business improvements to add to their revenues, profits and market valuation (Mehmood, et al., 2019). Schumpeterian concepts and ideas are relevant and essential in any discussion on development (Thanawala, 1994). Therefore, economic development theory would help to validate the understanding of the Nigerian graduates' entrepreneurship motives. Additionally, Schumpeter's work is regarded as an unadulterated theory that provides a better life, such as was demonstrated by Argentina in the post-war era adopting 'third-way' corporatism and Catholic social doctrine that was recommended by the theorist (Ocampo, 2021)

3.2.2 Need for Achievement Theory

McClelland, a psychologist, contends that individuals have an inner feeling as a key to accomplishing their proposed work (McClelland, 1961). McClelland's theory is like motivational theories and closely associated with learning concepts with the central theme that needs are learned by coping with one's environment. The theorist proposes that when a demand is vital in a person, its effect is to motivate the person to use behaviour, leading to the satisfaction of the need. The theorist said the drive for these accomplishments is achievement, power, and affiliation needs while emphasising that only the first two propel entrepreneurship. McClelland's experiment results indicated that traditional beliefs could not hinder entrepreneurship as it was possible to internalise the motivation required for achievement orientation through training. The challenge with this theory is that 'it is too focused on stable intra-individual processes to the exclusion of important social, cultural, and contextual influences on motivation' (Urdana & Kaplanb, 2020, p. 2). Also, empirical findings on McClelland's contention that need for achievement is a cause of economic development, and not a result of economic

development, indicated that need for achievement had a much smaller effect on economic development than originally reported by McClelland and concluded that the link between the need for achievement and economic development had been overstated (Frey, 1983, p. 67). Opponents argued that the theory is empirically invalid, theoretically inadequate, and offers little value to those interested in promoting economic growth (Frey, 1984). However, this theory helps answer this study research question; recent research shows a significant positive effect between the need for achievement and student entrepreneurial intentions (Ekawarna, et al., 2020; Aprilia & Ardana, 2021).

3.2.3 Theory of Social Change

Hagen's theory of social change, also known as Hagen's withdrawal of status, was propounded on the basis that traditional society retains its stability (including economic stability) because the behaviour of its members (peasants and elite alike) is governed by the tradition and authority, rather than by initiative and autonomous decision making (Everett, 1959). The author stated that emulating western technology is not the solution to economic growth, but it is interwoven into political and social change by emphasising historical shift as a vital force that brought social changes such as technology that led to the emergence of entrepreneurial spirit in different communities. Furthermore, the author said the withdrawal of status and respect is the mechanism that encourages entrepreneurial activities, especially in an area that they gain power. Like other social-cultural theories, 'the groups alleged to possess a propensity to entrepreneurship display their predisposition only under limited, country-specific and historically specific conditions' (Co, 2003, p. 41). However, the theory of social change helps to understand Nigerian entrepreneurship activities in the socio-cultural context because it considers differences among societies and cultures in explaining entrepreneurial activity (Co,

2003). This is due to previous research that revealed the Nigerian entrepreneurship system existed before the introduction of formal education in entrepreneurship, which could refer to tradition and authority in respect of Hagen's theory. Therefore, this theory would help to understand education's impact on the final findings of this study.

3.2.4 Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB)

This theory predicts human behaviour dispositions at a given time and place and posited that the driver for these is the attitude toward behaviour, a social factor termed subjective norm, and degree of perceived behavioural control (Ajzen, 1991). The researcher adopted TPB to assess how Nigerian graduates entrepreneurs built and developed their business ventures based on the acquired education. This model has been described as innovative development research that clarifies the effectiveness and success of entrepreneurial programs (Ajzen, 1991). In support of this model, attitude, social norm, and perceived behavioural control are determining factors that help control graduates entrepreneurs in setting up their business venture (Iglesias-Sanchez, et al., 2016). However, this has been argued by scholars as it assumed the individual acquired resources and opportunities to deliver the desired behaviour successfully no matter the intention, it does not consider behavioural intention such as experience, mood, or fear, or the environmental and economic factors that have potential to influence intention in relation to behaviours (Young, et al., 2013; Kalafatis, et al., 1999). Nevertheless, this theory is relevant in this study because TPB is a well-founded, sound theory that can explain considerable proportions of intention and behaviour (Sommer, 2011, p. 102). This is crucial in this study as it will help to understand the trajectory of Nigerian graduates to entrepreneurship.

3.3 Significance of Education and Entrepreneurship and Interplay Between Them

The purpose of this theme is to present the significance of education and entrepreneurship and discuss their relationship.

3.3.1 Significance of Education

At every endeavour of life, education has been acknowledged as an essential prerequisite tool for developing an individual, society, or nation. It has been established that 'education is a foremost human basic need' (Agbowuro, et al., 2017, p. 37) that forms the 'main component of the construction of human capital' (Salgur, 2013, p. 50), in the sense that 'education provides knowledge and skills to the population, as well as shaping the personality and culture of the youth of a nation' (Idris, et al., 2012; Volkmann, et al., 2009). In a nutshell, 'education is the engine that fuels personal development, and societal and economic progress' (Volkmann, et al., 2009, p. 9).

Nationally, education is the live wire of its industries and the foundation of moral regeneration and revival of a people (Orji & Job, 2013; Mbah & Okeke, 2020). Asikiya and Boma (2015, p. 37) said: 'education is an invaluable tool for attaining national development'. It serves as the most critical factor for the foundation of social, economic, political, and cultural development (Agbowuro, et al., 2017; Salgur, 2013; Adeniyi, et al., 2021). Education develops a country's economy and society; therefore, it is the milestone of a nation's development (Idris, et al., 2012; Yasin & Khansari, 2020). For a country to accomplish successful economic progress, it must invest sufficiently and judiciously in education (Salgur, 2013, p. 50). Additionally, a study titled 'the role of education in shaping youth's national identity' revealed that 'education contributes to the formation of national identity' (Idris, et al., 2012).

Educationists acknowledge higher education as fundamental to constructing knowledge, economy, and society in all nations (Saint, et al., 2003). Therefore, education remains the engine that drives the growth and development of a country. In other words, it is inconceivable to imagine a learning process without education; in this case, higher education (Jaja, 2013). From a global perspective, economic and social development are increasingly driven by the advancement and application of knowledge (Saint, et al., 2003). Thus, empirical findings have established the importance of education and its contribution to economic development. Marquez-Ramos and Mourelle (2019) show that both secondary and tertiary education matter for economic growth. Also, it was found that 'education quality played a significant role in enhancing inclusive growth' (Adeniyi, et al., 2021, p. 180), and skill acquisition were found to have a significant effect on youth empowerment (Mbah & Okeke, 2020). Mbulawa and Mehta (2016) find that the level of access to education has a positive and significant effect on economic development. Another investigation revealed 'the existence of the feedback causality between education and sustainable economic growth' (Liao, et al., 2019, p. 1).

In a key message by Yan (2019, p. 5), important contributions of education are summarised as

the foundation for economic and social development that helps people become more competitive and productive in an evolving labour market through teaching, training, upskilling and reskilling, and prepares a population for the process of contributing to a healthy and stable society and enhancing social wellbeing and economic prosperity.

Therefore, school education can contribute to developing entrepreneurship skills and knowledge about business and entrepreneurs' role in society (Dragomir & Panzaru, 2015, p. 56).

3.3.2 Significance of Entrepreneurship

Scholars, professionals, and policymakers have written about the essence of entrepreneurship in individuals and society. It is seen as a value-add. Entrepreneurship is identified as a driver for economic development and growth, the competitive edge of a nation, employment generation, innovation, productivity, and social development (Bianchi & Biffignandi, 2012; Angulo-Guerrero, et al., 2017; Kuratko & Morris, 2018; Ahmad & Hoffman, 2007; Iglesias-Sanchez, et al., 2016; OECD, 2008; Dilanchiev, 2014; Ungureanu, 2020). This is because 'entrepreneurship is the engine fuelling innovation, employment generation and economic growth' (Volkman, et al., 2009, p. 9).

Likewise, globalisation reshapes the international economic landscape whereby technology changes create more significant uncertainty in the nation's economy; the dynamism of entrepreneurship is believed to be the solution (OECD, 2008; Esmer & Dayi, 2016; Adelaja, 2021). Entrepreneurship creates value directly throughout the economy without limiting financial wealth and jobs creation and tackling inequalities and environmental issues (McElwee, et al., 2018; OECD, 2008; Kuratko, 2007; OECD, 2015; Adeniyi, et al., 2021). Also, entrepreneurship implies more, such as environmental protection and ethical and value-based businesses (Mehmood, et al., 2019), and it is 'a source of creativity and innovation that significantly contributes to the development of societies' (Sanchez, et al., 2017, p. 463). Entrepreneurship is still recognised as a critical factor for a nation's wealth and competitiveness (Bianchi & Biffignandi, 2012; Awwad & Al-Aseer, 2021). Therefore, entrepreneurship is vitally important in creating wealth and developing society and companies (Hansemark, 1998; Awwad & Al-Aseer, 2021). Entrepreneurship is more than starting a business because entrepreneurship is an integrated concept that permeates our society and individuals (Kuratko, 2007).

3.3 Interplay Between Education and Entrepreneurship

The interrelation between education and entrepreneurship is explored here. First, 'education directed toward small business management is considered to be entrepreneurial education' (Hansemark, 1998, p. 32). Therefore, 'entrepreneurship education is the process of educating individuals with the ability to recognise commercial opportunities, insight, self-confidence, knowledge and skills and to start and run a business' (Dhar & Farzana, 2018, p. 99). With this understanding, 'entrepreneurship and education are two such extraordinary opportunities that need to be leveraged and interconnected if we are to develop the human capital required for building the societies of the future' (Volkman, et al., 2009, p. 6). A study shows that business owners' entrepreneurial education directly affects their individual firm performance (Lux, et al., 2020). That is why Dragomir and Panzaru (2015, p.56) emphasised that 'the most economically developed countries are those that pay special attention to education and are more interested in the development of the educational and training programs in entrepreneurship'.

Thus, Volkman et al. (2009), Hansemark (1998) and Sanchez et al. (2017) established that

- Education develops the skills that generate an entrepreneurial mindset and prepares future leaders for solving more complicated, interlinked and fast-changing problems (Volkman, et al., 2009).
- Entrepreneurship education provides a mix of experiential learning, skill-building and, most importantly, mindset shift (Volkman, et al., 2009).

- The entrepreneurship programme's fundamental purpose is to develop abilities, knowledge, skills, attitudes, and personal attributes necessary for entrepreneurial activity (Hansemark, 1998).
- Entrepreneurship education is one of the critical drivers of sustained social development and economic recovery (Volkman, et al., 2009).
- Entrepreneurship education is critical for developing entrepreneurial skills, attitudes and behaviours that are the basis for economic growth (Volkman, et al., 2009).
- Access and exposure to entrepreneurship within educational systems at all levels are vital as they are the outreach to target audiences outside of traditional educational methods (Volkman, et al., 2009).
- Entrepreneurship education has significantly contributed to creating businesses and developing countries (Sanchez, et al., 2017).

3.3.4 Empirical Evidence on the Relationship Between Education and Entrepreneurship

The above review shows that conceptually, education and entrepreneurship are linked, resulting in the enhancement of knowledge, skills, and confidence to start and sustain a business, which leads to individual well-being, national economic development and growth.

Empirical and evidence-based research on this subject substantiates the above links and relationships. In a study titled 'the relationship between education and entrepreneurship in EU member states', it was found that 'the probability of being an entrepreneur is higher among those who have participated in an entrepreneurship course' and 'there is a significant relationship between education and entrepreneurial spirit development' (Dragomir & Panzaru, 2015, p. 63). Also, Aboobaker & D (2020, p. 73) show that

'entrepreneurial training and education are effective in eliciting an important student-level outcome of entrepreneurial intention'. Another study in Nigeria indicated a significantly positive relationship between entrepreneurship education and students' entrepreneurial intentions (Otache, 2019). Similarly, a meta-analysis by Bae et al. (2014, p. 217) on 'the relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intentions' found 'a significant but a small correlation between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intentions' and concluded that 'entrepreneurship education was related more positively to a participant's entrepreneurial intentions than was business education'. Furthermore, studies on 'a new index of entrepreneurship measure' found education a positive factor contributing to entrepreneurial performance (Bianchi & Biffignandi, 2012, p. 14). Also, an investigation on 'the impact of educational levels on formal and informal entrepreneurship' indicated that 'tertiary education increases formal entrepreneurship because of the higher self-confidence, lower perceived risk and enhanced human capital' (Jimenez, et al., 2015, p. 204).

3.4 Measurement of Entrepreneurship

This topic is vital to this study as entrepreneurship measurement helps determine why and where entrepreneurship flourishes and assesses the effects of public policies (Bianchi & Biffignandi, 2012; Kuratko & Morris, 2018). Some entrepreneurship measurement organisations are the GEDI and its Global Entrepreneurship Index (GEI), Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) and the OECD/EUROSTAT framework for entrepreneurship indicators. Here, the GEDI GEI is considered because of its scope and data availability.

3.4.1 Global Entrepreneurship Index (GEI)

The GEDI is a Washington, DC-based policy development organisation dedicated to expanding economic opportunities for individuals, communities, and nations (GEDI, 2018). Researchers at Imperial College Business School, George Mason University and the Universities of Strathclyde, Aston and Pecs, have developed it to measure and rank a country's entrepreneurial capacity. The GEDI methodology collects data on the entrepreneurial attitudes, abilities and aspirations – the 3As of the local population – and then weighs these against the prevailing social and economic 'infrastructure'. These three sub-indexes stand on 14 pillars – quasi-independent building blocks, each containing an individual and an institutional variable that correspond to the micro-and the macro-level aspects of entrepreneurship. These 14 pillars refer to Global Entrepreneurship Index (GEI) methodologies, a composite indicator of the entrepreneurship ecosystem health in each country. Therefore, it measures the quality and dynamics of entrepreneurship interconnectedness at a national, regional and local level (Acs, et al., 2018). The pillars are explained as follows.

- **Opportunity Perception:** This refers to the population's entrepreneurial opportunity perception potential and weighs this against the freedom of the country and property rights. Asking the question, can the population identify opportunities to start a business and does the institutional environment make it possible to act on those opportunities?
- **Start-up Skills:** Start-up skill captures the perception of start-up skills in the population and weighs this aspect with education quality. The question is, do the people have the skills necessary to start a business based on their perceptions and tertiary education availability?

- **Risk Acceptance:** This captures the inhibiting effect of fear of failure of the population on entrepreneurial action combined with a measure of the country's risk. The question asks, are individuals willing to take the risk of starting a business? Is the environment relatively low risk, or do unstable institutions add additional risk to starting a business?
- **Networking:** This pillar combines two aspects of networking: (1) a proxy of the ability of potential and active entrepreneurs to access and mobilise opportunities and resources and (2) the ease of access to reach each other. It asks, do entrepreneurs know each other and how geographically concentrated are their networks?
- **Cultural Support:** The cultural support pillar combines how positively a given country's inhabitants view entrepreneurs in terms of status and career choice and how the level of corruption in that country affects this view. The item asks, how does the country view entrepreneurship? Is it easy to choose entrepreneurship, or does corruption make entrepreneurship difficult relative to other career paths?
- **Opportunity Start-up:** This pillar captures the prevalence of individuals who pursue potentially better-quality opportunity-driven start-ups (as opposed to necessity-driven start-ups) weighed with the combined effect of taxation and government quality of services. It asks, are entrepreneurs motivated by opportunity rather than necessity, and does governance make the choice to be an entrepreneur easy?
- **Technology Absorption:** The technology absorption pillar reflects the technology intensity of a country's start-up activity combined with a country's capacity for firm-level technology absorption. The question asks, is the technology sector large and can businesses rapidly absorb new technology?
- **Human Capital:** The human capital pillar captures the quality of entrepreneurs by measuring the percentage of start-ups founded by individuals with higher than

secondary education with a qualitative measure of the propensity of firms in each country to train their staff combined with the freedom of the labour market. The question asks, are entrepreneurs highly educated, well trained in business and able to move freely in the labour market?

- **Competition:** This pillar measures the level of the product or market uniqueness of start-ups combined with the market power of existing businesses and business groups and the effectiveness of competitive regulation. It asks the question: Are entrepreneurs creating unique products and services and entering the market with them?
- **Product Innovation:** This captures the tendency of entrepreneurial firms to create new products weighed by the technology transfer capacity. The question asks, is the country able to develop new products and integrate new technology?
- **Process Innovation:** This pillar captures the use of new technologies by start-ups combined with the gross domestic expenditure on research and development (GERD) and a country's potential to conduct applied research. It asks whether businesses use new technology and can access high-quality human capital in STEM fields?
- **High Growth:** This pillar is a combined measure of (1) the percentage of high-growth businesses that intend to employ at least ten people and plan to grow more than 50% in five years, (2) the availability of venture capital, and (3) business strategy sophistication. The question asks, do businesses intend to grow and have the strategic capacity to achieve this growth?
- **Internationalisation:** This pillar captures the degree to which a country's entrepreneurs are internationalised, as measured by businesses' exporting potential weighted by the country's economic complexity. The question asks, do entrepreneurs

want to enter global markets, and is the economy complex enough to produce ideas that are valuable globally?

- **Risk Capital:** This pillar combines two finance measures: informal investment in start-ups and a measure of the depth of the capital market. It looks at the availability of risk capital to fulfil growth aspirations. It asks, how is money available from both individual and institutional investors?

The three as mentioned above are the building blocks of entrepreneurship, each influences the others, and none is of equal importance. Entrepreneurial attitudes influence entrepreneurial abilities and entrepreneurial aspirations, and entrepreneurial aspirations and abilities also influence entrepreneurial attitudes.

The attitude sub-index measures society's necessary attitudes toward entrepreneurship through education and social stability. The activity sub-index measures what individuals are doing to improve human resources and technological efficiency. The aspiration sub-index measures how much entrepreneurial activity is being directed toward innovation, high-impact entrepreneurship, and globalisation. Attitudes are an essential prerequisite for either activity or aspirations (Imperial College London, 2018).

3.5 Conceptual Framework

In line with this study's aim to unpack the relationship between tertiary education and entrepreneurship in Nigeria, the research model in Figure 1 below is developed for education and entrepreneurship interplay in Nigeria.

From Figure 1, the research model for education and entrepreneurship interplay in Nigeria proposes that there is no positive influences of tertiary education (H_4) on the entrepreneurial skills development in Nigeria (Dragomir & Panzaru, 2015; Adamu, 2015; Oguntimehin & Olaniran, 2017; GEM, 2012; Omoniwa & Adedapo, 2017; Babajide, et al.,

2020; Yasin & Khansari, 2020). In turn, there seems to be no positive relationship between the level of entrepreneurs (H₁) and outturns of tertiary institution graduates in Nigeria (Babalobi, 2019; Aririah, 2021; Nwosu & Chukwudi, 2018; Odumosu, et al., 2020). Similarly, there seems to be a negative relationship between entrepreneurship (H₂) and types of Nigerian graduate jobs (Adamu, 2015; Olorundare & Kayode, 2014; Olaore, et al., 2021). Also, there is no positive relationship between educated entrepreneurs (H₅) and successful entrepreneurs in Nigeria (Iglesias-Sanchez, et al., 2016; Hernandez-Sanchez, et al., 2019; Kolstad & Wiig, 2015; Hagg & Gabrielsson, 2021).

Therefore, there is likely no correlation between entrepreneurship (H₃) and tertiary education in Nigeria (Hansemark, 1998; Dragomir & Panzaru, 2015; Storen, 2014; Otache, 2019; Vicens, et al., 2021).

Figure 2: Conceptual Model for Education and Entrepreneurship Interplay in Nigeria

Source 2: Literature Review Synthesis

3.6 Development of Research Questions and Hypotheses

The ultimate objective of this study is to examine the interplay between tertiary education and entrepreneurship in Nigeria. As established in the literature, education

and entrepreneurship intersect and coexist as agents of innovative change, technological development, and competitiveness at both individual and national levels. Therefore, an insight into the relationship between education and entrepreneurship in Nigeria is essential because it will drive solutions to the high rate of unemployment, poverty and economic crisis in Nigeria. Also, limited research analysed the impact of the education reform on entrepreneurship in Nigeria, and it stands as justification for this study. Therefore, the main research questions and rationales in the view of the literature review were identified as follows:

RQ1: Is there a positive relationship between the level of entrepreneurs and outturns of tertiary institution graduates in Nigeria?

The reason for RQ1 includes the following. There are many investigations around entrepreneurship education, even in Nigeria. However, few studies in Nigeria examine entrepreneurship education with tertiary education and even fewer researched its relationship with outturns of tertiary institution graduates. This is the case in a review of Nigerian entrepreneurship education literature published in 20 journals over a 16-year period, and ‘the main finding of the paper is that related concepts like skills, intention, drive and attitude have been used in expounding discussions on the outcome of entrepreneurship education, but very little has been written on entrepreneurial mindset’ (Yatu, et al., 2018, p. 165). These showed a gap. Research is required to give insight into the gap between the number of graduates and the number of entrepreneurs. Therefore, H₁ is postulated as follows

H₁ – There seems to be no positive relationship between the level of entrepreneurs and outturns of tertiary institution graduates in Nigeria

RQ2: Is there a negative relationship between entrepreneurship and types of Nigerian graduate jobs?

The reason for RQ2 is the following. First, 'entrepreneurship is the engine fuelling innovation, employment generation and economic growth' (Volkman, et al., 2009, p. 9). Likewise, 'education is used to inspire entrepreneurship among young graduates for them to be able to produce job opportunities for themselves and their peers' (Bakar, et al., 2015, p. 88). Also, education can contribute to encouraging entrepreneurial initiative and entrepreneurial attitude development (Dragomir & Panzaru, 2015). In particular, 'entrepreneurship education is the type of education that seeks to provide students with the knowledge, skills and motivation to encourage entrepreneurial success in a variety of settings' (Olorundare & Kayode, 2014, p. 167). These show the consistency of the intersection of education and entrepreneurship. Hence, Nigeria has a long history of established higher institutions of learning and adaptation of entrepreneurship education curriculum that has been compulsory at all levels of tertiary education for about two decades, irrespective of the programme of the students (FRN, 2004; Yahya, 2011; FGN, 2019). However, it was found that 'Nigerians had no professional skills to enable them to stand on their own or even establish and manage their ventures' (Adamu, 2015, p. 86). Again, another study found that Nigerian universities produce graduates best suited for white-collar employment with little or no basic skills of any other vocational relevance (Olorundare & Kayode, 2014). Therefore, Nigeria has a growing unemployment problem, rising steeply from 3.6% in 2006 to 23.1% in 2018 (NESG, 2020). These points substantiate that, despite the established interplay of education and entrepreneurship, it is inconsistent in the context of Nigeria as most graduates want to secure white-collar jobs and present without the necessary skills. This study fills this gap by linking

entrepreneurship with types of Nigerian graduates' jobs. Accordingly, the hypothesis is formulated:

H₂ – There seems to be a negative relationship between entrepreneurship and types of Nigerian graduate jobs

RQ3: Is there a correlation between entrepreneurship and tertiary education in Nigeria?

Literature has indicated that education and entrepreneurship intersect and coexist as agents of innovative change, technological development and competitiveness at both individual and national levels. Likewise, the entrepreneurship programme noted serves the fundamental purpose of developing abilities, knowledge, skills, attitudes, and personal attributes necessary for entrepreneurial activity (Hansemark, 1998). Empirically, a study found 'there is a significant relationship between education and entrepreneurial spirit development' (Dragomir & Panzaru, 2015, p. 63). Equally, 'one specific learning outcome of entrepreneurship education is that it promotes entrepreneurial and innovative orientations that go beyond the question of starting up one's own business' (Storen, 2014, p. 798). However, another study indicated that entrepreneurship education had no connection with entrepreneurial orientation or business performance (Cho & Lee, 2018). These studies show the overlap of entrepreneurship and education. Therefore, this study examines the similarities in the context of Nigeria as part of the overall objective.

H₃ – There is likely no correlation between entrepreneurship and tertiary education in Nigeria

RQ4: Are there positive influences of tertiary education on entrepreneurial skills development in Nigeria?

The reason for RQ4 is as follows. There is an emphasis that 'school education can contribute to developing entrepreneurship skills and knowledge about business and entrepreneurs' role in society' (Dragomir & Panzaru, 2015, p. 56). Also, the findings show that the Nigerian universities' entrepreneurship education curriculum contents are relevant for sustainable development but do not equip students with adequate knowledge and skills to be self-employed (Nwambam, et al., 2018). Another study finds that Nigerians had no professional skills to enable them to stand on their own or even establish and manage their ventures (Adamu, 2015, p. 86). However, the result of the studies of 'the relationship between entrepreneurship education and students' entrepreneurial intentions in Ogun State-owned universities, Nigeria' indicated that 'entrepreneurship education significantly influences students' entrepreneurial intentions' (Oguntimehin & Olaniran, 2017). Similarly, GEM (2012, p. 45) reports, 'Nigeria leads the world in the proportion of the population who believe they have the skills to run a business; almost 90% of Nigerian adults think they have the ability to become entrepreneurs'. Likewise, another study revealed that a 'substantial percentage of the sampled respondents believed that the Nigerian graduates were employable' (Omoniwa & Adedapo, 2017, p. 58). These implied inconsistencies and called for research to understand why. This study fulfils this purpose. Therefore, the study postulates as follows.

H₄ – There is no positive influences of tertiary education on the entrepreneurial skills development in Nigeria

RQ5: Is there a positive relationship between educated entrepreneurs and successful entrepreneurs in Nigeria?

The reason for RQ5 is as follows. Education is acknowledged to play a prominent role in entrepreneurs' perception, confidence, ability and level of conviction (Iglesias-Sanchez, et al., 2016). Empirical evidence has shown that 'entrepreneurship education programmes significantly influenced the entrepreneurial activity of autonomous communities' (Hernandez-Sanchez, et al., 2019, p. 1). Likewise, another study finds education significantly affects entrepreneurial profitability (Kolstad & Wiig, 2015). It implies an intersection of educated entrepreneurs and successful entrepreneurs. Therefore, this study is accessing the two constructs in the Nigerian context as part of the overall objectives. The related hypothesis is stated below.

H₅ – There is no positive relationship between educated entrepreneurs and successful entrepreneurs in Nigeria.

3.7 Chapter Summary and Conclusions

The chapter reviewed literature surrounding entrepreneurship and education. It started with the brief historical meaning of entrepreneurship and its definition identified as an indistinct trajectory raised from different disciplines. Then, entrepreneurship classifications and dichotomies were discussed to understand the kinds of entrepreneurs. The theoretical framework for this study comprised economic development theory, need for achievement theory, theory of social change, and TPB. These theories were identified and adopted to help understand the relationship between tertiary education and entrepreneurship. It also revealed the significance of and relationship between education and entrepreneurship and the measurement of the various countries' entrepreneurship activities.

The chapter further explored applications of entrepreneurship education in Nigeria and found that entrepreneurship education belief is not new in Nigeria; Nigerians have been involved in traditional or informal entrepreneurship before the colonial era. Traditional entrepreneurship involved Nigerians of various ethnic nationalities in an enterprising attitude of self-employment and self-sufficiency through active involvement in artisanship, crafts and farming. As individual needs increased, Nigerians engaged in exchanging goods for goods or services, which encourage their individual specialisation and concentration on areas of production they are best fitted for until money was introduced worldwide.

Nigeria's transition from the traditional entrepreneurship system started in the 20th century when the colonial government began to provide a Western education to produce staff who can serve as administrative officers, clerks, teachers, interpreters, and other liberal arts graduates. After Nigeria achieved independence, the government delivered the same content and structure of formal education, but that system is not what is needed in the present state. It led Nigeria to a higher unemployment rate, poverty, and economic crisis as many Nigerians now depend on white-collar jobs and do not possess the technical skills needed. The colonial government educational policy was blamed for this situation.

Unemployment, poverty, and economic crisis continue to ravage Nigeria. The federal government of Nigeria considered options and formally adopted an entrepreneurship education curriculum at all levels of tertiary educations. In the same vein that formal education inherited from the colonial government does not meet present-day needs, this new curriculum has also failed to meet present-day needs despite its prospect and Nigerian government actions.

In the light of this study's aims, the literature reviewed and based on the revelations of the literature, a research model was developed, and research questions were generated and translated into hypotheses.

Chapter Four covers information on the research approach and methodology of this study. The instrumented research questions to fill the study gap were answered by engaging philosophical assumptions, research approach, research designs, research methods, data collection methods, and analysis.

CHAPTER FOUR: RESEARCH APPROACH AND METHODOLOGY

4.1. Research Philosophy

When adopting a research philosophy, a researcher needs to take a position in a specific approach before a research philosophy stance is established (Cameron, 2011; Saunders, et al., 2019) as that approach contains an essential assumption about the way researchers view or concept of the world (Saunders & Lewis, 2012; Walliman, 2011). The three types of assumptions that distinguish research philosophies include ontology, epistemology, and axiology (Saunders, et al., 2019). They are defined as follows: the ontology assumption is a researcher's view about the nature of realities encountered in research, the epistemology assumption is the researcher's concept about human knowledge (acceptable, valid, and legitimate knowledge), and the axiology assumption is the researcher's view about the extent and ways the researcher's values and ethics influence the research process (Rahi, 2017; Saunders, et al., 2019; Scotland, 2012). Therefore, the way the researcher's belief and assumption are relevant to this study's research design and research philosophy is the epistemology philosophical assumption.

Saunders, et al. (2016) highlighted that pluralism and unificationism philosophies emerged from different disciplines due to the emergence of the business and management academic discipline in the twentieth century. The formal embrace of diversity enriches the business and management discipline. However, scholars later argued that diversity made the field fragmented and deprived it of becoming a proper scientific discipline (Saunders, et al., 2019). This study is built on the pluralism stance.

In the same vein, the multidimensional continuum of philosophical assumption also emerged called objectivism and subjectivism. Saunders, et al. (2016) assert that objectivism incorporates the assumption of natural sciences, which state that social

reality is external to research and other social actors, while subjectivism incorporates the assumption of the arts and humanities that social reality is made from the perspectives and consequent actions of social actors. Additionally, research paradigms also differentiate between research philosophies. It is defined as 'a set of basic and taken-for-granted assumptions that underwrite the frame of reference, mode of theorising and ways of working in which a group operates' (Saunders, et al., 2019, p. 140).

The major five business and management philosophies are positivism, critical realism, interpretivism, postmodernism and pragmatism, according to Saunders et al. (2019). The authors explained as follows. Positivism takes a philosophical stance on the physical and natural sciences with a highly structured method to facilitate replication, resulting in law-like generalisations. Critical realism declared that objects exist independently of the social actors' knowledge with the claim that there are sensations and during the experience of an event, and there is mental processing that goes on after an experience when reasoning backwards from an experience to the underlying reality. Critical realism developed in the critique of positivism but from a subjectivism perspective, which emphasises that humans are different from physical phenomena because they create meanings to create new, richer understandings and interpretations of social words and contexts. Then, postmodernism emphasises the role of language and power relations, seeking to question accepted ways of thinking and give voice to alternative marginalised views; this places more importance on the role of language. Thus, pragmatists strive to reconcile both objectivism and subjectivism, facts and values, accurate and rigorous knowledge and different contextualised experiences by placing importance on research questions and objectives as the determinant of the research philosophy to be adopted.

Thus, this study adopts the epistemological assumption because of the variables under investigation, tertiary institutions and entrepreneurship, which are about the relationship of what constitutes acceptable, valid, and legitimate knowledge and effective communication between both variables. Also, the subjectivists' assumption stance is incorporated in this work because entrepreneurship as a social reality is investigated from the perspective of Nigerian tertiary institution graduate entrepreneurs.

The researcher is guided by research problems and questions, and these determine research design and strategy. Therefore, the research philosophical stance for this study is pragmatism. Reality is important in this study as the practical effects of the ideas, and the knowledge of the Nigerian tertiary institutions' graduates and entrepreneurs are the determinant of this study outcomes. The researcher's passion for this research subject is because of the importance of entrepreneurship, the problems observed in embedding the entrepreneurship curriculum into Nigerian tertiary institutions and the intention to contribute practical solutions that will inform the future. Epistemology assumptions are positioned under the positivism, interpretivism and social constructionism/constructivism paradigms (Quinlan, 2011). In realising each paradigm's aims, the positivists seek to generalise, the interpretivists strive for understanding, and the constructionists look for emancipation.

4.2 Research Approaches

The research approach adopted for this study is the deductive approach. First, the researcher reviewed literature and adopted theories to the established tertiary education and entrepreneurship relationship. Hypotheses are formed on the premises of subject variables (tertiary education and entrepreneurship). The study aims to establish if there are causal relationships between tertiary education and entrepreneurship. In light of this

research objective(s) set, the researcher is systematically gathering appropriate data to test the hypothesis (i.e., testing the theoretical positions identified in this study). Furthermore, the researcher planned to measure data to be collected numerically and analyse the data with statistical and graphical techniques. Finally, the results of the analysis are intended to support the theories or make recommendations for modification. Basically, the main approaches to theory development in the business and management field are categorised into deductive, inductive, and abductive (retroduction) approaches (Saunders, et al., 2019). The clarification of the researcher's approach in a study is important when either testing or building theory at the beginning of a study because it concerns the design of the research project (Saunders, et al., 2019). The deductivist method is when a general set of propositions about a subject under investigation is narrowed to a specific set of testable hypotheses or to a single testable hypothesis (Adams, et al., 2007). Therefore, the deductive project is driving by theory, and it operates from 'the general to the specific' (Adams, et al., 2007, p. 29). The opposite of deductive is the inductive research approach. An inductivist researcher relies on the empirical verification of a general conclusion derived from a finite number of observations (Adams, et al., 2007). Simply, it operates from general to specific. The abductive research approach is when data is collected, themes identified, and patterns explained with the aim to generate a new or modify an existing theory and subsequently test through additional data collection (Saunders, et al., 2019).

4.3 The Process of Research Design

This is the general plan on how the researcher wants to test the hypotheses or answer research questions that will contain a clear objective set, the specific source of data, the process of data collection and analysis, discussion of ethical issues and inevitable

constraints (Saunders, et al., 2019). This is also a way to turn research questions into a research project and achieve coherence. The research design is the blueprint for fulfilling research objectives and answering research questions (Adams, et al., 2007). In other words, it establishes the decision-making processes, the conceptual structure of the investigation, and the analysis methods to address the study's central research problem. Thus, it helps organise thoughts, set the study boundary, maximise the reliability, viability, and generalisation of the study findings, and avoid misleading or incomplete conclusions (Saunders, et al., 2019). Furthermore, this topic is essential because 'research design provides a framework for the collection and analysis of data and subsequently indicates which research methods are appropriate' (Walliman, 2011, p. 13). Again, that is why Adams, et al. (2007) emphasised that this is a critical aspect of the whole research process, and failure to address research design issues correctly can have serious consequences for any findings generated in a study. In that light, the following topics are discussed.

4.3.1 Methodological Choice

Evidence from the literature shows quantitative and qualitative research as two main types of research based on the kind of evidence in the business and management field that researchers frequently observed (Adams, et al., 2007; Saunders, et al., 2016). According to Adams, et al (2007),

quantitative research is the type of research that is based on the methodological principles of positivism and neopositivism and adheres to the standards of a strict research design developed prior to the actual research, while qualitative research is the type of research that uses a number of methodological approaches based on diverse theoretical principles (Phenomenology, Hermeneutics and Social Interactionism) (Adams, et al., 2007, p. 27).

Also, qualitative research explores attitudes, behaviour and experiences, while quantitative research generates statistics through large-scale survey research (Dawson, 2002). Quantitative and qualitative research are distinguished by data types, sources, collection techniques, and analysis procedures an investigator intends to adopt towards realising research objectives (Saunders, et al., 2019). Mixed-method research is defined as 'the class of research where the researcher mixes or combines quantitative and qualitative research techniques, methods, approaches, concepts or language into a single study' (Johnson & Onwuegbuzie, 2004, p. 17). In other words, a mixed methods study undertakes a combination of quantitative research and qualitative research features.

Therefore, the researcher implements a mixed methods research design in this study because history will help any researcher remember facts before turning them into statistical explanations or analysis. For instance, the present state of entrepreneurship and tertiary education in Nigeria must be gathered while also examining the past record. Adopting a mixed method approach can establish the relationship between tertiary education and entrepreneurship in Nigeria and gather enough data. Following Morgan's (2019) position, the underlying goal of using the qualitative and quantitative components is to cover more content than is possible by either method alone.

The choice of mixed methods research design for this study is consistent with the chosen research philosophy (pragmatism) to demonstrate coherence across this research design. This is the branch of multiple methods research that combines quantitative and qualitative techniques and analytical procedures (Saunders, et al., 2019).

Thus, it could be said that the researcher is following a trend, but it is based on the importance and facts of the mixed methods approach that will help actualise this study objective. There is a proliferation of work and a growth in popularity of studies combining

combine quantitative and qualitative methodologies over the last decade to explore social phenomena (Uprichard & Dawney, 2019; Cameron, et al., 2015). Using mixed methods by doctoral research candidates is recognised as ensuring that the candidates are properly trained in research design and methodology (Miller & Cameron, 2011). Furthermore, through mixed methods adoption, data integration is fundamental to the study and exploration of the social world (Uprichard & Dawney, 2019). Mixed methods research can provide significant insights into research problems and address complex phenomena (Cameron, et al., 2015). Mixed methods designs are well suited to research that attempts to explain socio-political action within a post-positivist epistemological framework (Gamlen & McIntyre, 2018). Therefore, the researcher will build capacity as a doctoral student by adopting mixed methods and gathering and integrating data sequentially.

One of the issues with mixed methods research adoption reported by Cameron et al. (2015) is that some researchers are not acquainted with the growing body of foundational concepts developing in the mixed methods research community.

4.3.2 Purpose of the Study

In business and management discipline, research projects are designed to satisfy a purpose(s) such as exploratory, descriptive, explanatory, evaluative, or combination of these (Saunders, et al., 2019). The authors further say the determinant of the purpose a researcher is fulfilling is the way the research questions are asked, and the purpose of a study can be change over time. Therefore, an explanation of research purposes deduced from Saunders et al. (2019) work is offered below.

- An exploratory study is designed to fulfil the purpose of discovery and gaining insights into a particular subject of focus or phenomenon while asking research questions or data collection questions that start with 'what' or 'how'. Usually, research

helps to clarify understanding of an issue or problem, and it can be conducted by searching the literature and relatively unstructured interview with expertise, individual in-depth, or focus groups. Also, it moves from the broad focus to the narrow with the great advantage of flexibility and adaptability to change, but the conclusion might need strong caution before being taken.

- Descriptive researchers intend to fulfil the purpose of presenting an accurate profile of events, situations or people. The research questions and questions for data collection under descriptive research are likely to include any of who, what, where, when, or how. It may be an extension of exploratory research or a forerunner of explanatory research. It is important for the researcher to have a clear understanding of the phenomenon before the data collection takes place. Research work is expected to go a bit further than just describing with depicting and evaluating skills and synthesising ideas. Therefore, it is strongly recommended that descriptive research should be a means to an end rather than an end by itself.
- Explanatory research may be designed for the purpose of establishing causal relationships between concepts. Identifying a research type of this nature is that questions for data collection and research questions start with or include 'why' or 'how'. Therefore, it is a study of a situation or problem to explain the relationships between variables.
- Evaluative research is a study designed to investigate a phenomenon to find and indicate how it has been performing. The evaluative research questions could start with 'how' or include 'what' (such as 'to what extent'). Additionally, data collection questions could begin with or include 'what', 'how', or 'why'. This type of research usually assesses policy, business strategy, or initiatives, and it could make a comparison between situations, events, groups, or periods while asking questions

that include 'how', 'what', 'where', or 'who'. Therefore, evaluative research helps to assess performance and in any subject of focus.

- Finally, combining studies is when researcher investigation focuses on fulfilling more than one purpose (descriptive, exploratory, explanatory, and evaluative) in a single study. A combined study's purpose can be achieved with a mixed methods research design or a single method research.

Therefore, this study is a combined purposes research. First, the descriptive research purpose was illustrated in this study at the starting point where the researcher presented the rationale for the research topic and discussed the themes in the literature. That process can be understood as an avenue to present an accurate profile of education and entrepreneurship broadly, which led to the formulation of the hypotheses. This study's second research purpose is explanatory, considering the subject focus, which intends to establish the relationship of tertiary education and entrepreneurship and formulate some of the secondary and primary questions for data collection, including questions such as 'How important do you see an act of creating a business venture in Nigeria?' Furthermore, the researcher showcases fulfilling the evaluative research purpose. This is indicated in the study's rationale when the researcher emphasised the Nigerian education reform in the year 2004, where entrepreneurship education was embedded in the curriculum. Also, the question for data collection include 'To what extent do you think Nigerian regulatory bodies support business start-ups?' and 'How often do you have tertiary institution graduate positions vacant in your organisation?'

4.3.3 Research Strategies

A research strategy is defined as how a researcher wants to answer research questions (Saunders, et al., 2019). In the same vein, different traditions manifested in business and

management led to many philosophical assumptions and research strategies. Therefore, types of research strategies suggested in the business and management academic field include experiment, survey, archival/documentary, case study, ethnography, action research, and grounded theory (Saunders & Lewis, 2012; Saunders, et al., 2019). These strategies are explained as follows.

1. Experimental strategy is

a research strategy that involves the definition of a theoretical hypothesis; the selection of a sample of individuals from the known population; the allocation of samples to different experimental conditions; the introduction of planned change on one or more of the variables; and measurement on a small number of variables and control of other variables. (Saunders & Lewis, 2012, p. 114)

In other words, the experiment strategy is a study of the cause and effect of linked variables to establish whether a change in an independent variable is making changes in another dependent variable. It owes much to natural sciences but still features strongly in social science research and psychological research (Saunders, et al., 2019). Thus, an explanation used by experiment strategy is hypothetical (null hypothesis and hypothesis) rather than research questions because the researcher hypothesises if a relationship exists between variables (Saunders, et al., 2019). The categories of experimental research include laboratory, experimental, and field studies.

2. A survey is a popular strategy in business and management research and is most frequently used to answer 'what', 'where', 'how much', and 'how many' questions (Saunders, et al., 2019). It is usually associated with an inductive research approach and an exploratory and descriptive research purpose (Saunders, et al., 2019). Survey research is a study that focuses on the population or the universe where data are collected from the population for intensive study analysis (Asika, 1991). The problem

with this strategy is the researcher's ability to select samples that will determine whether the findings can be generalised to the whole population or universe. Therefore, a popular survey strategy is a questionnaire; others include structured observation and structured interviews.

3. Archival and documentary research is a type of research strategy using data collection that focuses on secondary data collections. Therefore, it is defined as a research strategy that analyses administrative records and documents as the principal data sources (Saunders & Lewis, 2012). This strategy may be effective and efficient because it provides a rich source of data for analysis. Still, the researcher needs to be sensitive as the archives or documents data might not have been created for research purposes (Saunders, et al., 2019). Therefore, the research question would be the determinant of appropriateness and the accessibility of sufficient suitable documents. It might necessitate combining research strategies in a single study, such as documentary research, grounded theory strategy or documentary research, and a case study research strategy. These sources include emails, letters, blog posting, diaries, electronic calendars, agendas, policy statements, reports, publications, and so on.
4. A case study is 'a research strategy which involves the investigation of a particular contemporary topic within its real-life context, using multiple sources of evidence' (Saunders & Lewis, 2012, p. 116). The 'case' in case study research may refer to a person, a group, an organisation, an association, a change process, or an event (Saunders, et al., 2019). The case study strategy is mostly used for exploratory and explanatory research purposes. It is more appropriate to ask why' although 'what' and 'how' are also relevant (Saunders & Lewis, 2012). The case study research strategy is different from most other strategies based on its real-life setting or context (Saunders,

et al., 2019). For instance, experimental strategy contextualises variables that are controllable because it is seen as a threat to the result validity. The advantages of a case study strategy include an avenue for a researcher to understand the context of the research and the activities taking place within the context. However, case studies are usually criticised as a research strategy for generalisable, reliable and theoretical contribution knowledge because of their small samples' usage (Saunders, et al., 2019). Various data collection techniques can be used in case study research, including interviews, observation, documentary analysis, and questionnaires. The issues that arise with this type of strategy are whether a single case study or more than one is most suitable for a particular project, like other strategies discussed. It will be governed by what is ideal to answer the research question, availability, and accessibility to resources.

The approaches to a case study strategy that emerged in the literature include orthodox case study strategy and emergent case study strategy. 'An orthodox case strategy involves an approach that is rigorously defined and highly structured before the research commences, with the intention that it will proceed in a linear way' and 'an emergent case study strategy involves a researcher strategically choosing a case study environment within which research will be conducted but allowing the focus of the research to emerge through the engagement in the setting and with relevant literature' (Saunders, et al., 2019, p. 198). The orthodox case study strategy can be seen in orderly processes from 'literature review' to 'defining research question' to 'research project designed' to 'undertaken research' to 'data collection, analysis, and interpretation', to final stage 'report presentation'. Meanwhile, the emergent case study strategy seems opposite to the orthodox case study strategy because the core focus is emerging from the adopted case and literature.

The case study strategy is distinguished in four different ways and follows the explanation based on Saunders et al. (2019) work. First, a single case study strategy is a case the researcher purposely selected with a phenomenon that provides an opportunity to observe and analyse. Second, the multiple cases strategy occurs when a researcher incorporates various cases into a single project, usually justified by focusing on whether the outcomes could be replicated across chosen cases. Then, when the researcher predicted similar results in many cases carefully chosen, and the findings resulted in the same outcome, it is called a 'literal replication'. When sets of cases are selected with deliberate contextual factor differences, the anticipated results are predicted by the researchers, and the predicted variation result is achieved and is called 'theoretical replication'. The third and fourth are holistic and embedded case study strategies defined or referred to as 'the unit of analyses'. For instance, if a researcher chose and treated an organisation as a whole concerning a case, it is a 'holistic case study', and it is an 'embedded case study' when a researcher is researching a single case study such as a well-considered and logical sub-unit like a department of a larger organisation.

5. Ethnography is 'a research strategy that focuses on describing and interpreting the social world through first-hand field study' (Saunders & Lewis, 2012, p. 119). Similarly, 'ethnographers study people in groups, who interact with one another and share the same space, whether this is at street level, within a workgroup, in an organisation or within a society' (Saunders, et al., 2019, p. 200). Therefore, ethnography strategies are written account of people or ethnic groups, and the methods include realist ethnography, interpretive or impressionist ethnography and critical ethnography. However, they will not be discussed in detail here because of the scope of this study.

6. Action research is 'a research strategy concerned with managing a change and involving close collaboration between practitioners and researchers' (Saunders & Lewis, 2012, p. 117). Thus, the action research strategy is like the case study strategy. Both have a real-life event to be examined. The action researcher is an insider, part of the planning, experimenting, acting, and observing results, while the case study researcher is outside but might be a member of the 'case' (organisation) and playing a passive role. The uniqueness of action research compared to other research strategies is the action concerned.
7. Grounded theory is 'a research strategy in which theory is developed from data generated by series of observations or interviews principally involving an inductive approach' (Saunders & Lewis, 2012, p. 119). Unlike some other strategies, the grounded theory researcher starts collecting data without formulating the theory at the preliminary stage. Grounded theory involves more of an inductive approach than a deductive approach. Grounded theory involves a deductive approach when theory is being developed, and further observation is needed to retest the theory.

There are cautions about research strategy stance. First, labelling research strategies is valuable to differentiate them, but the label attached to a particular research strategy is relatively unimportant (Saunders & Lewis, 2012). Also, Saunders et al. (2019) emphasise that any research strategies could be used for any research purposes. Some strategies would clearly belong more closely to some research approaches than to others. At the same time, it is not helpful to attach one research strategy to one approach or another (ibid). Additionally, no research strategy is more important than others, and they are not mutually exclusive because a case study may include a survey or archival research (ibid). Additionally, the option of research strategy, that is, how a particular research project will be carried out in practice, is fundamentally connected to the nature of the research

question(s) asked (Adams, et al., 2007; Saunders, et al., 2019; Saunders & Lewis, 2012). Similarly, the research strategy is guided by the research hypotheses and objectives and coherently linked to the chosen philosophy, research approaches and purpose(s). It is also linked to a pragmatic stance that consists of existing knowledge, the amount of time, available resources, access to potential participants and other sources of data (Saunders, et al., 2016).

Therefore, this study is a case study combined with survey and archival and documentary strategy research. That is the combination of research strategies. First, it is a case study strategy research because the real-life chosen context is Nigeria, and both primary and secondary data sources are adopted. Second, it also relates to the purpose of this study identified above – explanatory and descriptive research and establishing the relationship between variables (tertiary education and entrepreneurship). It is best categorised as an emergent case study strategy because it involves the researcher choosing a case study environment (Nigeria) and allowing the focus of the research to emerge via engagement and literature review.

Second, it is a survey strategy research. Data about Nigerian entrepreneurs being will be collected for analysis and testing of the hypotheses. Third, it is archival and documentary strategy research. Finally, it is because of the secondary data collected and analysed as the principal data sources for this study, including a report from the GEDI. Other data sources are institutions such as universities, government, organisations, and media documents.

4.3.4 Times Horizons and Milestones

The two most common time dimensions are cross-sectional studies that are a study of a phenomenon at a time (snapshot) and longitudinal studies over the period (diaries)

(Saunders, et al., 2019). Therefore, this study is best fit under a cross-sectional study due to the researcher's degree-stipulated time and due to the research hypothesis, purpose of the research and the mixed methods research adopted.

4.3.5 Access Issues and Ethical Considerations

Research ethics are a critical part of research design formulation (Saunders, et al., 2019). Research ethics refers to 'the appropriateness of the researcher's behaviour in relation to the rights of those who become the subject of the research project, or who are affected by it' (Saunders & Lewis, 2012, p. 74). The standardised practice of business research ethics made available by UWS through the committee guidelines is strictly adhered to. The researcher obtained UWS ethical approval and further considered the ethics code of conduct outlined below.

1. **Non-Maleficence and Beneficence:** During the investigation data-gathering stage, the researcher ensures that every respondent is free to leave and protected from harm, either physically or emotionally. Then, the researcher's contact information is made available to them for any concerns or updates.
2. **Autonomy:** At all stages of gathering data for this study, participants' consent shall be sought, gained, and assured that their stance at any point in time would be respected. This includes if any participant would like to withdraw during the process. In addition, the study's procedures and purpose will be known to the respondents, while researcher contact information will be available if any respondent changes their mind.
3. **Justice and Inclusiveness:** Based on the guideline recommendation, here again, the researcher shall ensure equality of every participant in a selection process that will

include no preferential treatment because of religion, culture, age, disability, gender etc., while the final copy will be available for any interested participants.

4. **Confidentiality and Anonymity:** As been stipulated in guidelines, the researcher shall respect every participant's opinion and keep their information confidential in line with the Data Protection Act of every host country. Also, anonymity shall be ensured in the questionnaires' content where personal identities such as name, address, phone, etc., will not be requested. Then, gathered information shall be stored in a protected location, and after this study, it shall be deleted.

4.4 Research Methods

This is different from research methodology. The term 'methods' refers to techniques and procedures used to obtain and analyse data while methodology refers to the theory of how research should be undertaken' (Saunders, et al., 2019, p. 4). Closely, a research method is a way of conducting and implementing research, while research methodology is the science and philosophy behind all research (Adams, et al., 2007). Therefore, research methodology is wider in scope than research methods, and methods are a subset of methodology. More so, 'research methods are the practical techniques used to carry out research' (Walliman, 2011, p. 29). In other words, the tools a researcher adopt for data collection are called research methods (Dawson, 2002). So, a research method employed in a study is a strategy used to execute research design. In light of the understanding of research methods and research objectives, the followed topics are data collection sources and types, measurement and classification of data, data collection methods, sampling techniques, representative sampling plans, and sample size determination.

4.4.1 Sources of Data Collection

First, what is the meaning of data? It is the 'facts, opinions, and statistics that have been collected together and recorded for reference or analysis' (Saunders, et al., 2019, p. 801). Similarly, data is defined as 'the facts and figures collected for records or any statistical investigation' (Adams, et al., 2007, p. 85). The two sources of information generally used for research purposes are primary and secondary (Adams, et al., 2007; Saunders, et al., 2019). Primary data are the new data collected by the researcher for a definite investigation, while secondary data are from other sources that have initially been collected and used for a purpose (Saunders, et al., 2019). Similarly, 'primary sources are those in which researcher needs to conduct a new survey for gathering information at different levels with regard to the inquiry while secondary sources are those which are made available or have been collected for other research purposes' (Adams, et al., 2007, p. 85). So, data can be defined as either from primary or secondary sources; the former are usually and freshly collected for a particular study purpose, while the latter are from sources that have already been collected for a different purpose.

Thus, this study has been guided by the scholar's recommendation, which states that the nature of the research questions principally determines how the research itself will be implemented (Adams, et al., 2007; Saunders, et al., 2019). Therefore, based on the purpose of this study and the formulated hypotheses, data will be gathered from primary and secondary sources. Accordingly, data include secondary data collected from the Global Entrepreneurship Index (GEI) report and primary data collected from a survey conducted about the experiences and opinions of Nigerian tertiary education graduates and entrepreneurs.

4.4.2 Types of Data Collection

The discussion in Section 4.3.1 (Methodological Choice) identifies this study as mixed methods using a combination of qualitative data and quantitative data. Also, 'qualitative data are numerically non-measurable while quantitative data can be measured numerically' (Adams, et al., 2007, p. 85). Both qualitative and quantitative data will be collected from primary and secondary sources. For instance, qualitative data gathered from primary data sources include questionnaire number 9, which asked about the motive of the respondent for starting up a business, while qualitative data from secondary data sources include categorisation of Nigeria into states that are ascertained by the researcher based on the target audience (sample) detail on the internet. Likewise, quantitative data collected from primary data sources include questionnaire number 7, which asked about the number of employees, and secondary data sources, including data from GEDI, which gave a score for Nigerians' perception of business opportunity, start-up skill, etc.

4.4.3 Sampling Design

The focus of this section is to determine where to obtain appropriate data to answer the research question. Therefore, the consideration is whether the researcher will gather information from the whole population or a selected subgroup (sample) of the people. By definition, 'a sample design is a definite plan for obtaining a sample from a given population' (Kothari, 2004, p. 55). Additionally, 'sampling is the process or technique of selecting a suitable sample to determine parameters or characteristics of the whole population' (Adams, et al., 2007, p. 87). Therefore, one main reason stated by Saunders and Lewis (2012) for sampling is the enormous difficulty and practical impossibility of gathering data from the whole population in a study like this. The impossibility is due to

many reasons, including contact problems, timeframe, and financial constraints. Therefore, the next section discusses the study population, sampling unit, sampling frame, sample size, and presentation of sampling techniques.

4.4.3.1 Research Population

The research population is known as the 'universe', which refers to the full set of cases or elements from which a sample is taken (Saunders, et al., 2019). Equally, 'a population is a body of people or collection of items under consideration for statistical purposes' (Collis & Hussey, 2013, p. 197). Also, the population is regarded as 'an abstract idea of a large group of many cases from which a researcher draws a sample and to which results from a sample are generalized' (Neuman, 2014, p. 247). Therefore, the population could be seen as an identifiable total group or aggregation of pertinent and useful elements. Also, it could mean a total set of the subjects or group members of a research project where the researcher wants to make an inference. A population can either be known or unknown and finite or infinite (Kothari, 2004; Adams, et al., 2007). Examples of the research universe include people, the population of a city, an employee, an organisation, a place, stars in the sky, a music tracks list, radio programme listeners, and dice thrown (Saunders & Lewis, 2012; Kothari, 2004). Thus, the essence of defining the target population is that it helps the researcher focus on effective result delivery. The population for this study constitutes all Nigerian potential entrepreneurs and higher institution graduates or current entrepreneurs and higher institution graduates. In consideration of this study population element and timeframe for the researcher's programme, this study recognised that the whole population could not be fully surveyed. Therefore, the sampling unit is presented next.

4.4.3.2 Research Sampling Unit

Before sample selection, Kothari (2004) recommended that the sampling unit must be decided in any study. Similar to this term is 'unit of analysis,' defined by Collis and Hussey (2013, p. 101) as a 'phenomenon under study, about which data are collected and analysed, and is closely linked to the research problem and research question'. Sampling units were formerly referred to as 'elementary units or the group or cluster of such units that may form the basis of sampling process' (Kothari, 2004, p. 153). Therefore, it could be referred to as an element or set of elements considering to be selected from a sampling population. Then, the individual representative of a population or sample is acknowledged as the subject or element of the population or sample. Kothari (2004) explained it might be a division of geographical location, for example, a geopolitical zone, state government district, county, or community, or a construction structure, such as a house or flat, or a social unit such as a nuclear-family, extended family, sibling, club, school, or an individual. Therefore, with the understanding of this study's population elements, research question and objectives in mind, the sampling unit for this study comprises Nigerian graduate entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship professionals.

4.4.3.3 Research Sampling Frame

The sampling frame and population could be identical if studying a finite population and the time frame is present or past. In most studies, they are not the same because the possibility of a sample drawn directly from the population is not always guaranteed (Kothari, 2004). The sampling frame is also known as the source list (Kothari, 2004). It refers to an entire list of all the cases, elements, or items in the population from which a probability sample is drawn (Saunders, et al., 2019; Adams, et al., 2007; Kothari, 2004). Likewise, 'a sampling frame is a record of the population from which a sample can be drawn' (Collis & Hussey, 2013, p. 197). Similarly, a sampling frame is 'an empirically

concrete specific list that closely approximates all population elements' (Neuman, 2014, p. 252). Sampling frame decisions in a research study are extremely significant and must be as representative of the population as possible because an inappropriate selection will result in a systematic bias (Kothari, 2004). Therefore, the sample frame for this study was identified as the 145 approved private innovation enterprise institutions (IEIs) as of November 2019. The group was selected because most proprietors are graduates and entrepreneurs and would be able to provide information on their experiences as higher institution graduates and entrepreneurs in Nigeria. The characteristics of these proprietors are significant for this study's decisions, as highlighted above.

4.4.3.4 Research Sample Size Determination

This refers to the number of items to be selected from the study population to constitute a sample (Kothari, 2004). In other words, 'sample size is related to the size of the population under consideration' (Collis & Hussey, 2013, p. 51). Therefore, the research project sample size accounts for how well the result from the sample accurately represents the target population. More importantly, 'sample size plays a vital role in determining the precision of sample survey results' (Adams, et al., 2007). In other words, sample size ensures an optimum for a study to fulfil the requirements of efficiency, representativeness, reliability, and flexibility (Kothari, 2004).

Despite the crucial sample size role in a study like this, it is a difficult and ambiguous task for most researchers due to different opinions on what constitutes an appropriate sample size (Adams, et al., 2007; Neuman, 2014; Kothari, 2004; Saunders, et al., 2019). In the quest to find a solution to this problem, three main concerns have been identified. These concerns include a decision on how large the sample should be, the decision on how small the researcher could allow the sample to be, and the decision on how to judge whether

the sample size is suitable for a study goal. The typical response has been 'it depends', based on the following points.

- Characteristics of the population of a study, either homogenous or heterogenous
- Data analysis method type to be employed in a study
- Desired degree of confidence in sample precision needed for a study purpose
- View on parameters of interest in an investigation
- Time available for the study to be carried out
- Cost of the survey available for the study

Two approaches to determine and estimate sample size optimum are the practical approach and the statistical approach. The practical approach refers to a rule of thumb where the sample size is accepted based on conventional (Neuman, 2014). It implies that no precise fixed number of samples or specific percentage is ideal. Therefore, sample size is determined in relation to circumstances such as the amount of information required for a statistical estimation method or experiences with sample sizes that have met requirements for the statistical method (Neuman, 2014). Thus, it can be regarded as a qualitative method where the researcher combines subjective, intuitive experience and personal judgment. Also, sample size determination based on a rule of thumb or practical approach is difficult because statistical or quantitative inferences cannot be made about the population and parameters of the study.

A statistical approach is a method in which the investigator maximises some relationship between the sample of data and the population from which the sample was drawn (Kothari, 2004). Therefore, the statistical approach is very scientific because it is based on statistical principles. Therefore, a statistical approach was adopted for this study. The sample frame has been identified as the 145 IEs as of November 2019. Thus, the

estimated sample size is 95 respondents at a 90% confidence level and a 5% margin of error. However, the minimum actual sample size required for this study was calculated based on the formulas below.

$$\text{Formula} \quad n^a = \frac{n \times 100}{re\%} \quad \frac{30 \times 100}{95} = 32$$

n^a = actual sample size required

n = minimum (or adjusted minimum) sample size

$re\%$ = estimated response rate expressed as a percentage

Thus, the researcher considers the minimum appropriate sample size for this study to be 30. On the claim of scholars, Saunders said, 'Statisticians have also shown that a sample size of 30 or more will usually result in a sampling distribution for the mean that is very close to a normal distribution' (Saunders, et al., 2019, p. 300). In many surveys, researchers feel content if 20% of people respond to their survey (Adams, et al., 2007, p. 128). Also, Saunders et al. (2019) recommend that the researcher considers the response rates achieved for the similar surveys that have already been undertaken and base the estimate on that rate. Saunders et al. (2019) report a recent examination of business survey response rates on internet and postal questionnaires as low as 10%-20%. Therefore, the researcher forecast the minimum response rate for this study to be 20.50%. This is still in line with the advice that 30 respondents are an excellent sample size for statistical analyses as a valuable rule of thumb (Stutely, 2003).

Hence, after choosing a suitable sampling frame and the actual sample size required for a specific study, the researcher must select an appropriate sampling technique(s) to obtain a representative sample (Saunders, et al., 2019). Sampling techniques are presented in the next section.

4.4.3.5 The Study Sample

The sample refers to the selected elements or observations from the targeted population under an investigation. Therefore, what is the process of gaining a sample in a research study? This is called sampling. The two major sampling techniques are probability and non-probability (Adams, et al., 2007; Neuman, 2014; Kothari, 2004; Saunders, et al., 2019). Sampling techniques are the methods a researcher adopts in selecting the study elements for inclusion in the sample. The process of ‘taking a subset from chosen sampling frame or entire population is called sampling’ (Taherdoost, 2016, p. 19). The purpose of sampling is to ‘make inference about a population or to make generalization in relation to existing theory but depends on the choice of sampling technique’ (Taherdoost, 2016, p. 19). It is important because ‘a good sample selection is key as it allows one to generalise the findings from the sample to the population, which is the whole purpose of survey research (Kabir, 2016, p. 244). The merit of sampling can be extended to describe acquiring data about a study target population and rather than scrutinising the entire population or sampling frame. Also, it is a means to control cost and quickly gather data from a respondent within a study population. The sampling techniques and their categories are summarised in the table below and then discussed in the next sub-section. This is in accordance with Taherdoost’s (2016) recommendation that, before selecting a specific sampling method, it is necessary to decide on broad sampling techniques.

Table 1: Probability and Non-probability Sampling Techniques

Probability	Non-probability
Simple random sampling	Quota sampling
Systematic random sampling	Purposive sampling
Stratified random sampling	Snowball sampling

Probability	Non-probability
Multistage sampling	Self-selection sampling
Cluster sampling	Convenience sampling

Source 3: Adams et al., 2007; Neuman, 2014; Kothari, 2004 and Saunders et al., 2019

4.4.3.5.1 Probability Sampling Techniques

Probability sampling is also known as representative sampling. These sampling techniques are adopted when the researcher can obtain a complete population list. It is typically associated with survey and experimental research strategies where a researcher needs to make statistical inferences from a sample about a population to answer the research question and meet the research objective (Saunders, et al., 2019). Therefore, a probability sample is a sample in which each case or every element of the target population has an equal chance of being included (Adams, et al., 2007; Saunders, et al., 2019; Taherdoost, 2016). Similarly, 'it is defined a variety of sampling techniques for selecting a sample at random from a complete list of the population' (Saunders & Lewis, 2012, p. 133). The choice of probability sampling technique(s) to be adopted is influenced by research questions and objectives, if there is a need to meet respondents face-to-face, the nature of respondents' geographic location, sampling frame structure, and needed sample size (Saunders, et al., 2019).

Table 2: Probability Sampling Techniques Classifications and their Merits and Demerits

Types of Probability Sample	Descriptions	Merits	Demerits
Simple random sampling (SRS)	A sampling process when each element of the population has an equal chance to be selected	It ensures adequate population-representative and implementation	It is time-draining, expensive to undertake, and a population

Types of Probability Sample	Descriptions	Merits	Demerits
	randomly. Therefore, the population must be well defined, listed, and a sampling frame must exist.	simplicity. It has the greatest freedom from bias.	element exhaustive list not always possible. It is most helpful for a small population.
Systematic random sampling	A sampling process like SRS when the population is homogenous but has no equal chance of every case being selected; it is selected on a uniform order interval.	The entire reference population can be evenly selected, and the process is not so complex.	In the case of a heterogeneous population, sampling is very difficult, and an element of bias might be evidence.
Stratified random sampling	A sampling process when a heterogeneous population is reclassified into homogeneous relevant to research questions based on economic or social groups according to desired characteristics of the variables such as sex, location, nationality, socioeconomic group, qualifications, religious affiliation, etc. It is called strata or subgroups or layers where samples are now selected randomly.	It bridges the gap between systematic random and simple random sampling by producing a sample representative that captures the diversity of the targeted population.	It is tedious and time-consuming as time and skills are required to be stratified separately. Therefore, it requires a lot of time and effort.

Types of Probability Sample	Descriptions	Merits	Demerits
Multistage sampling	Sampling within the sample. It combines two or more probability sampling techniques, mostly adopted when the units of the population are over multiple locations and obtaining a representative sample is very difficult with any of the discussed techniques. The final sample collected after several stages is used for investigation.	It is time- and money-effective and is one of the significant ways of solving the heterogeneity population problem within clusters.	It is problematic when the selected cluster does not capture all the features of the population.
Cluster sampling	Also known as one-stage cluster sampling, mostly used in epidemiological research. It is like a stratified sampling method. The difference is that populations are divided into homogeneous groups but not individual entities. It is called a cluster where the final sample is taken randomly and studied.	It is good for large populations split over geographical areas because it saves time and money.	A systematic error could occur, and biases may surface in the process.

Source 4: Adams, et al., 2007; Neuman, 2014; Kothari, 2004 and Saunders, et al., 2019

Therefore, Saunders, et al. (2019) said probability sampling techniques are all based on a random selection of a sample from sampling frame and possibility any specific case be

included in the sample, but in business and management research, it might either be impossible due to unavailable sampling frame or not appropriate to answer the research question. Therefore, as the sample must be selected in another way, the next section is presented.

4.4.3.5.2 Non-Probability Sampling Techniques

Non-probability sampling techniques are usually connected with case study research design and qualitative research (Taherdoost, 2016). These sampling techniques are adopted when a researcher does not know or have a complete list of the population. According to Saunders et al. (2019), it is a non-probability sample where each element from the target population being selected is unknown, and it does not make it possible to answer research questions or address research objectives that require the researcher to make statistical inferences about the characteristics of the population. The authors caution that generalisation of research findings in a particular targeted population like this is possible, but not on statistical grounds. Therefore, it is defined as a variety of sampling techniques for selecting a sample when the researcher does not have a complete list of the population (Adams, et al., 2007). Notably, a 'sample of participants or cases does not need to be representative, or random, but a clear rationale is needed for the inclusion of some cases or individuals rather than others' (Taherdoost, 2016, p. 22). Furthermore, non-probability samples are more prevalent now due to the rapid growth of online questionnaire administration (Saunders, et al., 2019).

- Quota sampling involves the researcher segmenting the population into a mutually exclusive small group such as stratified sampling. Then, the researcher selects items from each segment based on the specified proportion. It differs from stratified sampling, which involves non-random sampling, while quota sampling involves the

researcher's personal judgment and convenience. More importantly, the 'logic behind quota sampling is that certain relevant characteristics describe the dimensions of the population' (Adams, et al., 2007, p. 90). Therefore, quota sampling is essential because it ensures that a predetermined population subgroup represents the researcher's sample list while not possessing random samples. According to Saunders and Lewis (2012), a non-probability sampling method ensures the samples included in a study represents specific characteristics of the researcher's chosen population. Similarly, quota sampling is 'a non-random sample in which the researcher first identifies general categories into which cases or people will be placed and then selects cases to reach a predetermined number in each category' (Neuman, 2014, p. 249). Therefore, the merit of quota sampling is a semblance of representativeness of the target population even though it is a non-probability sampling technique; meanwhile, the study's success depends on the researcher's subjective decisions about the samples to be adopted. Therefore, quota sampling might not be reliable because it is subjective, and an element of bias might surface.

- **Purposive/Judgmental Sampling:** The researcher purposely identifies samples with a prior definite criterion in mind. A study with this sampling technique does not select every participant at disposal but those whom the researcher believes possessed defined criteria. It is defined as 'a non-random sample in which the researcher uses a wide range of methods to locate all possible cases of a highly specific and difficult-to-reach population' (Neuman, 2014, p. 249). In the same vein, purposive sampling is a non-probability sampling where the researcher's judgement is used to select the sample members based on a range of possible reasons and promises (Saunders & Lewis, 2012). The merit of this sampling technique is that decision making is easier

and faster. However, it might not be reliable because of the subjective nature of the researcher.

- **Snowball/Referral Sampling:** involves the researcher contacting prospective respondents initially, and thereafter they help identify more respondents in an investigation. It is defined as 'a non-probability sampling in which, after the first sample member, subsequent members are identified by earlier sample members' (Saunders & Lewis, 2012, p. 138). Therefore, adopting snowball sampling has the advantage of reaching difficult sample representatives who may be unique, small and in a defined target population. It is very cheap to use as it involves small sample sizes. Meanwhile, it could be very biased, making it difficult to generalise study findings to a larger target population.
- **Self-selection Sampling** involves the researcher systematically requesting or arranging prospective sample members to identify themselves in a research investigation. It is defined as 'a non-probability sampling method in which possible sample members are asked to identify themselves as willing to participate in the research' (Saunders & Lewis, 2012, p. 140). The main problem with self-selection sampling is that results cannot be generalised, resulting in a systematic error, and respondents might include untargeted populations. It is useful when the researcher does not have much money, it is less time consuming, and large data can be gathered.
- **Convenience or Accidental Sampling:** In this non-probability sampling technique, researchers tend to draw samples at will; samples are included in a study on the basis of researcher convenience, and samples are only selected either by chance or by accident. Saunders et al. (2019) said a non-probability sampling involves selecting elements or cases haphazardly only because they are readily available (or most convenient) to obtain for the researcher sample. Similarly, the non-probability

sampling technique purposively or deliberately selected specific population items to constitute a sample that characterised the population (Kothari, 2004). The common problem identified with this method is the probability of a high level of biases, misleading information and unverifiable results, and in the end, the findings will be difficult to generalise. However, convenience sampling is very inexpensive, and it allows access to large numbers of respondents quickly. Also, it is used in pilot studies, and it is a straightforward technique.

4.4.3.5.3 Sampling Techniques Adopted for this Study

Both stratified random probability and purposive non-probability sampling techniques were adopted in this study due to sampling design procedures stipulated for this study and study objectives. The first stage of this study that involves purposive sampling was the selection of sampling units that are predetermined by population parameters; the sample estimate includes Nigerian graduate entrepreneurs. The second stage involves a stratified sampling technique adopted when the research population (sampling frame) is classified as Nigerian proprietors of the IEs. These techniques allow the researcher to identify specific characteristics of the element of the study population that will enable answering the research question. It increased the identification of the sub-groups contained by the study populace and the established sample that satisfactorily characterised these sub-clusters. Also, it helps the researcher to only select a sample that is believed to possess the defined criteria for this study. Other reasons include lack of access to all members of the sampling frame based on the researcher's programme timeframe and the major expenses of contacting all members of the sampling frame.

4.4.4 Data Collection Methods

Data collection methods are how information is obtained from the research participants. According to Kabir (2016, p. 202), 'data collection is the process of gathering and measuring information on variables of interest, in an established systematic fashion that enables one to answer stated research questions, test hypotheses, and evaluate outcomes'. It aims to obtain quality evidence that will then turn to rich information, analysis, and creating a compelling and reliable answer to research questions (Kabir, 2016).

The data collection usually begins once the sampling plan is formalised in the research design (Adams, et al., 2007; Kothari, 2004). Kothari (2004) advises that primary and secondary data should be kept in mind when the researcher decides the method of data collection for the study. Also, (Neuman, 2014, p. 46) said data collection techniques can be categorised into two based on the quantitative and qualitative data. With this understanding and as stated earlier under Section 4.4.1 above, primary and secondary sources of data were adopted. Therefore, the focus here will be on gathering information from primary and secondary sources as both can be quantitative or qualitative data. This section will further be building on the categorisation of this study as mixed methods research. Therefore, the selection of the methods is strongly guided by the combined research strategies adopted, which are case study strategy research, survey strategy research and archival/documentary strategy research.

4.4.4.1 Secondary Data Collection Methods

The imperative of secondary data in a research study like this has been emphasised. It is much more available than ever before on the internet, cost-effective, easily accessible, and free of time constraints. Adams et al.'s appeal to the researcher was more specific in

this regard that before accessing primary data, 'please think whether secondary data- either statistical compilations or existing surveys-could answer your research questions' (Adams, et al., 2007, p. 129). With this understanding, the researcher first explores secondary data sources, including books, government records, journals articles, and published electronic sources.

4.4.4.2 Primary Data Collection Methods

The researcher collects primary data using qualitative and quantitative methods. The main methods of collecting primary data include questionnaires, interviews, focus group interviews, observations, surveys, case studies, diaries, activity sampling techniques, process analyses, link analyses, time and motion studies, experimental methods, and statistical methods (Kabir, 2016). In respect of research strategies adopted for this study, surveys and case studies will be used to gather primary data.

4.4.4.2.1 Survey Method

In this section, the term 'survey' is used to define any research method that seeks to gather information from a group of respondents (Adams, et al., 2007). Additionally, survey research is often used to assess thoughts, opinions, and feelings (Kabir, 2016). In more detail, the 'survey method involves asking individuals questions face to face, by telephone or via questionnaires of individuals, and departments or companies to find out personal, company or sector information' (Adams, et al., 2007, p. 128). A survey consists of a predetermined set of questions given to a sample (Kabir, 2016). The principle of a survey is to collate answers to several questions, which lends itself to a more quantitative approach in terms of data analysis (Adams, et al., 2007). Surveys provide a means of measuring a population's characteristics, self-reported and observed behaviour, awareness of programs, attitudes or opinions, and needs (Kabir, 2016). Surveys are a

good way of gathering a large amount of data, providing a broad perspective (Kabir, 2016). However, the approach is over-used, and people and organisations are tired of surveys, and as a result, response rates are poor (Adams, et al., 2007).

The survey data collection form includes questionnaires, structured observation, and structured interviews (Saunders & Lewis, 2012). Questionnaire data collection was adopted for this study. It is detailed in the following section.

4.4.4.2.2 Questionnaire

A questionnaire refers to 'all methods of data collection in which each potential respondent is asked to answer the same set of questions in the same order' (Saunders & Lewis, 2012, p. 141). It consists of several questions printed or typed in a definite order on a form or set of forms (Kothari, 2004). The questionnaire is not particularly good for exploratory or other research that requires many open-ended questions; it tends to be for descriptive or explanatory research (Saunders, et al., 2019). For instance, this study described as explanatory research will enable the researcher to examine and explain relationships between variables (tertiary institution graduates and entrepreneurs in Nigeria), particularly cause-and-effect relationships.

Also, collecting data via a questionnaire method is suitable for this study, as Kothari (2004) stated, for the following reasons. It helps the researcher gather information at a low cost despite the researcher having distant and large participants spread all over Nigeria. Second, it helps research responses be free from the interviewer's bias as answers are in respondents' own words. Also, the research participants will have adequate time to give well thought out answers that will guarantee quality findings. In relation to Nigeria, the hierarchical cultural system is an avenue to conveniently reach some research participants who are not easily approachable. It is advantageous because

most of the prospective participants are educated. However, there are some barriers to using questionnaires to gather data for this study, as Kothari stated (2004). Those barriers include a low rate of return, and bias due to no-response is often indeterminate. It could lead to the researcher losing control over the questionnaire once it is sent. Also, it is not easy to know whether willing respondents are truly representative.

4.4.5 Research Instruments Measurement

The two fundamental features in evaluating research instruments measurement are reliability and validity (Mohajan, 2017; Dawson, 2002). The accuracy and consistency of research instruments are other important factors (Hamed, 2016). 'Validity concerns what an instrument measures, and how well it does so, while reliability concerns the faith that one can have in the data obtained from the use of an instrument' (Mohajan, 2017, p. 58). With this understanding, the research presents the secondary and primary data instrument measurements.

Secondary Data

The researcher establishes the suitability of the main secondary data gathered for this study and then presents it in the next chapter. There is no need to design a data collection method for secondary data.

The Global Entrepreneurship Index (GEI) report is the main source of secondary data gathered for analysis in this study. Therefore, the following themes present their relevancy and suitability for this study. The themes are formed from Saunders and Lewis (2012), who say that secondary data depends on the study, the purpose of the original data collected, and the method adopted.

- **Relevancy of GEDI Data Gathered for the Study**

To determine the relevance of the secondary data, Saunders and Lewis (2012) advised that the information must answer the research question. It means the required data must be matched with the readymade data and variables definition used. The GEDI annual report used almost the same data and variable definitions as are required for this study. For instance, the GEDI has been gathering and providing entrepreneurship and business statistics on the country's entrepreneurial ecosystem through the Global Entrepreneurship Index (GEI). The entrepreneurship ecosystem comprises attitudes, resources, and infrastructure. These are the variables needed to provide an answer to this research question.

- **Original Purposes of GEDI Research**

Saunders and Lewis (2012) emphasised that after finding that the readymade data are relevant to the subject of study, the researcher needs to understand why those data are being collected by looking into the secondary data's objectives or research questions. The GEDI advances knowledge on links between entrepreneurship, economic development, and prosperity (Acs, et al., 2019). This institute aims to provide a solid theory-based entrepreneurship measure that explains the role of entrepreneurship on economic development (Acs, et al., 2019). The objective of the GEDI is correlated with the subject of this study, mainly on the part of entrepreneurship. When it was explored in detail, the higher educational aspect of this study made it an appropriate report to use as a data source.

- **Assessment of the Method GEDI Used to Gather Data**

The GEDI methodology collects data on the entrepreneurial attitudes, abilities and aspirations, generally referred to as 3As, of the local population and then weighs these against the prevailing social and economic infrastructure. These three sub-indexes stand

on 14 pillars - quasi-independent building blocks, each containing an individual and an institutional variable that correspond to the micro-and the macro-level aspects of entrepreneurship. These are opportunity perception, start-up skills, risk acceptance, networking, cultural support, opportunity start-up, technology absorption, human capital, competition, product innovation, process innovation, high growth, internationalization, and risk capital. Understanding the technique GEDI uses to collect data should be very helpful in ascertaining the objectives of this study. The GEDI GEI measures the quality and dynamics of entrepreneurship interconnectedness at a national, regional and local level (Acs, et al., 2019).

Primary Data

The research instrument adopted for primary data for this study is a questionnaire. Methods of evaluating and ensuring the validity and reliability stages of a questionnaire are adopted, according to Kabir (2016).

The Survey Process – Questionnaire

This section outlines the processes the researcher followed in gathering data for this study via the questionnaire method. The four stages advised in Kabir's (2016) work were adopted: planning and designing, testing and modifying, conducting the survey, and processing and analysing. These are detailed as used in this study as follows.

Stage 1: Planning and Designing

The literature was reviewed and showed that correlations between tertiary institutions and entrepreneurship exist in some countries experiences and practices, but that is not the case in Nigeria. Therefore, secondary sources have limited information that appears to be insufficient to deliver this research objective. In this light, this questionnaire aims

to gather more information to explore the experiences and opinions of the sampling units of the study population.

This information collection uses the questionnaire data collection method. A self-completion questionnaire conducted by email was considered appropriate because of Covid-19 pandemic restrictions, time frame, response/consent rate, and the distance and cost involved in other methods. The other survey techniques considered for gathering data include telephone, face-to-face, or online interviews or combinations of these (Kabir, 2016). The administration of the questionnaires is via email. The Survey Monkey online survey software service company was considered, but researchers understood the potentially high number of non-responses that might occur, and plans for follow-up calls and reminder messages were implemented.

Then, a list of questions based on the set of hypotheses was developed with instructions and an introductory letter drafted and submitted to the lead supervisor. Some corrections were called for and were addressed accordingly. Sample lists of 10 prospective participants from the sampling frame were also discussed with the lead supervisor. A Plan B was created in the event that more clarification was needed or an untimely response was received. A second supervisor and adviser were also contacted for feedback.

Stage 2: Testing and Modifying

Scholars such as Adams, et al. (2007); Kabir (2016); and Saunders, et al. (2019) recommend piloting a questionnaire to ensure the instrument is measuring what is intended and is appropriate for the target sampling frame. Therefore, the drafted introductory letter and questionnaire proforma were sent to the planned participants through the online Survey Monkey software services. Unfortunately, the response from

these participants did not arrive as expected. A follow-up call was made, which yielded some results.

Feedback was received for some piloted questionnaires, and areas to be improved were highlighted for clarification, such as the layout of the questions, wording, and respondent reactions. Modifications were made, and questionnaires were ready for complete data collection.

Stage 3: Conducting the Survey

The Survey Monkey software application subscription package was upgraded to accommodate more participants and make more features accessible to help analyse the responses. In addition, with the hope of receiving more than a minimum of 30 responses, 107 prospect participants of the 145-person sampling frame were contacted.

Stage 4: Processing and Analysing: This stage is addressed in the next chapter.

4.5 Summary of Research Approach and Methodology

Table 2 below presented the summary of this research approach and methodology.

Table 3: Summary of Research Approach and Methodology

Approaches/Methodology	Adopted
Research philosophies	Epistemological assumption and pragmatists stance
Research approaches	Deductive
Methodological choice	Mixed methods – quantitative and qualitative
Purpose of the study	Combined purposes – descriptive, explanatory, and evaluative
Research strategies	Combinations of research strategies – case study, survey strategy, and archival and documentary
Times horizons and milestones	Cross-sectional study

Sources of data collection	Primary and secondary sources
Types of data collection	qualitative data and quantitative data
Probability sampling techniques	Stratified sampling technique
Non –probability sampling techniques	Purposive sampling technique
Survey method	Questionnaire

Source 5: Synthesised from the Literature

CHAPTER FIVE: DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

This chapter aims to aggregate all data gathered for this study and isolate the unrelated information. The data were gathered from primary and secondary sources.

5.1 Secondary Data Collected

There are two categories of secondary data gathered for this study. The first part is from the GEDI GEI, and the second part is the results of a survey of the owners of IEs in Nigeria.

5.1.1 Global Entrepreneurship Index (GEI)

The GEDI GEI data presented here are of five countries selected for comparison (United States, United Kingdom, South Africa, Botswana, and Nigeria). The data are collected on the local population of each country based on entrepreneurial building blocks called the attitudes sub-index, the abilities sub-index, and the aspirations sub-index weighed against prevailing social and economic infrastructure. These three sub-indexes stand on 14 pillars, each containing an individual and an institutional variable that correspond to the micro and the macro-level aspects of entrepreneurship. The five countries selected are then ranked in terms of performance against the others. The essence is to provide a broad picture of how Nigeria performs against other countries in both the domestic and international context. The data cover the same five-year period for each country. The following data are the relevant pillars to this study.

Figure 3 below shows that the opportunity perception of entrepreneurship in Nigeria compared to two peers in Sub-Saharan Africa, the United States and the United Kingdom, was very low and fluctuating. In 2017 and 2018, Nigeria was 37%, while the lowest scores in South Africa and Botswana were in 2018 at 40% and 2016 at 45%, respectively.

Figure 3: Opportunity Perception

Source 6: Acs et al., 2015; Acs et al., 2016; Acs et al., 2017; Acs et al., 2018; and Acs et al., 2019

The start-up skills of the entrepreneurial ecosystem of the countries presented in Figure 4 below indicate that the United States and the United Kingdom showed higher than 50% start-up-skill scores between 2015 and 2019, while none of the Sub-Saharan African countries presented had scores as high as 40%.

Figure 4: Start-Up Skills

Source 7: Acs et al., 2015; Acs et al., 2016; Acs et al., 2017; Acs et al., 2018; and Acs et al., 2019

Figure 5 presents the risk acceptance pillar scores. For the five-year period of 2015 to 2019, Nigeria's highest score is 21% in 2018 following by 20% in 2017, 10% in 2019, 8% in 2015 and the lowest in 2016 with 8%. South Africa fluctuates between a minimum of 24% in 2019 and a maximum of 46% in 2015 and 2016. Like the United States and the United Kingdom, Botswana has higher than 50% risk acceptance scores through all five years.

Figure 5: Risk Acceptance

Source 8: Acs et al., 2015; Acs et al., 2016; Acs et al., 2017; Acs et al., 2018; and Acs et al., 2019

In Figure 6 below, the cultural support pillar of entrepreneurship in the United States and the United Kingdom indicated a minimum of 82% in 2018 and 79% in 2015, respectively. In the same vein, only Botswana has no score below 50%. The South African score was fair and ranged from 38%, 42% and 43%. Nigeria's cultural support of entrepreneurship is very low compared to other countries, with a high score of 22% in 2015 and 2016, and the scores in 2017, 2018 and 2019 are 17%, 19% and 17%, respectively.

Figure 6: Cultural Support

Source 9: Acs et al., 2015; Acs et al., 2016; Acs et al., 2017; Acs et al., 2018; and Acs et al., 2019

In Figure 7 below, the opportunity start-up pillar presented for the five years indicated the United States and the United Kingdom had minimum scores of 73% in 2015 and 77% in 2016, respectively. The Sub-Saharan African countries presented are all below 50%, while Nigeria is extremely low. The maximum Nigerian score was 22% in 2015, and it decreases to 21% in 2016, 8% in 2017, 7% in 2018 and then increased slightly to 12% in 2019.

Figure 7: Opportunity Start-up

Source 10: Acs et al., 2015; Acs et al., 2016; Acs et al., 2017; Acs et al., 2018; and Acs et al., 2019

In Figure 8 below, the United States and the United Kingdom continue to show the greatest strength in human capital, with scores above the average in all years. This is otherwise in Sub Saharan Africa, where there are no countries above a 50% score. The highest and lowest scores for South Africa, Botswana and Nigeria, respectively, are 28% and 20%; 45% and 34%; and 46% and 38%.

Figure 8: Human Capital

Source 11: Acs et al., 2015; Acs et al., 2016; Acs et al., 2017; Acs et al., 2018; and Acs et al., 2019

5.1.1.1 The Global Entrepreneurship Index Ranking of the Five Selected Countries

Table 3 presents the GEI ranking of the five selected countries. It shows that Nigeria dropped in ranking every year from 2015 to 2018; she ranked 84, 85, 100 and 101 until 2019, when she had a fair ranking of 92. In relation to other countries in Africa and the United States and the United Kingdom, South Africa maintained a 52-58 ranking for the five years presented, Botswana had 51 and 66 rankings, the United Kingdom was between 4 and 9 and the United States ranked first for all five years.

Table 4: The Global Entrepreneurship Index rank of the five selected countries

Countries	2015 @ 130 countries		2016 @ 132 countries		2017 @ 137 countries		2018 @ 137 countries		2019 @ 137 countries	
	Global Ranking	Score								
United States	1	85.0	1	86.2	1	83.4	1	83.6	1	86.8
United Kingdom	4	72.7	9	67.7	8	71.3	4	77.8	5	77.5
South Africa	52	40.0	52	38.5	55	32.6	57	32.9	58	31.6
Botswana	66	33.0	66	33.1	52	34.4	52	34.9	51	34.4
Nigeria	84	28.9	85	28.1	100	19.9	101	19.7	92	20.8

Source 12: Acs et al, 2015; Acs et al, 2016; Acs et al, 2017; Acs et al, 2018; and Acs et al, 2019

5.1.2 Summary of Higher Institutions in Nigeria

The table below presents accredited tertiary institutions in Nigeria and ownership as of April 2019. This table shows that universities have highest number of established and accredited institutions in Nigeria following by IELs, polytechnics, technical colleges, VEIs, colleges of health science and technology, and colleges of agriculture, and specialised institutions have the lowest number.

Table 5: Summary of Tertiary Education Institutions in Nigeria

Types of Institution	Federal Government	State Government Owned	Privately Owned	Total
Universities	45	52	99	169
Polytechnics	37	48	68	153
Specialised	24	3	9	69
Colleges of Agriculture	19	14	0	33
Colleges of Health Science	25	18	10	53

Types of Institution	Federal Government	State Government Owned	Privately Owned	Total
VEIs	7	4	66	77
IEIs	6	5	147	158
Technical Colleges	123		0	123
Total				862

Source 13: Adapted from National Board for Technical Education: TVET Institutions and Nigerian Universities (NBTE, 2019; NUC, 2021)

5.1 Primary Data Collected

The empirical data obtained for this thesis were collected via a web-based survey format. The survey involves direct contact with research participants who were identified from the sampling frame through a group email. The survey had 24 multiple-choice questions. The questionnaire statements were all presented randomly and did not openly provide construct variables, and question names did not indicate the related hypothesis. The participants of this survey are the private owners of IEIs in Nigeria.

5.1.1 Statistical Presentation and Analysis of the Survey Responses

Figure 9 below shows that 100% of the respondents identified themselves as an entrepreneur.

Figure 9: Entrepreneurs Identification

Source 14: Survey by the author

Figure 10 below shows that 57% replied they became entrepreneurs because of their tertiary education while 43% did not credit their education.

Figure 10: Finding if becoming an entrepreneur is a result of tertiary education

Source 15: Survey by the author

Figure 11 below shows that 95% say they are providing vocational and innovation training while only 5% do not.

Figure 11: Does research participant provide vocational/innovation training

Source 16: Survey by the author

In Figure 12 below, 98% say that the programme they are running is a platform that enables students to become entrepreneurs, and only 2% said no.

Figure 12: Finding if the programme provided by the respondent's institution is platform for students to become entrepreneurs

Source 17: Survey by the author

Figure 13 shows that 39% usually see graduates establish their business venture due to their acquired skill; 32% say sometimes, 25% say always, and 5% say rarely.

Figure 13: How often do graduates establish their own business venture as a result of acquired skills

Source 18: Survey by the author

Figure 14 shows answers about how many employees work for the respondent; 16% have fewer than 10 staff, 58% have 10-49 staff, 12% have 50-99 staff, and 14% have more than 100 staff.

Figure 14: Finding on the number of respondents' employees

Source 19: Survey by the author

Figure 15 below shows that 42% sometimes have tertiary institution graduate positions vacant in their organisation, followed by 21% who say usually, 21% say rarely, and 16% indicated always. No one said never.

Figure 15: Finding on how often respondents have positions available for graduates of tertiary institution

Source 20: Survey by the author

Figure 16 shows that 61% of the respondents say it is extremely important to create a business venture in Nigeria, 34% said it is very important, and 5% said it is somewhat important. No one said it is not so important or it is not at all important.

Figure 16: Finding on how important do respondents see an act of creating business venture in Nigeria

Source 21: Survey by the author

In Figure 17, 23% are of the opinion that Nigerian regulatory bodies are not at all helpful, 39% believe they are not so helpful, 30% said they are somewhat helpful, 7% said they are helpful, and 2% are of the opinion that they are extremely helpful.

Figure 17: Finding on to what extent respondents think Nigerian regulatory bodies support business start-ups

Source 22: Survey by the author

In Figure 18 below, 75% of the respondents say their course of study helped them start a business, while 25% said no.

Figure 18: Finding on whether the course of study helped start a business

Source 23: Survey by the author

Figure 19 below shows that 7% of respondents always see Nigerian tertiary institution graduates as their major competitor in their sector, followed by 17% usually, 14% sometimes, 40% rarely and 21% never.

Figure 19: Finding about whether the respondents see Nigerian tertiary institution graduates as major competitor in their sector

Source 24: Survey by the author

In Figure 20 below, respondents indicate how frequently they receive job applications from recent graduates: 57% said always, 25% said usually, 9% said sometimes, 9% said rarely. No one said never.

Figure 20: Finding on how frequently respondents receive job applications from recent graduates

Source 25: Survey by the author

Respondents were asked if Nigeria is an entrepreneurial nation as a result of tertiary institution graduates creating a business venture. Figure 21 shows the responses as follows: 16% strongly agree, 16% agree, 23% neither agree nor disagree, 30% disagree, and 16% strongly disagree.

Figure 21: Is Nigeria is an entrepreneurial nation as a result of tertiary institution graduates creating a business venture

Source 26: Survey by the author

Figure 22 below shows that 12% of the participants think that tertiary education made an exceptional contribution to their business start-up, 17% said it was excellent, 17% said very good, 27% said good, 17% said their education made a fair contribution, 0% said poor, and 10% said their education made a very poor contribution to their business start-up.

Figure 22: Finding about how respondents rate the contribution made by their tertiary education to their business start-up

Source 27: Survey by the author

Figure 23 below shows that 21% have a high opinion that Nigerian technical institution graduates can become entrepreneurs, followed by 33% good, 28% acceptable, 12% poor, and 7% very poor.

Figure 23: Finding on how respondents rate the quality of becoming an entrepreneur through Nigerian technical Institutions

Source 28: Survey by the author

Figure 24 below present the respondents' view on whether students are more likely to become an entrepreneur in Nigeria if they graduate from university: 7% strongly agree, 9% agree, 25% neither agree nor disagree, 34% disagree, 23% strongly disagree and 2% low quality.

Figure 24: Finding if respondents believe people are more likely to become an entrepreneur in Nigeria if they graduate from university

Source 29: Survey by the author

Figure 25 shows the respondents main motive for starting up a business: 14% base their passion on carrying out a childhood dream, 28% want to generate income through business, 9% claim family orientation, 44% feel a responsibility to the society, 9% seek autonomy, 12% have no job, 19% say opportunity, and 28% claim educational exposure.

Figure 25: Finding on respondents' main motive for starting a business

Source 30: Survey by the author

Participants were allowed to select more than one answer, so the percentages sum to more than 100%.

Figure 26 shows the respondents view on what capacity they think Nigeria needs a graduate of vocational/innovation training institutions; 82% definitely would, 11% probably would, 5% would not and 2% definitely would not.

Figure 26: Finding on what capacity respondents think Nigeria needs a graduate of vocational/innovation training institutions

Source 31: Survey by the author

Figure 27 below shows that 16% agree that their course of study in Nigeria is extremely helpful to succeed in business, 32% agree it is very helpful, 27% agree somewhat helpful, 18% state it was not so helpful, and 7% declared it was not at all helpful.

Figure 27: Finding on whether respondents think their course of study in Nigeria helps them to succeed in business

Source 32: Survey by the author

Figure 28 below shows that 45% strongly agree that being educated helps nurture long-term business relationships, 32% agree, 9% somewhat agree, 7% neither agree nor disagree, 2% somewhat disagree, 0% disagree, and 5% strongly disagree.

Figure 28: Finding if respondents agree that being educated helps nurture long-term business relationships

Source 33: Survey by the author

Figure 29 shows that most respondents are men (78%), women make up 22% of the group.

Figure 29: Respondents' gender

Source 34: Survey by the author

Figure 30 shows the respondents' age group as follows: 22% are 25-34, 32% are 35-44, 20% are 45-54, 20% are 55-64 and 7% are older than 65.

Figure 30: Age group of respondents

Source 35: Survey by the author

CHAPTER SIX: RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the results and discussion of the data analysed in Chapter Five. It aimed to test the hypotheses, answer the research questions raised based on the research objectives, review the main study findings and examine their implications.

6.1 General Characteristics of the Data

The first considered data that was later built upon via the survey are from GEDI. This data set encompasses 14 pillar values for five years of the five selected countries. It is an annual data survey on the entrepreneurship ecosystem from most countries of the world. The research participants of the survey questionnaire are 44 owners of private IEs in Nigeria, which comprise 22% women and 78 men (see Figure 29). The age group of these IEs proprietors is 7% 65 years and older, 20% are between 55 to 64, 20% are between 45 to 54, 32% are between 35 to 44, and 22% are between 25 to 34 (see Figure 30). The next step is allocating and interpreting the related data to each hypothesis, followed by their implications.

6.1.1 Hypothesis One

In an attempt to test the H_1 that states 'there seems to be no positive relationship between the level of entrepreneurs and outturns of tertiary institution graduates in Nigeria', the statistical analyses presented in Chapter Five that are relevant for this hypothesis are Figure 4, Figure 5, Figure 7, Figure 10, Figure 13, Figure 18, Figure 23 and Figure 24. The details follow.

Figure 10 shows that 57% replied they became entrepreneurs because of their tertiary education, while 43% did not credit their education. Figure 13 shows 96% of research participants (always, usually, and sometimes) see their graduates establishing their own business ventures due to their acquired skills, while 5% stated rarely. In Figure 18, the

respondents acknowledge that their course of study helped start a business, with the majority of 75% saying yes and 25% saying no. Figure 23 shows 81% rated the possibility of becoming an entrepreneur through Nigerian technical institutions positively while 12% said it was poor and 7% said very poor. Figure 24 shows that respondents do not believe that graduates of the Nigerian universities are more likely to become an entrepreneur as only 16% agreed, 25% neither agree nor disagree, 34% disagree, 23% strongly disagree and 2% low quality.

The start-up skill scores of the entrepreneurial ecosystem of the countries presented in Figure 4 indicate that only the United States and the United Kingdom show higher than 50% start-up-skill scores between 2015 and 2019, while none of the Sub-Saharan Africa countries presented had scores as high as 40%. It implies that the populations of Nigeria, South Africa, and Botswana do not possess the necessary skills to start a business based on their perceptions, and tertiary educational institutions are not sufficiently available in each country. Figure 5 presents the risk acceptance pillar scores. For the five-year period of 2015 to 2019, Nigeria's highest score is 21% in 2018, followed by 20% in 2017, 10% in 2019, and 8% in 2015 and 2016. Therefore, it can be said of Nigeria that a majority of the citizens are not willing to risk starting a business, the environment is relatively high in risk, and the instability of the institutions adds to the risk of starting a business. Also, the Figure 7 results about the opportunity start-up pillar indicated the United States and the United Kingdom had minimum scores of 73% in 2015 and 77% in 2016, respectively. The Sub-Saharan African countries presented are all below 50%, while Nigeria especially is extremely low. The maximum Nigerian score was 22% in 2015, and it decreased to 21% in 2016, 8% in 2017, 7% in 2018 and then increased slightly to 12% in 2019. It shows that the Nigerian entrepreneurship opportunity start-up pillar is unstable while her counterparts South Africa and Botswana are fairly stable but not fully maximised like

the United States and the United Kingdom. Therefore, Nigeria is described as a country where entrepreneurs are not motivated by opportunity but rather by necessity. The government does not make becoming an entrepreneur easy.

H₁ Decision

H₁ is rejected, which states 'there seems to be no positive relationship between the level of entrepreneurs and outturns of tertiary institution graduates in Nigeria'. The reasons supported by the analysed data are as follows.

It was well established through Figure 18 that the course of study in Nigeria helps people start a business. Similarly, Figure 23 revealed that Nigerian technical institutions give quality training to become an entrepreneur. However, Figure 24 shows that Nigerian university graduates are not more likely to become entrepreneurs. Equally, Figure 4, which compared Nigeria to other countries, found that the populations of Nigeria, South Africa, and Botswana do not possess the necessary skills to start a business based on their perceptions, and tertiary educational institutions are not sufficiently available in each country. Also, it was obtained from Figure 5 that the majority of Nigerian citizens are not willing to risk starting a business, the environment is relatively high in risk, and the instability of the institutions add to the risk of starting a business. Again, in Figure 7, compared to the United States, the United Kingdom, South Africa and Botswana, Nigeria is described as a nation whose entrepreneurs are not motivated by opportunity but rather by necessity. The government does not make choosing to be an entrepreneur easy. However, Figure 13 indicated that 96% surveyed often see their graduates establish their business ventures due to their acquired skills. Figure 10 posited that a Nigerian could become an entrepreneur as a result of tertiary education. Also, considering the facts above, it is well established that the course of study in Nigeria help in a start-up a

business, and Nigerian technical institution give quality training to become an entrepreneur. H_1 is rejected. There is a positive relationship between the level of entrepreneurs and outturns of tertiary institution graduates in Nigeria.

6.1.2 Hypothesis Two

To test H_2 that states 'there seems to be a negative relationship between entrepreneurship and types of Nigerian graduate jobs', the statistical analyses presented in Chapter Five that are relevant for this hypothesis are Figure 3, Figure 6, Figure 11, Figure 12, Figure 15, Figure 19, Figure 20, Figure 23, Figure 24 and Figure 25. The details follow.

First, the data were categorised into four parts. The first part is Figure 11 and Figure 12, centred on the training quality; the second part is Figure 15, Figure 19 and Figure 20, focused on job competitiveness; the third part is Figure 23 and Figure 24, which look into Nigerian higher education capability; and final part is Figure 25, Figure 3 and Figure 6 that focus on the entrepreneurs and the process of becoming an entrepreneur.

Category 1: The response in Figure 11 revealed a 95% majority who say, 'Yes' that they provide vocational/innovation training and the remaining 5% say 'No'. A similar investigation in Figure 12 shows that 98% of research participants say, 'Yes, the programme they provide as a platform for students to become entrepreneurs', while only 2% declared 'No'. With these responses, it could be assumed there is enough provision and assurance of training to become an entrepreneur, which, in turn, it led to the belief that students received training that could make them entrepreneurs in Nigeria.

Category 2: Figure 15 revealed that 42% sometimes have tertiary institution graduate positions vacant in their organisation, followed by 21% who say usually, 21% say rarely, and 16% indicated always. No one said never. Figure 19 shows that 24% of respondents

see Nigerian tertiary institution graduates as their major competitor in their sector; 14% are on the fence (they say 'sometimes'), and 61% do not (40% rarely and 21% never). Additionally, Figure 20 indicated that 82% (57% always and 25% usually) of the respondents frequently receive job applications from recent graduates, while 9% said sometimes, 9% said rarely, and no one said never. With these three-dimensional inquiries and answers, it could be concluded a fair amount of graduate positions are vacant (37% responses), amidst a level of competition as a result of outturn graduates (24% response) while the rate of graduates applying for the job is very high (82% responses). This implies there is a higher number of graduates competing for a small number of vacant positions while the pressure to be gainfully employed might not be high.

Category 3: From Figure 23, 82% rated the quality of becoming an entrepreneur through Nigerian technical institutions as acceptable (21% very good, 33% good, and 28% acceptable) while 12% said it is poor and 7% declared it is very poor. At the same time, Figure 24 showed that only 16% agreed with the statement 'Nigerian university graduates are more likely to become an entrepreneur'; 25% neither agree nor disagree, while 59% disagree (34% disagree, 23% strongly disagree and 2% low quality). With these two enquiries, it could be concluded that Nigerians can become entrepreneurs through their tertiary education. A large percentage of the responses indicates that people can become entrepreneurs through their Nigerian technical training, which was expressly created for this purpose.

Category 4: Figure 25 showed research participants' main motives for starting a business include 12% who said, 'due to no job', 19% due to opportunity and 28% due to educational exposure (among other motivations). It infers that a small number of graduates are entrepreneurs because there was no job, others because of the opportunity,

and slightly more because of their educational background. Figure 3 shows that the opportunity perception of entrepreneurship in Nigeria compared to two peers in Sub-Saharan Africa, the United States and the United Kingdom, was very low and fluctuating. In 2017 and 2018, Nigeria was 37%, while the lowest scores in South Africa and Botswana were in 2018 at 40% and 2016 at 45%, respectively. This score shows a bottleneck of perception about entrepreneurship opportunity in Nigeria. It implied Nigerians could identify opportunities to start a business in specific years while the institutional environment partially supported acting on those opportunities. Likewise, Figure 6 shows that Nigeria's cultural support of entrepreneurship is very low compared to other countries, with a high score of 22% in 2015 and 2016, and the scores in 2017, 2018, 2019 are 17%, 19% and 17%, respectively. This indicates how Nigeria as a country views entrepreneurship. Nigerians do not easily choose to be an entrepreneur, and corruption has made entrepreneurship a relatively less-attractive career path than others. Figure 25, Figure 3 and Figure 6 could be seen to demonstrate that few Nigerian graduates are entrepreneurs or Nigerians do not easily choose to be entrepreneurs despite the lack of white-collar jobs and the difficulties caused by corruption. The opportunity perception of the Nigerian graduates seems to be low, or they are able to identify opportunities to start a business in certain years and not able in other years. A relatively small number of graduates choose to be an entrepreneur because of their educational background.

H₂ Decision

H₂, that state 'there seems to be a negative relationship between entrepreneurship and types of Nigerian graduate jobs', is accepted based on the followed facts. First, it has been deduced from Figure 11 and Figure 12 that Nigerian tertiary institution graduates received an education that could make them an entrepreneur. Similarly, findings from

Figure 23 and Figure 24 established that a large percentage of respondents believe that people can become entrepreneurs through education received in Nigerian technical institutions, which were predominantly created to empower them to do so.

However, with the evidence that graduates from Nigerian tertiary institutions received training and can become entrepreneurs, Figure 15, Figure 19 and Figure 20 revealed that a higher number of graduates compete for a small number of vacant positions. Also, Figure 25, Figure 3 and Figure 6 have established that few Nigerian graduates are entrepreneurs, or Nigerians do not easily choose to be entrepreneurs despite a lack of white-collar jobs and difficulties due to corruption. The opportunity perception of the Nigerian graduates seems to be low, or they are able to identify opportunities to start a business in certain years and not able in other years. Therefore, there is a negative relationship between entrepreneurship and types of Nigerian graduate jobs.

6.1.3 Hypothesis Three

To test H₃ that states 'there is likely no correlation of entrepreneurship and tertiary education in Nigeria', the statistical analyses presented in Chapter Five that are relevant for this hypothesis are Figure 4, Figure 7, Figure 8, Figure 16, Figure 18, Figure 21, Figure 22, Figure 23, and Figure 26. The details follow.

From Figure 16, the importance of creating a business venture in Nigeria is well established, with 95% saying it is important (61% say it is extremely important and 34% held it is very important) while the remaining 5% said it is somewhat important. Figure 18 shows that 75% of the research participants said their course of study helped them start a business, while only 25% said no. However, there is a mixed reaction in Figure 21 to the question of whether Nigeria is an entrepreneurial nation due to tertiary education graduates creating a business venture: 32% say yes (16% strongly agree and 16% agree),

23% neither agree nor disagree, 30% disagree and 16% strongly disagree. Figure 22 shows how respondents' rate the contribution their tertiary education made to their business start-up, where the majority (90%) rated it as 'exceptional' to 'excellent', 'good', or 'fair', while only 10% said very poor. Also, Figure 23 shows that 21% have a high opinion that Nigerian technical institution graduates can become entrepreneurs, followed by 33% good, 28% acceptable, 12% poor, and 7% very poor.

Figure 26 shows the respondents view on what capacity they think Nigeria needs a graduate of vocational/innovation training institutions; 82% definitely would, 11% probably would, 5% would not and 2% definitely would not. In Figure 8, the United States and the United Kingdom continue to show the greatest strength in human capital, scores above the average in all the years presented. It is otherwise in Sub Saharan Africa, where no country scored above 50% score for the period studied. The highest and lowest scores for South Africa, Botswana and Nigeria, respectively, are 28% and 20%, 45% and 34%, and 46% and 38%. This implies Nigeria has a more highly educated population of entrepreneurs who are well trained in business and able to move freely in the labour market than Botswana and South Africa, which are regional leaders of Sub-Saharan Africa. Figure 4 and Figure 7 are interpreted in hypothesis one above.

H₃ Decision

H₃, which states 'there is likely no correlation of entrepreneurship and tertiary education in Nigeria', is accepted. The reasons are the following. First, it was well established that it is important to create a business venture in Nigeria (95% of respondents say it is important), and a course of study helps in the start-up of a business (75% agree). Also, tertiary education's contribution to business start-ups in Nigeria was rated as high (90% ranging from exceptional to fair amount of help). Additionally, it was rated 82% the

quality of becoming an entrepreneur through Nigerian technical institutions, and it was discovered Nigeria needs graduates of vocational/innovation trained/educated with 82% respondents said definitely would. In the same vein, Figure 8 indicated that between 2015 to 2019, Nigeria has more highly educated population of entrepreneurs who are well trained in business and able to move freely in the labour market than Botswana and South Africa, which are regional leaders of Sub-Saharan Africa in entrepreneurship.

However, Figure 4 shows that from 2015 to 2019, the populations of Nigeria, South Africa, and Botswana did not possess the necessary skills to start a business based on their perceptions, and tertiary educational institutions are not sufficiently available in each country. Likewise, in Figure 7, Nigeria is described as a country where entrepreneurs are not motivated by opportunity but rather by necessity, and the government does not make the choice to be an entrepreneur easy. Also, Nigeria is identified is not identified as an entrepreneurial nation based on tertiary institution graduates creating a business venture (Figure 21). Therefore, there is likely no correlation between entrepreneurship and tertiary education in Nigeria. H_3 is accepted.

6.1.4 Hypothesis Four

In an attempt to test H_4 that states 'there is no possibility of positive influences of tertiary education on the entrepreneurial skills development in Nigeria', the statistical analyses presented in Chapter Five that are relevant for this hypothesis are Figure 4, Figure 8, Figure 21, Figure 22, Figure 23, and Figure 24. The details follow.

The investigation outcomes in Figure 21 show that Nigeria is not an entrepreneurial nation as a result of tertiary institution graduates creating a business venture. The response includes 32% who agreed she is (16% strongly agree and 16% agree) while 23% neither agree nor disagree, 30% disagree, and 16% strongly disagree. Figure 22

shows that 90% said that Nigerian tertiary education contributed to their business start-up, with 12% saying the contribution was exceptional, 17% excellent, 17% very good, 27% good, and 17% fair, while 10% said very poor.

Figure 23 shows that 21% have a high opinion that Nigerian technical institution graduates can become entrepreneurs, followed by 33% good, 28% acceptable, 12% poor, and 7% very poor. Figure 24 revealed that 16% agreed that Nigerian university graduates are more likely to become an entrepreneur while 25% neither agree nor disagree, 34% disagree, 23% strongly disagree and 2% low quality. Figure 4 was interpreted in hypothesis one, and Figure 8 was interpreted in hypothesis three.

H₄ Decision

The findings invalidated H₄ that states that 'there is no positive influences of tertiary education on the entrepreneurial skills development in Nigeria', based on the following. In Figure 22, 90% of respondents rated the contribution of Nigerian tertiary education to their business start-up as positive. Similarly, Figure 8 reported that for 2015-2019, Nigeria had a more highly educated population of entrepreneurs who are well trained in business and able to move freely in the labour market than Botswana and South Africa, which are regional leaders of Sub-Saharan Africa entrepreneurship ecosystem. In addition, Figure 23 rated the quality of becoming an entrepreneur through Nigerian technical institutions at 81%.

Meanwhile, from Figure 24, it is established that Nigerian universities graduates are not more likely to become an entrepreneur. Also, Figure 4 shows that from 2015 to 2019, Nigerians do not possess the necessary skills to start a business based on their perceptions, and tertiary educational institutions are not sufficiently available. Similarly,

Figure 21 shows Nigeria is not an entrepreneurial nation due to tertiary institution graduates creating a business venture.

However, H₄ is still rejected. There are positive influences of tertiary education on entrepreneurial skills development in Nigeria. The evidence shows that Nigerian tertiary education contributes to business start-ups, Nigeria has a more highly educated population of entrepreneurs who are well trained in business than Botswana and South Africa, and the likelihood of becoming an entrepreneur through Nigerian technical institutions is highly rated.

6.1.5 Hypothesis Five

To test H₅ that states 'there is no positive relationship between educated entrepreneurs and successful entrepreneurs in Nigeria', the statistical analyses presented in Chapter Five relevant for this hypothesis are Figure 4, Figure 8, Figure 14, Figure 17, Figure 22, Figure 27, and Figure 28. The details follow.

Figure 14 shows that the majority of respondents (58%) are employers of small enterprises that employed between 10 and 49 people, followed by micro-enterprises that employed fewer than 10 employees (16%), large enterprises that employed above 100 employees (14%) and medium enterprises that employed between 50 and 99 employees (12%). Figure 17 revealed that 62% of respondents believe that Nigerian regulatory bodies do not support business start-ups (39% said 'not so helpful' and 23% said 'not at all helpful'), 38% said they are helpful (30% said they are somewhat helpful, 7% said they are helpful and 2% think that they are extremely helpful). Figure 22 shows how respondents rated tertiary education's contribution to business start-up in Nigeria as very high at 90% (12% exceptional, 17% excellent, 17% very good, 27% good, 17% fair) and 10% very poor. Figure 27 reveals that course of study in Nigeria helps people succeed

in business with 75% support in total (16% say extremely helpful, 32% agree it is very helpful, 27% agree somewhat helpful), and 25% said it does not help (18% said it is not so helpful and 7% declared it is not at all helpful). Figure 28 shows that being educated helps nurture long-term business relationships, with 86% positive responses in total, including 45% strongly agree, 32% agree, 9% somewhat agree, 7% neither agree nor disagree, 2% somewhat disagree, and 5% strongly disagree. Figure 4 indicates that the United States and the United Kingdom showed higher than 50% start-up-skill scores between 2015 and 2019, while none of the Sub-Saharan African countries presented had scores as high as 40%. Equally, the populations of Nigeria, South Africa, and Botswana do not possess the necessary skills to start a business based on their perceptions, and tertiary educational institutions are not sufficiently available in each country. Figure 8 shows that the United States and the United Kingdom continue to show the greatest strength in human capital, with scores above 50% in all years. This is otherwise in Sub-Saharan Africa, where there are no countries above a 50% score. The highest and lowest scores for South Africa, Botswana and Nigeria, respectively, are 28% and 20%; 45% and 34%; and 46% and 38%. This implies Nigeria has a more highly educated population of entrepreneurs who are well trained in business and able to move freely in the labour market than Botswana and South Africa, which are the regional leaders of Sub-Saharan Africa.

H₅ Decision

H₅ is rejected. It states, 'there is no positive relationship between educated entrepreneurs and successful entrepreneurs in Nigeria', based on the following. First, Figure 14 revealed that most of these entrepreneurs are small enterprises (58%). In examining the effect of the environmental factors on these entrepreneurs' activities, Figure 17 pointed these

respondents believe that Nigerian regulatory bodies do not support business start-ups. Despite the environmental problem facing Nigerian entrepreneurs, Figure 22 revealed that tertiary education's contribution to business start-ups in Nigeria is very high. Similarly, Figure 21 shows that a course of study in Nigeria helps entrepreneurs succeed in business. More importantly, it was established in Figure 28 that being educated helps nurture long-term business relationships. Also, Figure 8 shows that from 2015 to 2019, Nigeria has a population of highly educated entrepreneurs who are well trained in business and able to move freely in the labour market compared to Botswana and South Africa. However, Figure 4 showed that Nigeria, South Africa, and Botswana population does not possess the necessary skills to start a business based on their perceptions, and there are not enough tertiary educational institutions in each country, 2015 to 2019.

Based on these findings, Nigerian higher education contributes to business start-ups, offers support to succeed in business and helps to nurture long-term business relationships. Therefore, there is a positive relationship between educated entrepreneurs and successful entrepreneurs in Nigeria.

6.2 Hypotheses Test Results in Discussion

The findings from the field research are discussed in the context of the related literature. This section aims to answer the study research questions based on the objectives of this study. Furthermore, it relates and substantiates the research result with existing theoretical and empirical knowledge on the topic. Therefore, the discussion is presented with the tested hypothesis and research questions.

6.2.1 The Level of Entrepreneurs and Outturns of Graduates in Nigeria

The data show a positive relationship between the level of entrepreneurs and outturns of tertiary institution graduates in Nigeria. This indicated that the number of entrepreneurs

is comparable to the number of graduates in Nigeria. This hypothesis result only supports a few previous studies, while most previous empirical studies in Nigeria show contradictory results. Attahiru et al.'s (2020) investigation in the northern part of Nigeria concluded that those students in Federal Polytechnic have a positive personal attitude towards entrepreneurship intention, and Mirjana et al. (2018) found that personal attitudes towards entrepreneurship are positively related to one's entrepreneurial intentions.

In contrast, Odumosu et al. (2020) show that the adopted Nigerian entrepreneurship education system has a positive but insignificant effect on Nigerian graduate entrepreneurship. This is evidenced in another study that 'found that graduate turnout outpaced the graduate employment over the years in Nigeria' (Akinyemi, et al., 2012b, p. 264). Additionally, Olofinyehun et al. (2018) found a high prevalence of interest in entrepreneurship but a low prevalence of the entrepreneurial practice in Nigeria. Additional scenarios include the account of how millions of Nigerian graduates pursued limited job slots, which led to the death of some, which were given by Babalobi (2019). These accounts include the Nigeria Immigration Service in 2014 advertising 4,000 vacant positions, receiving 520,000 applications, and 16 people died during the process. Likewise, Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) in 2018 announced 500 positions, 700,000 graduates applied, including 2,000 first-class graduates. When the Federal Road Safety Corps (FRSC) advertised for 4,000 job vacancies, they received 324,000 applications. Recently, 60,000 Nigerian graduates went for interviews for about 100 vacant jobs at the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC).

Theoretically, Nigerian graduates actions are aligned with the theory of economic development's postulate, which states 'the will and the action' are what anyone needs to

be an entrepreneur to attain higher social status as an individual (Schumpeter, 1943). This study finding validated the theory in that it shows some characteristics of entrepreneurs demonstrated by Nigerian graduates. For instance, with the evidence of Nigerian graduates' curiosity and enthusiasm in competition for limited job slots, the theory portrays their strong will and actions to attain higher social status. Also, other characteristics of an entrepreneur that Nigerian graduates have demonstrated include passion, positive attitude and motivation (Arruti & Panos-Castro, 2020).

However, what could have contributed to the unmatched outturn of Nigerian tertiary institution graduates and numbers of entrepreneurs? Studies on African nations have shown that no other regions have a significant positive contribution to entrepreneurship development (Babajide, et al., 2020). In contrast, Olaore et al. (2021) has shown a significant direct relationship between government policies and infrastructure development. One element of mismatch could be attributed to the Nigerian government's level of contribution to the development of the entrepreneurship sector based on these two findings.

Therefore, the inconsistent findings on this hypothesis and the prevailing situation in Nigeria called for further extensive study.

6.2.2 Entrepreneurship and Types of Nigerian Graduate Jobs

The study's findings revealed there is a negative relationship between entrepreneurship and types of Nigerian graduate jobs. This finding has been supported in many dimensions. First, the evidence of the multitude of Nigerian graduates chasing limited job vacancies is demonstrated in hypothesis one above. Therefore, the definition of entrepreneurship and the desperate job-hunting scenarios faced by Nigerian graduates showed firm support for this hypothesis result: there is a negative relationship between entrepreneurship and

types of Nigerian graduates' jobs. Also, Akinyemi et al.'s (2012b, p. 264) findings reveal that Nigerian graduates do not possess employable skills to match the requirements for jobs in the present labour market.

Thus, Odumosu et al. (2020, p. 50) described graduate entrepreneurship as 'the process of designing, launching and running a new business, by graduates combining knowledge from entrepreneurship education and training to start and manage a business venture'. And the Nigerian government incorporated entrepreneurship in the national education system (FRN, 2004) and made it compulsory at all levels of tertiary education since 2006 (Yahya, 2011). Then, studies have established that entrepreneurship education significantly influences students' entrepreneurial spirit. For instance, Hassan et al. (2020) find that entrepreneurship education encourages the entrepreneurial attitude of young people to venture into entrepreneurship. In the same vein, there is a meaningful positive relationship between entrepreneurship education and students' commitment to entrepreneurship goals (Sherkatand & Chenari, 2020). Moreover, most Nigerian graduates possess skills that could enable them to launch a business venture or to be more attractive to work in an existing one. However, research has found that Nigerian education does not significantly enhance entrepreneurship development in Nigeria (Babajide, et al., 2020, p. 12). Also, entrepreneurship education was found to have an insignificant positive effect on Nigerian graduates' entrepreneurship (Odumosu, et al., 2020).

Conversely, another study shows that 68.30% of the recent graduates in a study surveyed in Nigeria believed their academic experience prepared them for employment (Stutern, 2016). This result is similar to Harima et al.'s (2021) result that indicated tertiary education as knowledge-intensive institutions that provide learners with consistent

access to entrepreneurial or technological resources. Longva et al. (2020) show that entrepreneurship education provides space for students' career reflections where they can explore, commit to and reconsider entrepreneurship as a career.

However, in Nigeria, 'learning and inspiration account for the variation in students' attitude towards self-employment' (Iyortsuun, et al., 2020, p. 64). At the same time, investigation on entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial orientation shows no connection (Cho & Lee, 2018). Additionally, a study finds that career experiences and outcomes are highly idiosyncratic and do not seem to correspond closely to original intentions, regardless of original ambitions (Galloway, et al., 2015). This implies Nigerian graduates could still have other alternatives and not choose to create a business venture despite all the proof of inculcating entrepreneurship into Nigeria educational system and mandating it at all tertiary education levels. This could be the reason why this study has demonstrated a negative relationship between entrepreneurship and types of Nigerian graduate jobs.

Therefore, this finding would be considered as a validation of the need for achievement theory. The theory proclaimed that individuals have an inner feeling as a key to accomplishing their proposed (McClelland, 1961). Prior studies in Nigeria found the need for achievement theory positively related to Nigerian tertiary institutions students' entrepreneurship intentions. These studies include Ayodotun et al. (2021), which found the need for achievement as entrepreneurial characteristics significantly influence students' entrepreneurial intentions. Similarly, the effects of the entrepreneurship education variable had a positive and statistically significant relationship with the need for achievement and entrepreneurial goal intentions (Ndofirepi, 2020). It could be concluded education is not the predominant factor for Nigerian tertiary institutions

graduates to be empowered to become entrepreneurs or even to secure an available job as they appear to be strongly influenced by their inner feelings.

6.2.3 Correlation of Entrepreneurship and Tertiary Education

The result of this research showed no correlation between entrepreneurship and tertiary education in Nigeria. This revealed that Nigerian tertiary education graduates are unable to create a firm or growing of new enterprises based on the acquired educational skills. It shows, the overall objectives of Nigerian tertiary education institutions are not met, which state

continuously foster entrepreneurship culture amongst students and faculty with a view of not only educating them but also to support graduates of the system towards establishing and maintaining sustainable business ventures, including but not limited to those arising from research. (Yahya, 2011, p. 3)

With the understanding of entrepreneurship and objectives of tertiary education in Nigeria, even with the evidence of entrepreneurship education curriculum, the finding indicated an unrealistic goal.

Thus, this hypothesis result supports the previous studies findings in Nigeria, such as Adelaja's (2021) work that revealed no significant relationship between entrepreneurial education and entrepreneurial intention in Nigeria. Similarly, the effect of education was found not to significantly enhanced the entrepreneurship development of Nigerian students (Babajide, et al., 2020). Additionally, the level of entrepreneurial education in the Nigerian tertiary institutions was low, and the graduates produced lack employable skills, explaining the prevalence of unemployment (Agboola, 2010). Related results found in the different regions include Cho and Lee's (2018) research that showed entrepreneurship education had no connection with entrepreneurial orientation or business performance.

In contrast, some studies in Nigeria and other countries have established the relationship between entrepreneurship and tertiary education. Nimitha and Renjini's (2020) investigation result uncovered entrepreneurial training and education as an effective to elicit student-level entrepreneurial intention. Built on this is Umar and Hassan's (2020) work that found a significant relationship between interest in entrepreneurship education and academic achievement in entrepreneurship education in north-eastern Nigeria. Likewise, Vicens et al. (2021) found that education in entrepreneurship influenced the entrepreneurial spirit of Nigerians. Also, an empirical analysis demonstrated a substantially positive connection between entrepreneurship education and undergraduates' entrepreneurial intentions (Otache, 2019). In addition, educational innovation and digital innovation were found to be significantly affected by graduate entrepreneurship in Nigeria (Odumosu, et al., 2020) and enhancement of entrepreneurship education on the entrepreneurial intention by regulating students' emotions (Haddoud, et al., 2020).

Scholars in other countries that have found education and entrepreneurship interplay include Sherkatand and Chenari (2020), whose studies in Iran show a meaningful positive relationship between entrepreneurship education and students' commitment to entrepreneurship goals. Similarly, a significant relationship between management student's entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial intention was found in Morocco (Boubker, et al., 2021).

However, what could have contributed to the inconsistency of the relationship between entrepreneurship and education relationship in the context of Nigeria? First, it was found in Nigeria that entrepreneurial lecturers have a significant positive link with students' entrepreneurial intentions (Otache, 2019), and another result indicated that learning and

inspiration account for the variation in students' attitude towards self-employment (Iyortsuun, et al., 2020). Findings have also shown the major challenges impeding the institutionalization of quality education in Nigeria include inadequate funding, administrative recklessness, noncommitment of government to the educational sector and a non-meritorious standard of recruitment (Lohnan, 2019). Also, entrepreneurship education that is not well aligned with contextual peculiarities may not yield the desired outcome (Olutuase, et al., 2020). The evidence of these has been shown in Ofoegbu et al. (2018, p. 394), which revealed 'a deficient university accounting curricula and poorly motivated Nigerian accounting lecturers'. Francis et al. (2019) found that most Nigerian graduates of vocational agriculture are less likely to establish a farm or enterprise of their own, and the majority want to obtain certificates required for securing employment in paying jobs. Therefore, Nigerian tertiary education institution lecturers are not qualified to deliver even though they are not well remunerated, and these factors directly impact the students.

6.2.4 Influences of Tertiary Education on Entrepreneurial Skills Development

This finding indicated positive influences of tertiary education on entrepreneurial skills development in Nigeria. It implies teaching and learning in Nigerian higher institutions have been supporting students to develop certain entrepreneurial skills.

In the context of Nigeria, the result of this hypothesis supports limited previous studies. Edokpolor (2020, p. 329) found a 'statistically significant and positive mediating role of entrepreneurial skills developed by Nigerian undergraduates on the relationship between entrepreneurship education and the core values of sustainable development'. Likewise, Dakung et al. (2017) and Oguntimehin and Olaniran (2017) indicated that the university's role and entrepreneurship education significantly influence students'

entrepreneurial intentions in Nigeria. Another study uncovered that entrepreneurship education positively and substantially affects graduates' business start-up intention in Nigeria (Faloye & Olatunji, 2018). Additionally, research in Nigeria indicated that university students demonstrated intention towards entrepreneurship and were quite positive towards becoming entrepreneurs (Koe, 2016).

At the same time, studies from different parts of the world have established the influences of education on entrepreneurship skills development. These include 'quantitative and qualitative analysis suggests that students developed more enterprising attitudes as a result of participating in the course' (Morselli, 2018, p. 122). Al Mamun et al. (2019) discovered that entrepreneurial skills positively affect entrepreneurial competency. Similarly, a significant improvement was found in the enterprising characteristics of students because of undertaking the learning programme in enterprise education (Yasin & Khansari, 2020, p. 872). Also, education was found to contribute to encouraging entrepreneurial initiative and entrepreneurial attitude development (Dragomir & Panzaru, 2015, p. 56). Additionally, it was found that 'entrepreneurial training and education are effective in eliciting an important student-level outcome of entrepreneurial intention' (Aboobaker & D, 2020, p. 73).

In contrast, the effect of education appears not to have significantly enhanced entrepreneurship development in Nigeria (Babajide, et al., 2020, p. 12). Therefore, the consequences are due to the details the researcher demonstrated in the last paragraph under Section 6.2.3 above.

Also, the influences of education on entrepreneurship skills development might be ascribed to 'the demand of globalization which creates more pressure for the development of unique skills' (Mattare, 2010, p. 25). However, it has been suggested that

appropriate educational support must be applied to help to develop students' entrepreneurial attitudes and improve matching their skill expectations with their skill achievement (Bazkiaei, et al., 2020).

6.2.5 The Relationship Between Educated Entrepreneurs and Successful Entrepreneurs

This study's findings revealed a positive relationship between educated entrepreneurs and successful entrepreneurs in Nigeria. It suggests that Nigerian higher education contributes to business start-ups, supports business success, and helping to nurture long-term business relationships. Also, a successful entrepreneur is described as an individual who must 'be operationally informed of finance, marketing, strategy, and human resource management' (Mattare, 2010, p. 24).

There are some corroborations of this hypothesis' findings with the previous researchers' outcomes. In the Nigerian context, they found that financial literacy knowledge and practice in small business operations enhances firms' sustainability (Babajide, et al., 2021). Also, Mbah and Okeke's (2020) study showed skill acquisition significantly affects Nigerian youth empowerment. This shows that a relationship exists between educated entrepreneurs and successful entrepreneurs in Nigeria to some extent.

Many studies have demonstrated the relationship between these two concepts outside Nigeria. For instance, the role of the chief executive officer education in investment-cash flow sensitivity is highly significant during a crisis period (Gupta, et al., 2021). Comparably, the effect of education on profits is found sizeable for some groups of entrepreneurs (Kolstad & Wiig, 2015). Also, Kurczewska and Mackiewicz's (2020) empirical study demonstrates that individuals with more diverse education have both greater chances of starting a company and a higher probability of entrepreneurial

success. Additionally, a longitudinal study of Peters and Brijlal (2011) for two consecutive years showed a relationship between the business owner's level of education and the business's ability to grow by increasing its labour force and annual turnover. Likewise, strong evidence was found supporting the relationship between levels of general education and several entrepreneurial success measures (Dickson, et al., 2008), in the sense that the findings have revealed that entrepreneurial skills enhance and have a positive effect on entrepreneurial competencies (Al Mamun, et al., 2019; Hagg & Gabrielsson, 2021). At the same time, educated people have more skills and the ability to increase productivity and income level (Munir & Kanwal, 2020, p. 1043). Also, more education is associated with more knowledge and skills in the practice of business (Bosire & Etyang, 2003).

Thus, two theories are identified with this hypothesis finding. First, it was established there is a relationship between educated entrepreneurs and successful entrepreneurs in Nigeria and beyond. In the context of Nigeria, it validates the theory of social change. There is a history of a successful entrepreneurship system in Nigeria before the colonial system of government and empirical evidence from the previous studies. This theory is on the assumption that 'traditional society retains its stability (including economic stability) because the behaviour of its members (peasants and elite alike) is governed by tradition and authority, rather than by initiative and autonomous decision making' (Everett, 1959). Drawing from the literature reviewed in Section 3.4.1, it was established that before the era of colonialism, Nigeria has a traditional entrepreneurship system which was a huge success. It was affirmed that

entrepreneurship education is not a new phenomenon in the annals of Nigeria; it has always been an age-long tradition, a culture and a habit that has consistently been transferred from one generation to another

within the diverse ethnic nationalities that made up Nigeria.
(Akhuemonkhan, et al., 2013, p. 2)

Also, a key finding revealed that entrepreneurs who participated in the Igbo entrepreneurship model have higher business survival rates, business growth rates and access to trade and informal credit. In contrast, non-Igbo entrepreneurship model entrepreneurs only have better access to formal credit sources than the Igbo entrepreneurship model graduates (Ekesiobi & Dimnwobi, 2021). Evidence was found for the ancestral trajectory of the entrepreneurship system of Nigeria before colonial rule. That is, old Nigeria retained its economic stability governed by tradition and authority rather than initiative and autonomous decision making (Everett, 1959).

At the same time, the theory of planned behaviour supposes that an individual acquired resources and opportunities to deliver desired behaviour no matter the intention for success. This is not the case for the proven relationship between educated entrepreneurs and successful entrepreneurs in Nigeria. This research finds that education and Nigerian tradition have significant influences on the success of entrepreneurs, which are experience and economic factors. Therefore, it confirmed the arguments of Young et al. (2013) and Kalafatis et al. (1999) that behavioural intention such as experience, mood, fear, and environmental and economic factors have the potential to influence intention about behaviours.

CHAPTER SEVEN: CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

7.1 Conclusions

At individual citizen and national levels, it is understood that education and entrepreneurship interconnect and collaborate as an agent of innovative change, technological development, and competitiveness. However, these are important in a developing nation such as Nigeria, and a few studies have examined the relationship between tertiary education and entrepreneurship. The concern of this research is to question the interplay between tertiary education and entrepreneurship in Nigeria. Therefore, the researcher aims to convey a comprehensive understanding of the relationship between education and entrepreneurship in Nigeria, resulting in socioeconomic promotion and business development. Five research questions were generated and translated into hypotheses toward achieving the broad objectives of this study, and they have been addressed. A summary of the research and findings is presented below.

7.1.1 Research Summary

At the initial stage, an understanding of the connection between entrepreneurship and education was sought to build a robust, comprehensive background for this study. The word 'entrepreneurship' originated from the German and French languages, and both mean 'undertake'. Entrepreneurship emerged as a legitimate field of academics due to its importance to economic growth. However, there is no generally accepted definition for entrepreneurship. Scholars and academicians contribute to its field from economics, psychology, sociology, and organisation and business management. Their consensus definition is that entrepreneurship establishes a new venture or promotes an existing one. An individual taking such responsibility is referred to as an 'entrepreneur'. As a

group, entrepreneurs are characterised as innovative, enthusiastic, resilient, creative, ambitious, passionate, risk-taker, opportunity recogniser, leadership potentiality, network builder, independent and self-reliant people. There are many ways to act as an entrepreneur, including social entrepreneur, serial entrepreneur, e-preneur, nascent entrepreneurs, and green entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurship is a multi-faceted phenomenon.

Some of the dichotomies of entrepreneurship in the literature include opportunity versus necessity, formal versus informal, and legal versus illegal. With the focus on actualising these study objectives, existing knowledge explored per the itemised research questions includes the theory of economic development, needs for achievement theory, theory of social change, and theory of planned behaviour. Thus, education is found as a critical player in individual, society, and national development. At the same time, entrepreneurship is indicated as the key to economic development and growth. As education toward building entrepreneurial skills is regarded as an entrepreneurship education. Then entrepreneurship and education can be leveraged and interconnected to develop human capital, as affirmed in empirical and evidence-based research. Consequently, the entrepreneurship capacity of the nation was examined to understand the competitiveness, policy development and state of entrepreneurship in Nigeria.

Next on this preliminary research is the insight into the Nigerian tertiary education system and applications of entrepreneurship education in the context of Nigeria. This work focused on a better understanding of the Nigerian education system that sets the stage for a meaningful relationship with entrepreneurship. This work shows the formulation of Nigerian tertiary education, objectives, management system, types, statistics, challenges and output. Also, an insight into the application of entrepreneurship

education is explored. This work helped to build a robust and comprehensive picture of how entrepreneurship and education interplay in Nigeria. Gaps in the literature were identified, and research questions for this study were finalised.

The research approach and methodology aimed to establish theory and procedures for data gathering and evaluation that will help produce valid and reliable answers to the research questions. Therefore, the research philosophy adopted is an epistemological assumption with a pragmatist stance, followed by the deductive approach. The study used mixed methods, with a combined purpose (descriptive, explanatory, and evaluative), and combined research strategies (case study, survey strategy, and archival and documentary) using primary and secondary sources, and stratified and purposive sampling techniques and survey methods.

The primary and secondary data gathered were integrated and presented. This includes secondary data from the GEDI and higher learning institutions in Nigeria and a survey. The private owners of IEDs in Nigeria are the survey participants. The questionnaire went through a validation and reliability test before it was administered to ensure consistency and accuracy. The questionnaires were administered via a web-based survey tool, and data were analysed with an MS Excel spreadsheet.

7.1.2 Findings and Conclusions

Figure 31 below presents the findings of this study based on the secondary and primary data gathered and analysed.

Figure 31: Findings of the Study Model

Source 36: Designed by the author

As demonstrated in Figure 31, the study has shown a positive relationship between the level of entrepreneurs and outturns of tertiary institution graduates in Nigeria. This is due to a strong indication that a Nigerian can become an entrepreneur as a result of tertiary education, as well as confirmation from the IEI proprietors that their graduates often establish their venture based on the acquired skills. However, this finding does not support earlier research work.

There was also evidence of a negative relationship between entrepreneurship and types of Nigerian graduate jobs; see Figure 31 above. On the one hand, Nigerian graduates received the skills that could make them entrepreneurs. On the other hand, Nigerian graduates have no willingness to become entrepreneurs, and the majority are still competing for the limited number of salaried job vacancies to the point of death on many occasions. There is more consensus from the past studies with this outcome.

Figure 31 above shows no evidence of a correlation between entrepreneurship and tertiary education. Nigeria is identified as a non-entrepreneurial nation in terms of tertiary institution graduates creating a business venture. The result shows that Nigeria is best described as a country where entrepreneurs are not motivated by opportunity but by necessity. However, the Nigerian government does not make the choice to be an entrepreneur easy. The prior studies supported this finding very well.

This study established favourable influences of tertiary education on entrepreneurial skills development in Nigeria. Tertiary education contributes to business start-ups and was rated high in reasons for becoming an entrepreneur through Nigerian technical institutions. This outcome supported many previous findings.

Also, this study concludes that there is a positive relationship between educated entrepreneurs and successful entrepreneurs in Nigeria; see Figure 31 above. This is

because education supports success in business, helps to nurture long-term business and contributes to business start-ups. Previous studies have also shown similar results.

7.2 Recommendations

In the light of this study findings, the researcher makes the followings recommendations.

- As many graduates are already on the street searching for jobs with some entrepreneurship skills and capability, it will be of great interest if the Nigerian government could set up a platform to support them in their business ventures and innovative ideas such as the setting of up laboratory and manufacturing space, acquiring and allocating land, patent approval and bank loans.
- Because most graduates are pursuing white-collar jobs despite some entrepreneurial skills acquired, the Nigerian government should develop a reorientation programme that could bridge the gaps that graduates might be missing. It should be targeted to specific sectors or industries as needed in every part of the country.
- As there are rapid changes in the global labour market requirement, there is a strong and urgent need for the Nigerian government, employers and recruiters to collaborate with entrepreneurship education curriculum developers and policymakers in educational sectors to develop programming and curriculum that is up to these challenges. This would bridge the gaps between entrepreneurship and tertiary education mismatch.
- For the effective transition of graduates to entrepreneurs so far, tertiary education has positive influences on entrepreneurial skills development in Nigeria. It could be helpful to introduce placement services after graduation or inculcating

entrepreneurship into National Youth Services Corps (NYSC), where graduates will be paid and exposed to the business world.

- The Nigerian government should pay special attention to the educational sector and entrepreneurship sector by ensuring the parastatals and agencies involved are up to date in their services.
- Through the federal ministry of education, the Nigerian government should institute entrepreneurship education at all levels of education throughout Nigeria, such as the 'catch them young' programme.
- The tertiary institutions should engage in capacity building of the staff and teachers to effectively deliver entrepreneurship education.
- There should be a collaborative engagement with field expertise at the institution level to add more value to the students' experience before graduation.

7.3 Research Contributions

In the light of the foregoing findings of this thesis, the research has improved the understanding of the connections between tertiary education and entrepreneurship in the context of Nigeria. Therefore, the following contributions have been made to the body of managerial and academic knowledge.

- The thesis broadens the literature of education and entrepreneurship constructs in the context of developing nations. Some research has explored these subjects individually, but they have rarely been researched in an interconnected form. Therefore, this study has contributed to filling the gap in the literature on the interplay of education and entrepreneurship.
- This study showed that the rate of graduating students in Nigerian tertiary institutions are similar to the number of entrepreneurs in the country. This improves

the ability of Nigerians to improve their standard of living, drive innovation, and create wealth.

- Despite the constraints Nigerian graduates face in becoming gainfully employed or working as an entrepreneur, the study found that they demonstrated their willingness and actions toward attainment. Therefore, this research contributed theoretically by supporting Schumpeter's (1943) supposition of economic development theory.
- This study showed that entrepreneurship and types of graduates' jobs are unrelated in Nigeria. Therefore, it raises questions about the quality of services offered by the bodies of tertiary institutions' management, teaching teams, and policymakers.
- The Nigerian government has enacted and mandated entrepreneurship education curriculum at all levels of tertiary educations for about two decades, but many graduates have not chosen to create any business venture. Therefore, the study finds that entrepreneurship education does not have an influence on their career decision apart from an 'inner feeling' (McClelland, 1961). This is a theoretical contribution that validated the theorist hypothesis in the context of developing economics.
- This research contributed to the practices and nation's policymakers' decision-making process by demonstrating the lack of relationship between entrepreneurship and tertiary education. Particularly, it draws attention to the content of curriculum, and need for practitioners' involvement to match the skills required in the field with those taught in the curriculum, leading to high quality productivity and performance.
- This study contributed to the managerial knowledge by indicating the influences of tertiary education on the entrepreneurship skills development of Nigerian graduates. The result is positive, and it indicates the availability of knowledge that organisations could use to optimise production and performance.

- As a managerial contribution, this study found that the education and success of entrepreneurs are related. This finding begins to unfold one mystery of entrepreneur success that could serve as a lesson for others.
- This study provides new insight into the theory of social change in the context of Nigeria by affirming that traditional society retains its stability (Everett, 1959). Educated entrepreneurs were found to be related to successful entrepreneurs, which further confirms the long-term historical success of informal entrepreneurship in Nigeria.
- The study made a practical contribution to tertiary education institution managers who have a strategic role in promoting and widening institutionalisation of entrepreneurship education by presenting empirical evidence on the state and relationship of tertiary education and entrepreneurship in Nigeria.

7.4 Research Limitations and Suggestions for Further Studies

Despite the contributions of this study to the body of knowledge, some cautions must be taken in its implementations based on the scope of this study. These are enumerated below with the submissions of areas for additional examination.

- There is a disparity in the finding that states there is a positive relationship between the level of entrepreneurs and outturns of tertiary institution graduates in Nigeria. This could have been achievable but that it has not been disturbing and unfortunate. However, further research is required to shed more light on this subject.
- The graduate entrepreneur research participants provided the primary perceptions on which this study is built; this may be a small group that limits the quality of information but is relevant for this degree. Therefore, future studies might expand the scope by surveying a different segment of graduate entrepreneurs.

- The chosen sample approach for this study limited its findings. The researcher strives to overcome this by focusing on the segment of the education industry. Also, the limitation is complemented and minimised by using the data from the GEDI. Therefore, it would be informative to include other industries in future research.
- As part of the data gathering method used in this study, the risk of research participants not providing accurate answers to the questionnaire survey cannot be overlooked despite the certification of the validity and reliability of the test. Future studies can build on this subject.
- This study has examined the interplay of entrepreneurship and tertiary education cross-sectionally, which perhaps could have limited the perceptions on this subject. The body of knowledge about industry education and entrepreneurship, policymakers, and practitioners would benefit from longitudinal research findings on this topic.
- Generalising case study research to the population is always an issue. However, this study supports naturalistic generalisations of similar cases and is generalisable to theoretical propositions. Because it shows limitations, it would be of great value for another study to research this subject in a broader scope in the future.

REFERENCES

- Abend, G., 2008. The Meaning of 'Theory'. *American Sociological Association*, 26(2), pp. 176 - 199.
- Aboobaker, N. & D, R., 2020. Human Capital and Entrepreneurial Intentions: Do Entrepreneurship Education and Training Provided by Universities Add Value?. *Emerald Publishing Limited*, 28(2), pp. 73-83.
- Abu-Saifan, S., 2012. Social Entrepreneurship: Definition and Boundaries. *Technology Innovation Management Review*, 2(2), pp. 22-27.
- Acs, Z. J., Szerb, L. & Autio, E., 2015. *Global Entrepreneurship Index 2015*, Washington: The Global Entrepreneurship and Development Institute.
- Acs, Z. J., Szerb, L. & Autio, E., 2016. *Global Entrepreneurship Index 2016*, Washington: The Global Entrepreneurship and Development Institute.
- Acs, Z. J., Szerb, L., Autio, E. & Lloyd, A., 2017. *The Global Entrepreneurship Index 2017*, Washington: The Global Entrepreneurship and Development Institute.
- Acs, Z. J., Szerb, L., Lafuente, E. & Lloyd, A., 2018. *The Global Entrepreneurship Index 2018*, Washington: The Global Entrepreneurship and Development Institute.
- Acs, Z. J., Szerb, L., Lafuente, E. & Markus, G., 2019. *The Global Entrepreneurship Index 2019*, Washington: The Global Entrepreneurship and Development Institute.
- Acs, Z. J., Szerb, L. & Lloyd, A., 2018. *The Global Entrepreneurship Index*, Washington: The Global Entrepreneurship and Development Institute (GEDI).
- Adams, J., Khan, H. T., Raeside, R. & White, D., 2007. *Research methods for graduate business and social science students*. 1st ed. London: Sage Publications Ltd.
- Adamu, L. E., 2015. Repositioning Nigeria University Education for Economic Development through Entrepreneurship Education. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(25), pp. 84-89.
- Adebakin, A. B., Ajadi, O. T. & Subair, S. T., 2015. Required and Possessed University Graduate Employability Skills: Perceptions of the Nigerian Employers. *World Journal of Education*, 5(2), pp. 115-121.
- Adelaja, A. A., 2021. Entrepreneurial education exposure: a comparative investigation between technical and nontechnical higher education. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development (JSBED)*, 28(5), pp. 711-723.
- Adeniyi, O., Ajayi, P. I. & Adedeji, A. A., 2021. Education and Inclusive Growth in West Africa. *Journal of Economics and Development*, 23(2), pp. 163-183.
- Adeosun, O. T. & Shittu, A. I., 2021. Small-Medium Enterprise Formation and Nigerian Economic Growth. *Review of Economics and Political Science (REPS)*, ahead-of-print(ahead-of-print).
- Adesina, O. B., 2011. Organizational and Management Problems Confronting Redesigning Teaching and Learning in Nigerian Schools in the Globalization Era. *Journal of Management and Strategy*, 2(2), pp. 78-86.

- Agasisti, T., 2017. Management of Higher Education Institutions and the Evaluation of their Efficiency and Performance. *Tertiary Education and Management*, 23(3), pp. 187-190.
- Agboola, B. M., 2010. *Entrepreneurial Education in Nigeria Tertiary Institutions and Sustainable Development*, Benin: Department of Educational Studies and Management, Faculty of Education, University of Benin.
- Agbowuro, C., Saidu, S. & Jimwan, C. S., 2017. Creative and Functional Education: The Challenges and Prospects in a Comatose Economy. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 8(8), pp. 37-40.
- Ahmad, N. & Hoffman, A., 2007. *A Framework for Addressing and Measuring Entrepreneurship*, Paris: OECD.
- Ahmad, N. & Seymour, R. G., 2008. *Defining Entrepreneurial Activity: Definitions Supporting Frameworks for Data Collection - OECD Statistics Working Paper*. Paris, Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD).
- Ahsan, M., Zheng, C., DeNoble, A. & Musteen, M., 2018. From Student to Entrepreneur: How Mentorships and Affect Influence Student Venture Launch. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 56(1), p. 76 – 102.
- Ajzen, I., 1991. The Theory of Planned Behaviour. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, Volume 50, pp. 179 - 211.
- Akhuemonkhan, I. A., Raimi, L. & Sofoluwe, A. O., 2013. Entrepreneurship Education and Employment Stimulation in Nigeria. *Afro Asian Journal of Social Sciences*, 4(4), pp. 1-22.
- Akinpelu, Y., 2020. *2019 UTME: Two in three students who applied for admission into Nigerian institutions not admitted*, Lagos: The Premium Times, Nigeria.
- Akinyemi, S. & Ofem, I. B., 2012. Planning and Funding of Higher Education in Nigeria: The Challenges. *International Education Studies*, 5(4), pp. 86-95.
- Akinyemi, S., Ofem, I. B. & Ikuenomore, S. O., 2012b. Graduate Turnout and Graduate Employment in Nigeria. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 2(14), pp. 257-265.
- Al Mamun, A., Fazal, S. A. & Muniady, R., 2019. Entrepreneurial Knowledge, Skills, Competencies and Performance: A study of Micro-Enterprises in Kelantan, Malaysia. *Asia Pacific Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 13(1), pp. 29-48.
- Aladekomo, F. O., 2004. Nigeria Educational Policy and Entrepreneurship. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 9(2), pp. 75-83.
- Alarape, A., 2008. On the Road to Institutionalising Entrepreneurship Education in Nigerian Universities. *International Journal of Management Education*, 7(2), pp. 81 -87.
- Albertini, S. & Muzzi, C., 2016. Institutional entrepreneurship and organizational innovation: The start-up of a divergent new venture at the periphery of a mature field. *The International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation*, 17(2), p. 110–119.
- Alemu, Z. G., 2015. The Challenge of Job Creation in Nigeria. *African Development Bank Group (AfDB) - Africa Economic Brief*, 6(8), pp. 1-16.

- Alvareza, S. A. & Busenitz, L. W., 2001. The Entrepreneurship of Resource-Based Theory. *Journal of Management*, Volume 25, p. 755 – 775.
- Angulo-Guerrero, M. J., Perez-Moreno, S. & Abad-Guerrero, I. M., 2017. How economic freedom affects opportunity and necessity entrepreneurship in the OECD countries. *Journal of Business Research*, 73(Online), p. 30–37.
- Aprilia, G. & Ardana, I. K., 2021. The Influence of Subjective Norms, Locus of Control, and Need for Achievement on Entrepreneurial Intentions. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 5(6), pp. 168-173.
- Arab, Z. & Sofiyabadi, J., 2013. Entrepreneurship Indicators with An Emphasis on Global Entrepreneurship Monitor. *International Journal of Research and Reviews in Applied Sciences*, 16(2), pp. 288-296.
- Aririah, C., 2021. *10 Reasons Why Nigerian Graduates are Unemployed and Unemployable*, Lagos: After School Africa.
- Arruti, A. & Panos-Castro, J., 2020. International Entrepreneurship Education for Pre-Service Teachers: A Longitudinal Study. *Education + Training*, 62(7/8), pp. 825-841.
- Asika, N., 1991. *Research Methodology in the Behavioural Sciences*. 1st ed. Kaduna: Longman Nigeria Plc.
- Asikiya, A. & Boma, I., 2015. Confronting the Challenges in the Education Sector in Nigeria. *IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education (IOSR-JRME)*, 5(4), pp. 37-43.
- Asiyai, R. I., 2013. Challenges of Quality in Higher Education in Nigeria in the 21st Century. *International Journal of Educational Planning & Administration*, 3(2), pp. 159-172.
- Asuquo, A. E. & Agboola, B. M., 2014. Nigerian Universities Outputs and Their Employability in the Labour Markets in South- South, Nigeria. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 2(12), pp. 1244-1249.
- Attahiru, S. I., Olaoyem, M. A., Isyaku, B. & Abubakar, M., 2020. Assessment of Relationship Between Personal Attitude and the Entrepreneurship Intention Among Students in Federal Polytechnic in Northern Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Business*, 3(1), pp. 295-298.
- Aulet, B. & Murray, F., 2013. *A TALE OF TWO ENTREPRENEURS: Understanding Differences in the Types of Entrepreneurship in the Economy*, Kansas: Ewing Marion Kauffman Foundation.
- Awogbenle, A. C. & Iwuamadi, K. C., 2010. Youth Unemployment: Entrepreneurship Development Programme as An Intervention Mechanism. *African Journal of Business Management*, 4(6), pp. 831 - 835.
- Awwad, M. S. & Al-Aseer, R. M. N., 2021. Big Five Personality Traits Impact on Entrepreneurial Intention: The Mediating Role of Entrepreneurial Alertness. *Asia Pacific Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 15(1), pp. 87-100.
- Ayeni, E., Sani, K., Andeshi, C. & Adamu, S., 2020. Job Creation and Youth Empowerment in Nigeria, 2011 – 2020. *Iraqi Journal of Social Sciences*, 2(1), pp. 1-19.

- Ayodotun, S. I., Dumebi, M. & Adebajji, W. A. A. A., 2021. Entrepreneurial Characteristics Amongst University Students: Insights for Understanding Entrepreneurial Intentions Amongst Youths in A Developing Economy. *Education + Training*, 63(1), pp. 71-84.
- Babajide, A. et al., 2020. Financial Stability and Entrepreneurship Development in Sub-Saharan Africa: Implications for Sustainable Development Goals. *Cogent Social Sciences*, 6(1), pp. 1-17.
- Babajide, A. et al., 2021. Financial literacy, financial capabilities, and sustainable business model practice among small business owners in Nigeria. *Journal of Sustainable Finance & Investment*, pp. 1-23.
- Babalobi, B., 2019. *Nigeria: Why graduates are unemployed and unemployable*, Lagos: Vanguard Media Limited, Nigeria.
- Bae, T. J., Qian, S., Miao, C. & Fiet, J. O., 2014. The Relationship Between Entrepreneurship Education and Entrepreneurial Intentions: A Meta-Analytic Review. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, pp. 217 - 254.
- Bakar, R., Islam, M. A. & Lee, J., 2015. Entrepreneurship Education: Experiences in Selected Countries. *International Education Studies*, 8(1), pp. 88-99.
- Bamiro, O. A., 2012. *Tertiary Education in Nigeria and the Challenge of Corporate Governance*. Abuja, TETFund.
- Barton, D., 2019. *Business Population Estimates for the UK and the Regions 2019*, London: National Statistics - Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy.
- Baxter, P. & Jack, S., 2008. Qualitative case study methodology: Study design and implementation for novice researchers. *The Qualitative Report*, 13(4), pp. 544-559.
- Bazkiaei, H. A. et al., 2020. Do Entrepreneurial Education and Big-Five Personality Traits Predict Entrepreneurial Intention Among Universities Students?. *Cogent Business & Management*, 7(1), pp. 1-18.
- Bianchi, A. & Biffignandi, S., 2012. A New Index of Entrepreneurship Measure. *Journal of Marketing Development and Competitiveness*, 6(4), pp. 35-50.
- Blundel, R., Lockett, N. & Wang, C., 2018. *Exploring Entrepreneurship*. 2nd ed. London: SAGE Publications Ltd.
- Bosire, J. & Etyang, M., 2003. The effect of education on business skills cognition: the case of indigenous microscale enterprise owners in Kenya. *Journal of Vocational Education and Training*, 55(1), pp. 5-20.
- Boubker, O., Arroud, M. & Ouajdouni, A., 2021. Entrepreneurship Education Versus Management Students' Entrepreneurial Intentions. A PLS-SEM Approach. *The International Journal of Management Education*, 19(1), pp. 1-14.
- Bragg, S. & Henry, N., 2011. *Order 121 - Study on Support to Indicators on Entrepreneurship Education*, Birmingham: GHK.
- Brush, C. G. et al., 2003. Doctoral Education in the Field of Entrepreneurship. *Journal of Management*, 29(3), p. 309-331.

Budget Office of the Federation - Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2020. *Budget Document - Sub Categories*. [Online] Available at: <https://budgetoffice.gov.ng/index.php/resources/internal-resources/budget-documents> [Accessed 18 June 2020].

Bula, H. O., 2012. Evolution and Theories of Entrepreneurship: A Critical Review on the Kenyan Perspective. *International Journal of Business and Commerce*, 1(11), pp. 81-96.

Bull, I. & Willard, G. E., 1993. Towards a Theory of Entrepreneurship. *Journal of Business Venturing*, Volume 8, pp. 183 - 195.

Burns, P., 2016. *Entrepreneurship and Small Business : Start-Up, Growth and Maturity*. 4th ed. London: Palgrave.

Cacciotti, G. & Hayton, J. C., 2015. Fear and Entrepreneurship: A Review and Research Agenda. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 17(2), p. 165–190.

Cameron, R., 2011. Mixed Methods Research: The Five Ps Framework. *Electronic Journal of Business Research Methods*, 9(2), pp. 96 - 108.

Cameron, R., Sankaran, S. & Scales, J., 2015. Mixed Methods Use in Project Management Research. *Project Management Journal*, 46(2), p. 90–104.

Carswell, P. & Rolland, D., 2007. Religion and entrepreneurship in New Zealand. *Journal of Enterprising Communities: People and Places in the Global Economy*, 1(2), pp. 162-174.

Chen, J., 2006. Development of Chinese small and medium-sized enterprises. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 13(2), pp. 140-147.

Chepurensko, A., 2015. Entrepreneurship Theory: New Challenges and Future Prospects. *Foresight-Russia*, 9(2), p. 44 – 57.

Cho, Y. H. & Lee, J.-H., 2018. Entrepreneurial Orientation, Entrepreneurial Education and Performance. *Asia Pacific Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 12(2), pp. 124-134.

Collis, J. & Hussey, R., 2013. *Business Research: A Practical Guide for Undergraduate & Postgraduate Students*. 4th ed. London: Palgrave Macmillan.

Co, M. J., 2003. A Socio-Cultural Explanation of black Entrepreneurship in South Africa. *South African Journal of Business Management*, 34(4), pp. 35-44.

Costa, S. F., Santos, S. C., Wach, D. & Caetano, A., 2018. Recognizing Opportunities across Campus: The Effects of Cognitive Training and Entrepreneurial Passion on the Business Opportunity Prototype. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 56(1), p. 51 – 75.

Croitoru, A., 2012. A review to a book that is 100 years old - Schumpeter, J.A., 1934 (2008), *The Theory of Economic Development: An Inquiry into Profits, Capital, Credit, Interest and the Business Cycle*, translated from the German by Redvers Opie, New Brunswick (U.S.A). *Journal of Comparative Research in Anthropology and Sociology*, 3(2), pp. 137 - 148.

Dakung, J., Orobia, L., Munene, J. C. & Balunywa, W., 2017. The Role of Entrepreneurship Education in Shaping Entrepreneurial Action of Disabled Students in Nigeria. *Journal of Small Business & Entrepreneurship*, 29(4), pp. 293-311.

- Davis, T., 2008. Understanding Entrepreneurship: Developing Indicators for International Comparisons and Assessments. In: E. Congregado, ed. *Measuring Entrepreneurship: Building a Statistical System*. New York: Springer Science+Business Media, LLC, pp. 39-63.
- Dawson, C., 2002. *Practical Research Methods - A user-friendly guide to mastering research techniques and projects*. 1st ed. Oxford: How To Books Ltd.
- Desai, S., 2009. *Measuring Entrepreneurship in Developing Countries*, Helsinki: The United Nations University World Institute for Development Economics Research (UNU-WIDER).
- Dhar, S. & Farzana, T., 2018. Entrepreneurship Education at Tertiary Level in Bangladesh. *Journal of Economics and Business Research*, 24(2), pp. 97 - 124.
- Diandra, D. & Azmy, A., 2020. Understanding Definition of Entrepreneurship. *International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics*, 7(5), pp. 235-241.
- Dickson, P. H., Solomon, G. T. & Weaver, K. M., 2008. Entrepreneurial Selection and Success: Does Education Matter?. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 15(2), pp. 239-258.
- Dilanchiev, A., 2014. Relationship between Entrepreneurship and Unemployment: The Case of Georgia. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 3(2), pp. 5-9.
- Dragomir, C.-C. & Panzaru, S., 2015. The Relationship Between Education and Entrepreneurship in EU Member States. *Review of General Management*, 22(2), pp. 55 - 65.
- Dvoulety, O., 2018. How to analyse determinants of entrepreneurship and selfemployment at the country level? A methodological contribution. *Journal of Business Venturing Insights*, Volume 9, pp. 92-99.
- Edokpolor, J. E., 2020. Entrepreneurship Education and Sustainable Development: Mediating Role of Entrepreneurial Skills. *Asia Pacific Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 14(3), pp. 329-339.
- Eisenmann, T. R., 2013. *Entrepreneurship: A Working Definition*. [Online] Available at: <https://hbr.org/2013/01/what-is-entrepreneurship> [Accessed 23 February 2018].
- Ekawarna, P. M. et al., 2020. Analyzing the Effect of Need for Achievement and Locus of Control on Student Entrepreneurial Intentions. *Indonesian Research Journal in Education*, 4(1), pp. 28-42.
- Ekesiobi, C. & Dimnwobi, S. K., 2021. Economic assessment of the Igbo entrepreneurship model for entrepreneurial development in Nigeria: evidence from clusters in Anambra state. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*, 27(2), pp. 416-433.
- Eroglu, O. & Picak, M., 2011. Entrepreneurship, National Culture and Turkey. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 2(16), pp. 146-151.
- Esmer, Y. & Dayi, F., 2016. *Entrepreneurial Leadership: A Theoretical Framework*. Paris, International Academic Conference, pp. 112 -124.
- European Commission/EACEA/Eurydice, 2016. *Entrepreneurship Education at School in Europe*, Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.

European Union, 2013. *Entrepreneurship Education: A Guide for Educators*, Brussels: Entrepreneurship 2020 Unit - Directorate-General for Enterprise and Industry European Commission.

Everett, E. H., 1959. Economic Structure and Economic Growth: A Survey of Areas in which Research is Needed. In: W. G. Raymond, ed. *The Comparative Study of Economic Growth and Structure*. Cambridge: National Bureau of Economic Research (NBER), pp. 124 - 141.

Ezeh, P. C., Nkamnebe, A. D. & Omodafe, U. P., 2020. Determinants of Entrepreneurial Intention Among Undergraduates in A Muslim Community. *Management Research Review*, 43(8), pp. 1013-1030.

Ezenyilimba, E., 2015. The Challenges of Tertiary Management Education and Strategic Learning Panacea in Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 5(6), pp. 35-49.

Faloye, D. O. & Olatunji, O. D., 2018. Entrepreneurship Education and Self-employment Intentions among Fresh Graduates in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 9(12), pp. 146-158.

Feldman, M. P., 2014. The Character of Innovative Places: Entrepreneurial Strategy, Economic Development, and Prosperity. *Small Bus Econ*, Volume 43, p. 9–20.

FGN, 2019. *Background of the Nigerian Economy*. [Online] Available at: <http://www.nigeria.gov.ng/index.php/2016-04-06-08-38-30/economy> [Accessed 31 January 2019].

FGN, 2019. *Education: Programs and Initiatives*. [Online] Available at: <http://nigeria.gov.ng/index.php/2016-04-06-08-48-10/programs-initiatives/246-education> [Accessed 17 January 2019].

Fisher, G., 2012. Effectuation, Causation, and Bricolage: A Behavioral Comparison of Emerging Theories in Entrepreneurship Research. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 10(11), pp. 1019 - 1051.

Florczak, K. L., 2014. Purists Need Not Apply: The Case for Pragmatism in Mixed Methods Research. *Nursing Science Quarterly*, 27(4), p. 278–282.

FME, 2005. *Nigeria Education Sector Diagnosis - A Framework for Re-engineering*. Abuja, Education Sector Analysis Unit Federal Ministry of Education.

Francis, O. M. et al., 2019. Vocational Agriculture and Entrepreneurship Aspirations among University Students in Nigeria. *International Journal of Training Research*, 17(3), pp. 220-237.

Franco, M. & Piceti, P., 2020. Family dynamics and gender perspective influencing copreneurship practices: A qualitative analysis in the Brazilian context. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*, 26(1), pp. 14-33.

Frey, R. S., 1983. Does n-Achievement Cause Economic Development? A Cross-Lagged Panel Analysis of the McClelland Thesis. *The Journal of Social Psychology*, 122(1), pp. 67-70.

- Frey, R. S., 1984. Need for Achievement, Entrepreneurship, and Economic Growth: A Critique of the McClelland Thesis. *The Social Science Journal*, 21(2), p. 125–134.
- FRN, 2004. *Federal Republic of Nigeria: National Policy on Education*, Lagos: Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC).
- FRN, 2004. *Federal Republic of Nigeria: National Policy on Education*, Lagos: Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC).
- FRN, 2013. *Federal Republic of Nigeria: National Policy on Education*, Lagos: Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC).
- Fuentelsaz, L., Gonzalez, C., Maicas, J. P. & Montero, J., 2015. How different formal institutions affect opportunity and necessity entrepreneurship. *BRQ Business Research Quarterly*, 18(4), pp. 246-258.
- Gabadeen, W. O. & Raimi, L., 2012. *Management of Entrepreneurship Education in Nigerian Higher Institutions: Issues, Challenges and Way Forward*, Abuja: Abuja International Journal Of Education and Management Sciences,
- Galloway, L., Kapasi, I. & Whittam, G., 2015. Exploring ‘Successful’ Outcomes of Entrepreneurship Education - A Follow-Up Study. *Industry & Higher Education*, 29(6), pp. 1-11.
- Gamlen, A. & McIntyre, C., 2018. Mixing Methods to Explain Emigration Policies: A PostPositivist Perspective. *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 12(4), p. 374 – 393.
- Gartner, W. B. & Baker, T., 2010. A Plausible History and Exploration of Stevenson’s Definition of Entrepreneurship. *Frontiers of Entrepreneurship Research*, 30(4), pp. 1 - 15.
- Garud, R., Gehman, J. & Giuliani, A. P., 2018. Why not take a performative approach to entrepreneurship?. *Journal of Business Venturing Insights*, Volume 9, pp. 60-64.
- Garud, R., Hardy, C. & Maguire, S., 2007. Institutional Entrepreneurship as Embedded Agency: An Introduction to the Special Issue. *Organization Studies*, 28(7), p. 957–969.
- GEDI, 2018. *Global Entrepreneurship Index*. [Online] Available at: <http://thegedi.org/global-entrepreneurship-and-development-index/> [Accessed 29 November 2018].
- GEM, 2012. *GEM Nigeria - Insights For Policy*, London: Global Entrepreneurship Research Association.
- GEM, 2017. *Global Entrepreneurship Monitor: Global Report 2016/2017*, Wellesley: Global Entrepreneurship Research Association (GERA).
- GEM, 2018. *Global Entrepreneurship Monitor: 2017/18 Global Report*, Wellesley: Global Entrepreneurship Research Association (GERA).
- George, I. N. & Ukpong, D. E., 2013. Contemporary Social Problems in Nigeria and its Impact on National Development: Implication for Guidance and Counselling Services. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 3(2), pp. 167-173 .
- Glanz, K., 2020. *Social and Behavioral Theories*, Bethesda: Office of Behavioral & Social Sciences Research.

- Graevenitz, G. v., Harhoff, D. & Weber, R., 2010. The Effects of Entrepreneurship Education. *Journal of Economic Behavior and Organization*, 76(1), pp. 90-119.
- Grant, C. & Osanloo, A., 2014. Understanding, Selecting, and Integrating A Theoretical Framework in Dissertation Research: Creating The Blueprint For Your “House”. *Administrative Issues Journal : Connecting Education, Practice, and Research*, 4(2), pp. 12-26.
- Guercini, S. & Cova, B., 2018. Unconventional entrepreneurship. *Journal of Business Research*, Volume 92, pp. 385-391.
- Guerrero, M., Urbano, D., Cunningham, J. A. & Gajon, E., 2018. Determinants of Graduates’ Start-Ups Creation across a Multi-Campus Entrepreneurial University: The Case of Monterrey Institute of Technology and Higher Education. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 56(1), p. 150 – 178.
- Gupta, G., Mahakud, J. & Verma, V., 2021. CEO’s Education and Investment–Cash Flow Sensitivity: An Empirical Investigation. *International Journal of Managerial Finance*, 17(4), pp. 589-618.
- Haddoud, M. Y., Onjewu, A.-K. E., Nowinski, W. & Alammari, K., 2020. Assessing the Role of Entrepreneurship Education in Regulating Emotions and Fostering Implementation Intention: Evidence from Nigerian Universities. *Studies in Higher Education*, pp. 1-19.
- Hafiz, U. A., Salleh, F. & Garba, M., 2021. A Theoretical Basis for Innovation, Institutions and Insurance Penetration Nexus. *Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal*, 8(3), pp. 61-72.
- Hagg, G. & Gabrielsson, J., 2021. A Systematic Literature Review of the Evolution of Pedagogy in Entrepreneurial Education Research. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*, 25(5), pp. 829-861.
- Hahn, D., Minola, T., Gils, A. V. & Huybrechts, J., 2017. Entrepreneurial Education and Learning at Universities: Exploring Multilevel Contingencies. *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development: An International Journal*, 29(9-10), pp. 945-974.
- Hamdi-Kidar, L. & Vellera, C., 2018. Triggers Entrepreneurship Among Creative Consumers. *Journal of Business Research*, Volume 92, pp. 465-473.
- Hamed, T., 2016. Validity and Reliability of the Research Instrument; How to Test the Validation of a Questionnaire/Survey in a Research. *International Journal of Academic Research in Management IJARM*, 5(3), pp. 28-36.
- Hannon, P. D., 2018. On Becoming and Being An Entrepreneurship Educator: A Personal Reflection. *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development*, 30(7-8), p. 698–721.
- Hansemark, O. C., 1998. The effects of an entrepreneurship programme on Need for Achievement and Locus of Control of reinforcement. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour & Research*, 4(1), pp. 28 - 50.
- Harima, A., Giebelmann, J., Gootsch, V. & Schlichting, L., 2021. Entrepreneurship? Let Us Do It Later: Procrastination in the Intention–Behavior Gap of Student Entrepreneurship. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*, 27(5), pp. 1189-1213.

Hassan, H., Sade, A. B. & Rahman, M. S., 2020. Shaping Entrepreneurial Intention Among Youngsters in Malaysia. *Journal of Humanities and Applied Social Sciences*, 2(3), pp. 235-251.

Hernandez, J. G. V., Osmar, A. P. E. & Rangel, A. C., 2016. A Review of Research Methods in Strategic Management; What Have Been Done, and What is Still Missing. *Journal of Knowledge Management, Economics and Information Technology*, 6(2), pp. 1-42.

Hernandez-Sanchez, B. R., Sanchez-Garcia, J. C. & Mayens, A. W., 2019. Impact of Entrepreneurial Education Programs on Total Entrepreneurial Activity: The Case of Spain. *Administrative Sciences*, 9(25), pp. 2-16.

Iacovidou, M., Gibbs, P. & Zopiatis, A., 2009. An Exploratory Use of the Stakeholder Approach to Defining and Measuring Quality: The Case of a Cypriot Higher Education Institution. *Quality in Higher Education*, 15(2), pp. 147-165.

Idris, F. et al., 2012. The role of education in shaping youth's national identity. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, Volume 59, p. 443 – 450.

Iglesias-Sanchez, P. P., Jambrino-Maldonado, C., Velasco, A. P. & Kokash, H., 2016. Impact of Entrepreneurship Programmes on University Students. *Education + Training*, 58(2), pp. 209 - 228.

Imenda, S., 2014. Is There a Conceptual Difference between Theoretical and Conceptual Frameworks?. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 38(2), pp. 185 - 195.

Imperial College London, 2018. *About GEI*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.imperial.ac.uk/business-school/research/innovation-and-entrepreneurship/ie-research/research-initiatives-and-themes/gedi/about-gedi/> [Accessed 04 December 2018].

Iruonagbe, C. T., Imhonopi, D. & Egharevba, M. E., 2015. Higher Education in Nigeria and the Emergence of Private Universities. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 3(2), pp. 49-64.

IseOlorunkanmi, J. O. et al., 2021. Challenges in Nigeria's Education Sector and the Migration of Nigerian Postgraduate Students to South African universities. *Cogent Social Sciences*, 7(1), pp. 2-19.

Iyortsuun, A. S., Goyit, M. G. & Dakung, R. J., 2020. Entrepreneurship Education Programme, Passion And Attitude Towards Self-Employment. *Journal of Entrepreneurship in Emerging Economies*, 13(1), pp. 64-85.

Jacob, O. N. & Musa, A., 2020. Higher Education in Nigeria: Challenges and the Ways Forward. *Electronic Research Journal of Behavioural Sciences*, Volume 3, pp. 84-98.

Jaja, J. M., 2013. Higher Education in Nigeria: its Gain, its Burden. *Global Journal of Human Social Science Linguistics & Education*, 13(14), pp. 21-29.

Jia, S., 2018. Foreign aid: boosting or hindering entrepreneurship?. *Journal of Entrepreneurship and Public Policy*, 7(3), pp. 248-268.

Jimenez, A. et al., 2015. The impact of educational levels on formal and informal entrepreneurship. *BRQ Business Research Quarterly*, 18(3), pp. 204-212.

- Johnson, R. B. & Onwuegbuzie, A. J., 2004. Mixed Methods Research: A Research Paradigm Whose Time Has Come. *Educational Researcher*, 33(7), p. 14–26.
- Justo, R., De Castro, J. O. & Maydeu-Olivares, A., 2008. Indicators of entrepreneurship activity: some methodological contributions. *Int. J. Entrepreneurship and Small Business*, 6(5), p. 604–621.
- Kabir, S. M. S., 2016. Methods Of Data Collection. In: K. SMS, ed. *Basic Guidelines for Research: An Introductory Approach for All Disciplines*. Chittagong: Book Zone Publication, pp. 201-276.
- Kalafatis, S. P., Pollard, M., East, R. & Tsogas, M. H., 1999. Green Marketing and Ajzen's Theory of Planned Behaviour: A Cross-Market Examination. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 16(5), pp. 441 - 460.
- Khyareh, M. M., 2020. Entrepreneurship and economic growth: the mediation role of access to finance. *e-journal of International Relations*, 11(1), pp. 98-111.
- Kibler, E. & Kautonen, T., 2016. The Moral Legitimacy of Entrepreneurs: An Analysis of Early-Stage Entrepreneurship Across 26 Countries. *International Small Business Journal*, 34(1), p. 34 –50 .
- Kirzner, I. M., 1973. *Competition and Entrepreneurship*. Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press.
- Kivunja, C., 2016. Distinguishing between Theory, Theoretical Framework, and Conceptual Framework: A Systematic Review of Lessons from the Field. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 7(6), pp. 44 - 53.
- Kobe, K. & Schwinn, R., 2018. *Small Business GDP*, Washington: U.S. Small Business Administration.
- Koe, W.-L., 2016. The relationship between Individual Entrepreneurial Orientation (IEO) and Entrepreneurial Intention. *Journal of Global Entrepreneurship Research*, 6(13), pp. 2-11.
- Koe, W.-L., 2016. The Relationship between Individual Entrepreneurial Orientation (IEO) and Entrepreneurial Intention. *Journal of Global Entrepreneurship Research*, 6(13), pp. 2-11.
- Kolstad, I. & Wiig, A., 2015. Education and entrepreneurial success. *Small Bus Econ*, Volume 44, p. 783–796.
- Kothari, C. R., 2004. *Research Methodology: Methods and Techniques*. 2nd ed. Daryaganj: New Age International (P) Limited.
- Kumar, S. & Ahmad, S., 2008. *Meaning, Aims and Process of Education*, Delhi: University of Delhi Press..
- Kuratko, D. F., 2007. Entrepreneurial Leadership in the 21st Century - Guest Editor's Perspective. *Journal of Leadership and Organizational Studies*, 13(4), pp. 1-11.
- Kuratko, D. F. & Morris, M. H., 2018. Examining the Future Trajectory of Entrepreneurship. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 56(1), p. 11 – 23.

- Kurczewska, A. & Mackiewicz, M., 2020. Are Jacks-of-All-Trades Successful Entrepreneurs? Revisiting Lazear's Theory of Entrepreneurship. *Baltic Journal of Management*, 15(3), pp. 411-430.
- Lackeus, M., 2015. *Entrepreneurship in Education: What, Why, When, How*, Paris: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD).
- Lawal, S. M., 2013. Entrepreneurship Education at Tertiary Education Level: Implication to Historical Studies. *International Journal of Education & Literacy Studies*, 1(1), pp. 33-37.
- Lee, Y. S. & Eesley, C., 2018. The persistence of entrepreneurship and innovative immigrants. *Research Policy*, 47(6), pp. 1032-1044.
- Leppaaho.Tanja, Chetty, S. & Dimitratos, P., 2018. Network Embeddedness in the Internationalization of Biotechnology Entrepreneurs. *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development*, 30(5-6), p. 562-584 .
- Liao, L., D. M., Wang, B. & Yu, Y., 2019. The Impact of Educational Investment on Sustainable Economic Growth in Guangdong, China: A Cointegration and Causality Analysis. *Sustainability*, 11(3), pp. 1-16.
- Lohnan, N. N., 2019. Challenges to Educational Quality in Nigeria. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Development, Education and Science Research (IJEDES)*, 5(1), pp. 116-126.
- London Business School, 2018. *What is the National Expert Survey (NES)?*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.gemconsortium.org/wiki/1142> [Accessed 05 December 2018].
- Longva, K. K., Strand, O. & Pasquine, M., 2020. Entrepreneurship Education as An Arena for Career Reflection: The Shift of Students' Career Preferences After A Business Planning Course. *Education + Training*, 62(7/8), pp. 877-896.
- Lux, A. A., Macau, F. R. & Brown, K. A., 2020. Putting the Entrepreneur Back into Entrepreneurial Ecosystems. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*, 26(5), pp. 1011-1041.
- Machado, H. P. V., Gaiotto, S. A. V. & Machado, M. C. R., 2021. Growth and Social Entrepreneurs: The Challenge of Conciliating Economic and Social Values. *Revista de Gestao*, 28(1), pp. 2-22.
- Marcotte, C., 2013. Measuring entrepreneurship at the country level: A review and research agenda. *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development*, 3(4), pp. 174-194.
- Marquez-Ramos, L. & Mourelle, E., 2019. Education and Economic Growth: an Empirical Analysis of Nonlinearities. *Applied Economic Analysis*, 27(79), pp. 21-45.
- Matlay, H. & Carey, C., 2007. Entrepreneurship Education in the Uk: A Longitudinal Perspective. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 14(2), pp. 252 - 263.
- Mattare, M., 2010. Use of Self 101: The Case for Teaching Personal Development in the Entrepreneurship Curriculum. *New England Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 13(1), pp. 17-28.

- Mbah, S. & Okeke, G., 2020. Entrepreneurship Education and Youth Empowerment in Selected States in South-East, Nigeria. *Unizik Journal of Business*, 3(1), pp. 15-25.
- Mbulawa, S. & Mehta, P., 2016. The Effect of Access and Quality of Education on Economic Development in Botswana. *International Journal of Business, Economics and Management*, 3(11), pp. 144-159.
- McClelland, D. C., 1961. *The Achieving Society*. London: D Van Nostrand Company, Ltd.
- McElwee, G., Smith, R. & Somerville, P., 2018. Conceptualising Animation in Rural Communities: The Village SOS Case. *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development: An International Journal*, 30(1-2), p. 173–198.
- Mehmood, T., Alzoubi Haitham, M., Alshurideh, M. & Al-Gasaymeh, A., 2019. Schumpeterian Entrepreneurship Theory: Evolution and Relevance. *Academy of Entrepreneurship Journal*, 25(4), pp. 1 - 10.
- Miller, P. J. & Cameron, R., 2011. Mixed Method Research Designs: A Case Study of Their Adoption in A Doctor of Business Administration Program. *International Journal of Multiple Research Approaches*, 5(3), p. 387 – 402.
- Mirjana, P. B., Ana, A. & Marjana, M.-S., 2018. Examining Determinants of Entrepreneurial Intentions in Slovenia: Applying the Theory of Planned Behaviour and An Innovative Cognitive Style. *Economic Research-Ekonomska Istrazivanja*, 31(1), pp. 1453-1471.
- Mishra, C. S. & Zachary, R. K., 2014. *The Theory of Entrepreneurship*. 1st ed. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Mohajan, H. K., 2017. Two Criteria for Good Measurements in Research: Validity and Reliability. *Annals of Spiru Haret University*, 17(3), pp. 58-82.
- Morgan, D. L., 2019. Commentary - After Triangulation, What Next?. *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 13(1), pp. 6 - 14.
- Morgan, J. & Sisak, D., 2016. Aspiring to succeed: A model of entrepreneurship and fear of failure. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 31(1), pp. 1-21.
- Morrison, A., 2000. Entrepreneurship: what triggers it?. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*, 6(2), pp. 59-71.
- Morselli, D., 2018. Teaching A Sense of Initiative and Entrepreneurship with Constructive Alignment in Tertiary Non-Business Contexts. *Education + Training*, 60(2), pp. 122-138.
- Mrozewski, M. & Kratzer, J., 2017. Entrepreneurship and Country-Level Innovation: Investigating the Role of Entrepreneurial Opportunities. *The Journal of Technology Transfer*, 42(5), p. 1125–1142.
- Munir, K. & Kanwal, A., 2020. Impact of Educational and Gender Inequality on Income and Income Inequality in South Asian Countries. *International Journal of Social Economics*, 48(8), pp. 1043-1062.
- Naminse, E. Y., Zhuang, J. & Zhu, F., 2019. The Relation between Entrepreneurship and Rural Poverty Alleviation in China. *Management Decision*, 57(9), pp. 2593-2611.
- NBS, December 2018. *Labor Force Statistics - Volume I: Unemployment and Underemployment Report (Q4 2017-Q3 2018)*, Abuja: National Bureau of Statistics (NBS).

NBS, 2018. *Nigerian Gross Domestic Product Report - (Q3 2018)*, Abuja: National Bureau of Statistics .

NBTE, 2007. *Standards and Creteria for Approval of Programmes in Vocational Enterprise Institutions (VEIs) & Innovation Enterprise Institutions (IEIs) Programmes*, Kaduna: National Board for Technical Education (NBTE).

NBTE, 2017. *Digest of Statistics of Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) Institutions in Nigeria: 2014/2015*, Kaduna: National Board for Technical Education (NBTE).

NBTE, 2019. *National Board for Technical Education: TVET Institutions*. [Online] Available at: <https://net.nbte.gov.ng/Federal%20Polytechnics> [Accessed 14 January 2019].

NBTE, 2020. *APPROVED AND ACCREDITED COLLEGES OF AGRICULTURE*. [Online] Available at: <https://net.nbte.gov.ng/colleges%20of%20agric> [Accessed 15 June 2020].

NBTE, 2020. *APPROVED AND ACCREDITED SPECIALISED INSTITUTIONS AS AT APRIL 2019*. [Online] Available at: <https://net.nbte.gov.ng/specialised%20institutions> [Accessed 15 June 2020].

NBTE, 2020. *APPROVED PUBLIC COLLEGES OF HEALTH SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY*. [Online] Available at: <https://net.nbte.gov.ng/public%20colleges%20of%20health> [Accessed 15 June 2020].

NBTE, 2021. *Approved and Accredited Private, State Government and Federal Government Polytechnics as at April 2021*. [Online] Available at: <https://net.nbte.gov.ng/private%20polytechnics> [Accessed 10 June 2021].

NBTE, 2021. *Approved and Accredited Vocational Enterprise Institutions (VEIs)*. [Online] Available at: <https://net.nbte.gov.ng/VEI> [Accessed 14 August 2021].

NBTE, 2021. *APPROVED AND ACCREDITED VOCATIONAL ENTERPRISE INSTITUTIONS (VEIs)*. [Online] Available at: <https://net.nbte.gov.ng/technical%20colleges> [Accessed 10 August 2021].

NBTE, 2021. *APPROVED FEDERAL POLYTECHNICS*. [Online] Available at: <https://net.nbte.gov.ng/state%20polytechnics> [Accessed 14 August 2021].

NBTE, 2021. *APPROVED INNOVATION ENTERPRISE INSTITUTIONS AS AT NOVEMBER 2019*. [Online] Available at: <https://net.nbte.gov.ng/IEIs> [Accessed 14 August 2021].

Ndofirepi, T. M., 2020. Relationship between Entrepreneurship Education and Entrepreneurial Goal Intentions: Psychological Traits As Mediators. *Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 9(2), pp. 1-20.

NESG, 2020. *Growing an Inclusive Economy: Job Creation and Nigeria's Future*, Abuja: NESG Research & Development .

Neuman, W. L., 2014. *Social Research Methods: Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches*. 7th ed. Harlow: Pearson Education Limited.

NUC, 2018. *Nigerian University System Statistical Digest - 2017*, Abuja: National Universities Commission.

NUC, 2019. *Nigerian Universities*. [Online] Available at: <https://nuc.edu.ng/nigerian-universities/federal-universities/#> [Accessed 14 January 2019].

NUC, 2021. *List of Approved Universities in Nigeria as at April 2021*, Abuja: National Universities Commission (NUC).

Nwambam, A. S., Nnennaya, O. O. & Nwankpu, I. S., 2018. Evaluating the Entrepreneurship Education Programme in Nigerian Universities for Sustainable Development. *Journal of Entrepreneurship Education*, 21(1), pp. 1-13.

Nwekeaku, C., 2013. Entrepreneurship Education and Challenges to Nigerian Universities. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 4(3), pp. 51-56.

Nwosu, J. C. & Chukwudi, J. H., 2018. Entrepreneurship Education and the Challenges of Graduate Employability in Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovation, Management and Technology*, 9(5), pp. 189-193.

Ocampo, E., 2021. *Capitalism, Populism and Democracy: Revisiting Samuelson's Reformulation of Schumpeter*, Buenos: Universidad del CEMA.

Odeleye, D. A., 2009. *Repositioning Nigeria's Education for Relevance in the 21st Century*. Ibadan, College Press & Publishers, pp. 330-355.

Odia, L. O. & Omofonmwan, S. I., 2018. Educational System in Nigeria Problems and Prospects. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 14(1), pp. 86-95.

Odumosu, A. A., Binuyo, A. O., Adefulu, A. D. & Asikhia, O. U., 2020. Social Innovation and Graduate Entrepreneurship in Nigeria. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)* , 22(2), pp. 48-55.

OECD, 2008. *Measuring Entrepreneurship: A digest of indicators*, Paris: OECD-Eurostat Entrepreneurship Indicators Program.

OECD, 2015. *United States Policy Brief on Entrepreneurship: Improving SME Financing for Stronger Growth and Job Creation*, Paris: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD).

OECD, 2017. *Entrepreneurship at a Glance 2017*, Paris: OECD Publishing.

Ofem, I. B., Akinyemi, S. & Ikuenomore, S. O., 2012. Graduate Turnout and Graduate Employment in Nigeria. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 2(14), pp. 257-265.

- Ofoegbu, G. N., Okaro, S. C. & Okafor, G. O., 2018. Suitability, Challenges and Way Forward for University Accounting Education in Nigeria. *International Journal of Management Education*, 16(3), pp. 394-404.
- Oguntimehin, Y. A. & Olaniran, O. O., 2017. The Relationship between Entrepreneurship Education and Students' Entrepreneurial Intentions in Ogun State-Owned Universities, Nigeria. *British Journal of Education*, 5(3), pp. 9-20.
- Ojeifo, S. A., 2012. Entrepreneurship Education In Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 3(14), pp. 78-82.
- Ojha, A. K. & Rao, R. A., 2017. The Emergence of an Organizational Field: The Case of Open Source Software. *Vikalpa*, 39(2), pp. 127-143.
- Okeke, F. C. & Edikpa, E. C., 2014. Entrepreneurship Education in Nigeria: Prospects, Challenges and Strategies. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Research Development*, 22(2), pp. 1-11.
- Okeremi, A., Amoako-Gyampah, K. & Caesar, L. D., 2021. Exploring the Antecedents of Entrepreneurship Success in Information Technology Firms in Nigeria. *Africa Journal of Management*, 7(2), pp. 286-313.
- Okoli, N. J., Ogbondah, L. & Ewor, R. N., 2016. The History and Development of Public Universities in Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Evaluation*, 2(1), pp. 60-76.
- Okoroma, N., 2006. Educational Policies and Problems of Implementation in Nigeria. *Australian Journal of Adult Learning*, 46(2), pp. 244-263.
- Olaore, G. O., Adejare, B. O. & Udofia, E. E., 2021. The Gains and Pains of Small and Medium-Scale Enterprises (SMES): The Way Forward for Entrepreneurship Development in Nigeria. *Rajagiri Management Journal*, 15(1), pp. 53-68.
- Olibie, E. I., Eziuzo, G. O. & Enueme, C. P., 2018. Inequalities in Nigerian Education Sector: Some Perspectives for Improvement. *IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education (IOSR-JRME)*, 3(6), pp. 07-14.
- Olofinyehun, A. O., Adelowo, C. M. & Egbetokun, A. A., 2018. The Supply of High-Quality Entrepreneurs in Developing Countries: Evidence from Nigeria. *Science and Public Policy*, 45(2), p. 269-282.
- Olorundare, A. S. & Kayode, D. J., 2014. Entrepreneurship Education in Nigerian Universities: A Tool for National Transformation. *Asia Pacific Journal of Educators and Education*, Volume 29, p. 155-175.
- Olusola, A. A., Oluranti, A. S. & Ibrahim, T. U., 2017. Prospects and Challenges of Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria, Way Forward. *Counselling and Behavioural Studies Journal*, 7(1), pp. 1-9.
- Olutuase, S. O., Brijlal, P. & Yan, B., 2020. Model for Stimulating Entrepreneurial Skills Through Entrepreneurship Education in An African Context. *Journal of Small Business & Entrepreneurship*, pp. 1-21.
- Omoniwa, O. B. & Adedapo, A. A., 2017. Assessing Nigerian Graduate Employability. *Global Journal of Business Disciplines*, 1(2), pp. 58-75.

- Orji, K. E. & Job, M., 2013. The Role of Education in National Development: Nigerian Experience. *European Scientific Journal*, 9(28), pp. 312-320.
- Otache, I., 2019. Enhancing the Effectiveness of Entrepreneurship Education: The Role of Entrepreneurial Lecturers. *Education + Training*, 61(7/8), pp. 918-939.
- Otonko, J., 2012. University Education in Nigeria: History, Successes, Failures and the Way Forward. *International Journal of Technology and Inclusive Education*, 1(2), pp. 44-48.
- Owualah, S. I. & Obokoh, L. O., 2008. Tackling Youth Restiveness in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria through Entrepreneurship. *Journal of Enterprising Communities: People and Places in the Global Economy*, 2(2), pp. 168 - 179.
- Pacheco, D. F., York, J. G., Dean, T. J. & Sarasvathy, S. D., 2010. The Coevolution of Institutional Entrepreneurship: A Tale of Two Theories. *Journal of Management*, 36(4), pp. 974-1010.
- Packard, M. D., 2017. Where did interpretivism go in the theory of entrepreneurship?. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 32(5), pp. 536-549.
- Peters, R. M. & Brijlal, P., 2011. The Relationship between Levels of Education of Entrepreneurs and their Business Success: A Study of the Province of KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. *Industry & Higher Education*, 25(4), p. 265 – 275.
- Piano, N., 2020. Neoliberalism, Leadership, and Democracy: Schumpeter on “Schumpeterian” Theories of Entrepreneurship. *European Journal of Political Theory*, 0(0), pp. 1-23.
- Pietak, L., 2014. Review of Theories and Models of Economic Growth. *Comparative Economic Research*, 17(1), pp. 45 - 60.
- Pietak, L., 2014. Review of Theories and Models of Economic Growth. *Comparative Economic Research*, 17(1), pp. 45 - 60.
- Pinsonneault, A. & Kraemer, K. L., 1993. Survey Research Methodology in Management Information Systems: An Assessment. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 10(2), pp. 75 - 105.
- QAA, 2018. *Enterprise and Entrepreneurship Education: Guidance for UK Higher Education Providers*, Gloucester: The Quality Assurance Agency for Higher Education.
- Quinlan, C., 2011. *Business Research Methods*. Andover: Thomas Rennie.
- Rahi, S., 2017. Research Design and Methods: A Systematic Review of Research Paradigms, Sampling Issues and Instruments Development. *International Journal of Economics & Management Sciences*, 6(2), pp. 1 - 5.
- Rahman, M. & Fatima, N., 2011. Entrepreneurship and Urban Growth: Dimensions and Empirical Models. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 18(3), pp. 608-626.
- Raposo, M. & do-Paço, A., 2011. Entrepreneurship education: Relationship between education and entrepreneurial activity. *Psicothema*, 23(3), pp. 453 - 457.
- Reynolds, P. D. et al., 2001. *Global Entrepreneurship Monitor: 2001 Executive Report*, Wellesley: GEM.

- Ribeiro-Soriano, D., 2017. Small Business and Entrepreneurship: Their Role in Economic and Social Development. *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development*, 29(1 - 2), pp. 1 - 3.
- Sahara, 2019. *About 2 Million Nigerian Students Sought University Admission, Less Than 500,000 Successful -Report*, New York: Sahara Reporters.
- Saint, W., Hartnett, T. A. & Strassner, E., 2003. Higher Education in Nigeria: A Status Report. *Published in Higher Education Policy*, Volume 16, pp. 259-281.
- Salgur, S. A., 2013. The Importance of Education in Economic Growth. *Euromentor Journal*, iv(4), pp. 50-57.
- Sanchez, J. C., Ward, A., Hernandez, B. & Florez, J., 2017. Entrepreneurship Education: State of the Art. *Propósitos y Representaciones*, 5(2), pp. 401 - 473.
- Sanchez, J. C., Ward, A., Hernandez, B. & Florez, J., 2017. Entrepreneurship Education: State of the Art. *Propósitos y Representaciones*, 5(2), pp. 401 - 473.
- Sánchez, J. C., Ward, A., Hernández, B. & Florez, J., 2017. Entrepreneurship Education: State of the Art. *Propósitos y Representaciones*, 5(2), pp. 401 - 473.
- Sanusi, I. T., Olaleye, S. A. & Atjonen, P., 2017. Assessment of Innovative Entrepreneurship Education in Nigerian Tertiary Institutions. *Journal of Entrepreneurship Education*, 20(2), pp. 7 - 29.
- Saunders, M. & Lewis, P., 2012. *Doing Research in Business & Management: An Essential Guide to Planning Your Project*. 1st ed. Harlow: Pearson Education Limited.
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P. & Thornhill, A., 2016. *Research Methods for Business Students*. 7th ed. Harlow: Pearson Education Limited.
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P. & Thornhill, A., 2016. *Research Methods for Business Students*. 7th ed. Harlow: Pearson Education Limited.
- Saunders, M. N. K., Lewis, P. & Thornhill, A., 2019. *Research Methods for Business Students*. 8th ed. Harlow: Pearson Education Limited.
- Schramm, C. J., 2017. *Entrepreneurship in American Higher Education*, Kansas: Kauffman: The Foundation of Entrepreneurship .
- Schumpeter, J. A., 1943. *Capitalism, Socialism and Democracy with a new Introduction by Richard Swedberg (2003)*. e-Library ed. London and New York: Taylor & Francis.
- Scotland, J., 2012. Exploring the Philosophical Underpinnings of Research: Relating Ontology and Epistemology to the Methodology and Methods of the Scientific, Interpretive, and Critical Research Paradigms. *English Language Teaching*, 5(9), pp. 9 - 16.
- Sherkatand, A. & Chenari, A., 2020. Assessing the Effectiveness of Entrepreneurship Education in the Universities of Tehran Province Based on An Entrepreneurial Intention Model. *Studies in Higher Education*, pp. 1-19.
- Simon-Moya, V., Revuelto-Taboada, L. & Ribeiro-Soriano, D., 2016. Influence of Economic Crisis on New SME Survival: Reality or Fiction?. *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development*, 28(1 - 2), pp. 157 - 176.

- Simpeh, K. N., 2011. Entrepreneurship Theories and Empirical Research: A Summary Review of the Literature. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 3(6), pp. 1-8.
- Sofoluwe, A. O., Shokunbi, M. O., Raimi, L. & Ajewole, T., 2013. Entrepreneurship Education as a Strategy for boosting Human Capital Development and Employability in Nigeria: Issues, Prospects, Challenges and Solutions. *Journal of Business Administration and Education*, 3(1), pp. 25-50.
- Sojdrova, M., 2015. *Motion for a European Parliament Resolution: On Promoting Youth Entrepreneurship Through Education and Training*, Brussels: European Parliament.
- Sommer, L., 2011. The Theory Of Planned Behaviour And The Impact Of Past Behaviour. *International Business & Economics Research Journal*, 10(1), pp. 91-110.
- Stam, E. & Stel, A. v., 2011. *Types of Entrepreneurship and Economic Growth*. Maastricht, United Nations University - Maastricht Economic and social Research and training centre, pp. 78-95.
- Statista, 2018. *Nigeria: Unemployment rate from 2007 to 2017*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/382366/unemployment-rate-in-nigeria/> [Accessed 10 April 2018].
- Stenholm, P., Acs, Z. J. & Wuebker, R., 2013. Exploring country-level institutional arrangements on the rate and type of entrepreneurial activity. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 28(1), pp. 176-193.
- Stevenson, H. H., 1983. A Perspective on Entrepreneurship. *Harvard Business School Working Paper*, Issue 9, pp. 384 - 131.
- Storen, L. A., 2014. Entrepreneurship in Higher Education: Impacts on Graduates' Entrepreneurial Intentions, Activity and Learning Outcome. *Education + Training*, 56(8/9), pp. 795 - 813.
- Stutely, R., 2003. *The Economist Numbers Guide: The Essentials of Business Numeracy*. 5th ed. London: Profile Books Ltd.
- Stutern, 2016. *Nigeria Graduate Report*, Lagos: Stutern.
- Taatila, V. P., 2010. Learning Entrepreneurship in Higher Education. *Education + Training*, 52(1), pp. 48 - 61.
- Taherdoost, H., 2016. Sampling Methods in Research Methodology; How to Choose a Sampling Technique for Research. *International Journal of Academic Research in Management (IJARM)*, 5(2), pp. 18-27.
- Tam, M., 2001. Measuring Quality and Performance in Higher Education. *Quality in Higher Education*, 7(1), pp. 47-54.
- Tawney, R. H., 1930. Foreword. In: *The Protestant Ethic and The Spirit of Capitalism*. London: George Allen & Unwin Ltd, pp. 1-12.
- Tetrevova, L. & Vlckova, V., 2018. Benefits, limitations and measures concerning the development of cooperation between higher education institutions and external entities. *Tertiary Education and Management*, 24(4), p. 377-394.

- Thai, M. T. T. & Turkina, E., 2014. Macro-level determinants of formal entrepreneurship versus informal entrepreneurship. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 29(4), p. 490–510.
- Thanawala, K., 1994. Schumpeter's Theory Of Economic Development and Development Economics. *Review of Social Economy*, 52(4), pp. 353 - 363.
- Turner, T. & Gianiodis, P., 2018. Entrepreneurship Unleashed: Understanding Entrepreneurial Education outside of the Business School. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 56(1), p. 131 – 149.
- Udefuna, P. N., Akalefu, C. & Asogwa, C., 2013. Entrepreneurship Education and Economic Development in Nigeria: Policy Issues and Options. *Industry and Higher Education*, 27(2), pp. 343 - 348.
- Udey, F. U., Ebuara, V. O., Ekpoh, U. I. & Edet, A. O., 2009. *Management and Administration of Nigerian Education System: Problems, Challenges, and the Way Forward*. Cape Town, International Conference of Educational Management Association of South Africa (EMASA).
- Umar, S. M. & Hassan, T., 2020. Development and Validation of Entrepreneurship Education Interest Inventory (EEII) for Colleges of Education in North Eastern Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Development*, 9(7).
- Ungureanu, A. V., 2020. Entrepreneurship in the New Global Economy - The Role of Innovation in Economic Development. *"Ovidius" University Annals, Economic Sciences Series*, 10(1), pp. 541-548.
- Uprichard, E. & Dawney, L., 2019. Data Diffraction: Challenging Data Integration in Mixed Methods Research. *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, 13(1), pp. 19 - 32.
- Urdana, T. & Kaplanb, A., 2020. The Origins, Evolution, and Future Directions of Achievement Goal Theory. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, Volume 61, pp. 1-10.
- Vakili, F., Tahmasebi, N., Tahmasebi, S. & Tahmasebi, D., 2019. Role of Education in Entrepreneurship Development. *Journal of Ecophysiology & Occupational Health*, 3(4), p. 78–87.
- Veeraraghavan, V., 2009. Entrepreneurship and Innovation. *Asia-Pacific Business Review*, 5(1), pp. 14-20.
- Veiderpass, A. & McKelvey, M., 2016. Evaluating the performance of higher education institutions in Europe: a nonparametric efficiency analysis of 944 institutions. *Applied Economics*, 48(16), pp. 1504-1514.
- Vicens, G. R., Casanovas, L. V.-l., Canals, C. S. & Serra, L., 2021. Entrepreneurship Analysis in Spanish Universities. *Higher Education, Skills and Work-Based Learning*, ahead-of-print(ahead-of-print).
- Volkman, C. et al., 2009. *Educating the Next Wave of Entrepreneurs - Unlocking Entrepreneurial Capabilities to Meet the Global Challenges of the 21st Century*, Switzerland: World Economic Forum.
- Volkman, C. et al., 2009. *Educating the Next Wave of Entrepreneurs - Unlocking Entrepreneurial Capabilities to Meet the Global Challenges of the 21st Century*, Switzerland: World Economic Forum - A Report of the Global Education Initiative.

- Wacker, J. G., 1998. A definition of theory: research guidelines for different theory-building research methods in operations management. *Journal of Operations Management*, Volume 16, p. 361 – 385.
- Walliman, N., 2011. *Research Methods: The Basics*. 1st ed. Oxon: Routledge.
- Walter, S. G. & Block, J. H., 2016. Outcomes of entrepreneurship education: An institutional perspective. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 31(2), p. 216–233.
- Weber, M., 1930. *The Protestant Ethic and the Spirit of Capitalism, With an introduction by Anthony Giddens*. 1st ed. London and New York: Taylor & Francis e-Library.
- Welter, F., Baker, T., Audretsch, D. B. & Gartner, W. B., 2016. Everyday Entrepreneurship - A Call for Entrepreneurship Research to Embrace Entrepreneurial Diversity. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 41(3), pp. 311-321.
- Wennekers, A. R. M., 2006. *Entrepreneurship at Country Level: Economic and Non-Economic Determinants*. ERIM Ph.D. Series Research in Management, 81 ed. Rotterdam: Erasmus Research Institute of Management (ERIM).
- Wolfe, M. T. & Patel, P. C., 2018. Satisfaction guaranteed? Life satisfaction, institutional factors, and self-employment. *Journal of Business Venturing Insights*, Volume 9, pp. 45-52.
- World Bank Group, 2019. *Doing Business 2019 - Economy Profile of Nigeria*, Washington: World Bank Group.
- World Bank Group, 2019. *Doing Business 2019 - Economy Profile of Nigeria*, Washington: World Bank Group.
- Wu, S., Matthews, L. & Dagher, G. K., 2007. Need for Achievement, Business Goals, and Entrepreneurial Persistence. *Management Research News*, 30(12), pp. 928 - 941.
- Yahya, H. U., 2011. *Why We Set Up Entrepreneurship Studies in Varsities – FG*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.thenigerianvoice.com/news/45849/why-we-set-up-entrepreneurship-studies-in-varsities-8211.html> [Accessed 10 July 2021].
- Yan, W., 2019. *APEC 2018 Report on Education and Economic Development - Inclusive and Quality Education: Embracing Digital Future*, Singapore: APEC Secretariat.
- Yasin, N. & Khansari, Z., 2020. Evaluating the Impact of Social Enterprise Education on Students' Enterprising Characteristics in the United Arab Emirates. *Education + Training*, 63 (6), pp. 872-905.
- Yatu, L., Bell, R. & Loon, M., 2016. Entrepreneurship Education Research in Nigeria: Current Foci and Future Research Agendas. *African Journal of Economic and Management Studies*, pp. 1 - 17.
- Yatu, L., Bell, R. & Loon, M., 2018. Entrepreneurship Education Research in Nigeria: Current Foci and Future Research Agendas. *African Journal of Economic and Management Studies*, 9(2), pp. 165-177.
- Yiming, G., 2019. *Gov't should support SMEs to stabilize jobs: NPC deputy*, Beijing: China.org.cn.

Yin, R. K., 2014. *Case Study Research - Design and Methods*. 5th ed. London: SAGE Publications Ltd.

Young, R. M., Prentice, G. R. & McLaughlin, C. G., 2013. Prisoner Intentions to Participate in An Electronic Monitoring Scheme: An Application of the Theory of Planned Behaviour. *Journal of Criminal Psychology*, 3(2), pp. 108 - 114.

Zhou, M. & Xu, H., 2012. A Review of Entrepreneurship Education for College Students. *Administrative Science*, 2(1), pp. 82 - 98.

APPENDICES

Appendix One: Ethical Approval Letter

25/05/2021

Dear Adewuyi Samuel Akinola,

Your application 12029: INVESTIGATING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TERTIARY EDUCATION AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN NIGERIA, submission 13691, has been approved by the Business and Creative Industries SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr John Quinn

Appendix Two: Sample of Invitation Letter to Pilot and Answer Survey

11th February 2020
Adewuyi Samuel Akinola
UWS London Campus
235 Southwark Bridge Road
London, SE1 6NP
United Kingdom

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

Invitation to Pilot and Answer Survey

I, the undersigned is a Doctoral of Business Administration research student in the School of Business and Enterprise at the University of the West of Scotland, United Kingdom. I am researching the relationship between tertiary education and entrepreneurship in Nigeria under the supervision of Dr Khalid Bichou. Your expertise revealed a lot that will help the efficiency future of this study as well as smooth out difficulties before administering the main survey. Therefore, I am specially inviting you to answer and make comments as seen necessary on all questions raised toward achieving the set objectives of this research.

This questionnaire will require approximately 10 minutes to complete. There is no compensation for responding nor is there any known risk. Please, as you choose to participate in this project, kindly attach it back to [REDACTED]

Thank you for supporting me in my educational endeavours.

Yours sincerely

Adewuyi Samuel Akinola

[REDACTED]

Appendix Three: Sample of Questionnaire

DOCTORATE OF BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION (DBA)'S
THESIS QUESTIONNAIRE

INVESTIGATING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN
TERTIARY EDUCATION AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN
NIGERIA

BY

ADEWUYI SAMUEL AKINOLA
B00333357

Questionnaires

Please, kindly answer the followings questions. Questions designed to know how you become an entrepreneur (vocational/innovation institution proprietor), your organisation, training you offer, your graduate and some environmental factors that influence your organisation in Nigeria. It consists of 24 questions and will not take longer than 10 minutes to be complete. All responses will be kept anonymous, and you will not be identified in the research.

1. Do you see yourself as an entrepreneur?

- Yes
 No

2. Are you an entrepreneur as a result of your tertiary education?

- Yes
 No

3. Do you provide vocational/innovation training?

- Yes
 No

- Between 10 to 49
 Between 50 to 199
 Above 100

8. How often do you have tertiary institution graduate positions vacant in your organisation?

- Always
 Usually
 Sometimes
 Rarely
 Never

9. How important do you see an act of creating a business venture in Nigeria?

- Extremely important
 Very important
 Somewhat important
 Not so important
 Not at all important

10. To what extent do you think Nigerian regulatory bodies support business start-ups?

- Extremely helpful
 Very helpful
 Somewhat helpful
 Not so helpful
 Not at all helpful

11. How do you rate each of the followings as an obstacle to a start-up business in Nigeria?

	Very poor	Poor	Okay	Good	Very good	N/A
Lack of skill	<input type="radio"/>					

4. What is the major programme/course of training you are providing?

- Innovative agriculture
 Banking operations
 Building construction
 Computer software engineering
 Shipping management
 Hospitality and tourism studies
 Entrepreneurship capacity building
 Computer studies
 Information technology
 Micro computer maintenance

Others; please specify

5. Do you see the programme you provide as a platform for students to become entrepreneurs?

- Yes
 No

6. How often do you see your graduate established their own business venture as a result of their acquired skill?

- Never
 Rarely
 Sometimes
 Usually
 Always

7. What is the number of your employees?

- Less than 10

Lack of resources

Lack of regulation	<input type="radio"/>					
--------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

Lack of electricity

Lack of opportunity	<input type="radio"/>					
---------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

Lack of internet	<input type="radio"/>					
------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

Lack of good road	<input type="radio"/>					
-------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

12. Did your course of study help you in start-up a business?

- Yes
 No

13. Do you ever see Nigeria tertiary institution graduates as your major competitor in your sector?

- Always
 Usually
 Sometimes
 Rarely
 Never

14. How frequently do you receive job applications from recent graduates?

- Always
 Usually
 Sometimes
 Rarely
 Never

15. Do you agree with the following statement: Nigeria is an

entrepreneurial nation as a result of tertiary institution graduates creating a business venture.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

16. Please rate how much your tertiary education has contributed to your business start-up.

Very poor	Poor	Fair	Good	Very good	Excellent	Exceptional
<input type="radio"/>						

17. How do you rate the quality of becoming an entrepreneur through Nigerian technical institutions?

Very poor	Poor	Acceptable	Good	Very good
<input type="radio"/>				

18. Do you agree with the following statement: You are more likely to become an entrepreneur in Nigeria if you graduate from university.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

19. What is your main motive for starting up a business?

- Educational exposure
- Opportunity
- No job

5

- Autonomy
- Responsibility to society
- Family orientation
- Generating income through business
- Passion for carrying out a childhood dream

Others, please specify

20. To what capacity do you think Nigeria needs a graduate of vocational/innovation training institutions?

- Definitely would
- Probably would
- Probably would not
- Definitely would not

21. Do you feel that your course of study in Nigeria helps you succeed in business?

- Extremely helpful
- Very helpful
- Somewhat helpful
- Not so helpful
- Not at all helpful

22. Did you agree that being educated helps nurture long-term business relationships?

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Somewhat agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Somewhat disagree
- Disagree

6

- Strongly disagree

23. What is your gender?

- Female
- Male

Other (please specify)

24. To which age group do you belong?

- Under 18
- 18-24
- 25-34
- 35-44
- 45-54
- 55-64
- 65+

7

